

ATTI DEL MUSEO DI STORIA NATURALE DELLA MAREMMA

N. 25 - 31 DICEMBRE 2021

PROCEEDINGS OF "FAUNA 2020",
THE ITALIAN NATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON THE EUROPEAN WILDCAT
DEDICATED TO THE MEMORY OF
PROF. BERNARDINO BACCHI

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25

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Cover image:

One of the European wildcats that Bernardino Ragni rescued and studied in Spoleto (Villa Redenta).

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BERNARDINO RAGNI AND THE WILDCAT OF THE OLD WORLD

BERNARDINO RAGNI E IL GATTO SELVATICO DEL VECCHIO MONDO

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Abstract. The conference ‘The European wildcat in Italy: current knowledge and future prospects’ is the first thematic national meeting of a series of annual events called ‘Fauna’ dedicated to the figure of the zoologist Bernardino Ragni. The meetings started in 2019 with a conference dealing with the person and career of Prof. Ragni one year after his death, and are strongly supported by the Ragni family, the Municipality of Spoleto and the Professor’s colleagues and former students. The paper describes the figure of Prof. Bernardino Ragni, commemorating his dedication to research over his entire life and, in particular, to the iconic species he devoted most of his time and energies to, namely the European wildcat.

Riassunto. Il convegno ‘Il gatto selvatico europeo in Italia: conoscenze attuali e prospettive future’ è il primo incontro nazionale tematico inserito in una serie di eventi annuali denominati “Fauna” dedicati allo zoologo Bernardino Ragni. Gli incontri, avviati nel 2019 con un convegno sulla figura di Ragni ad un anno dalla sua scomparsa, sono fortemente voluti dalla famiglia Ragni, dal Comune di Spoleto e dai colleghi ed ex studenti del Professore. L’articolo descrive la figura del Prof. Bernardino Ragni, per commemorare la sua dedizione alla ricerca e, in particolare, alla specie iconica a cui ha dedicato la maggior parte del suo tempo e delle sue energie: il gatto selvatico europeo.

PREFACE

Why dedicate an annual event to the figure of Bernardino Ragni, why in Spoleto and why choose the European wildcat as the subject of the first scientific conference?

Bernardino Ragni is part of that group of Italian scientists, naturalists and zoologists who, starting from the 1960’s, sowed the first seeds of scientific environmentalism, saw them sprout, took care of the new plants allowing them to grow, saw the first leaves blossom and bear the first fruits. He took care that the seeds were dispersed in all directions, that they colonized different sectors of human activities, generating new thinking and critical minds, giving way to an environmental awareness which has never reached useless harmful extremes. His scientific ideas and methodological approaches spread both locally, nationally and internationally. He dedicated every moment of his life to the accurate observation and critical analysis of numerous aspects of nature and human life, never separating one from the other.

PERSONAL NOTES

Bernardino Ragni was born and lived in Spoleto (PG), a city he loved, in the Region he adored - Umbria, Italy, for which he felt a strong and contrasting feeling of love and hate. Love for the beauty of nature, history, culture and art that characterize this country, hate for any form

of mismanagement of its paramount potential. In Spoleto he took his first steps as a naturalist and zoologist. In Spoleto he served the civil society as an administrator, holding the position of Councillor for Urban Planning in the years 1995-2000. Famous at the time was his denial to the request to plug a ‘niche’ in the thick walls of an old farmhouse under renovation, because a barn owl was nesting there. He fought to include in the staff of the Municipality of Spoleto the figure, perhaps unique in Italy, of a Naturalist, who gives advice on every political decision involving the environment.

The Mountains around Spoleto saw his blossoming as a scientist, and as a zoologist he traveled far and wide in this area, in all seasons, for many years, making them his open-air laboratory. In these mountains, in the late sixties and early seventies, he began to carry out researches on the European wildcat, then an almost completely unknown animal, which he studied for 50 years. Ragni became the greatest expert on this taxon in Italy and developed several national and international collaborations.

Thanks to his figure and activity, it was decided to dedicate to the Late Bernardino Ragni an annual scientific event, to be held in Spoleto. In 2020 the conference was dedicated to *Felis silvestris silvestris*. Over ten speakers described the state of the art on this elusive carnivore in Italy.

This contribution aims to retrace the scientific career of the Late Bernardino Ragni in short stages.

Born in 1946, by the age of 14 he had already

begun to explore the mountains around Spoleto, driven by his strong curiosity. In 1968 this curiosity is flanked by a scientific approach and so began his scientific activity. Mainly two taxa attracted his attention: the wildcat (*Felis silvestris*) and the golden eagle (*Aquila chrysaetos*). In this context, we will deal with the former.

THE SCIENTIFIC WORK OF BERNARDINO RAGNI

Right from the start, in the late sixties-early seventies, Bernardino Ragni dealt with four aspects relating to *Felis silvestris*: distribution, eco-ethology, morphology, morphometry and genetics.

Concerning the first two, he mainly used two methods: survey-interview and field data collection. The surveys-interviews included those categories of people who, for pleasure or for their job, could come in contact with the species of interest. Hunters first of all, but also breeders-farmers, nature enthusiasts, practitioners and researchers working in Natural History Museums, State Forests Administrations and Universities. There are many statements, mainly from hunters, reported in his notes. Very often they were embellished with side comments, useful to grasp one of his strongest character aspects: being direct, without filters, towards everyone. The field research was carried out in person, often accompanied by his first wife, friends and colleagues. He faithfully reported everything observed in his usual field notebook, often accompanying the text with drawings of the environment, burrows, footprints, tracks and drawings of the coats of the cats he observed.

In 1972 he published "The cat of the woods", his first popular publication, including all the information on the European wildcat personally collected to date.

He carried out ethological observations in captivity on wildcats found injured, animals he tried to recover in order to release them back into the wild. Over the years, several individuals, of both sexes and all ages, have been hosted and nursed. This allowed him to define the basis for the description of the ethogram of the European wildcat; to detect differences in the coat pattern and to define a method to estimate the age of individuals.

There are also numerous wildcats that he recovered dead (shot, poisoned or hit by cars). The corpses, sad evidences of individuals being subtracted from the wild populations, were nevertheless a precious source of data: morphological (coat colour and pattern markings), morphometric (measures such as head-trunk length, tail length, gut length, cranial capacity, etc.), ecological (diet in particular) and obviously

distributive, (the locality of origin for each corpse was noted).

The first ethological publication dates back to 1977, 'Observations on the wildcat in captivity'. The following year Prof. Ragni published 'Observation on the ecology and behavior of the wildcat (*Felis silvestris* Schreber) in Italy', his first international paper.

In 1981 he published for the Italian National Council of Research (CNR) the fact sheet 'The wildcat', within the framework of the wider publication 'Distribution and biology of 22 mammal species in Italy,' which became the handbook that he distributed to anyone willing to approach this taxon.

In the second half of the Eighties he started a fruitful and long-lasting collaboration with Ettore Randi, geneticist of the then National Institute for Wild Fauna (INFS). The first scientific outputs are from 1986: 'First results of the electrophoretic analysis of a sample of Italian populations of wildcat and domestic cat' and 'Multivariate analysis of craniometric characters in European Wildcat, Domestic cat and African wildcat (Genus *Felis*)'.

As already mentioned, the research on the wildcat does not only concern the Umbria region, but it extended over a large part of the country. In 1987 two publications regarding two geographically distant areas of Italy were published: one about Sicily 'The wildcat: knowledge and conservation of a species. News on the lynx and the wolf' written in collaboration with S. Seminara; and the other about the North-East 'Current situation of the wildcat (*Felis silvestris*) and of the lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in the area of the south-eastern Alps', marking the start of other very important collaborations, namely those with the researchers Luca Lapini and Franco Perco.

In the same year, Ragni launched the longest project of his career; the reintroduction of the European wildcat in the Maremma Regional Park. A project that continued in alternate phases until 2006. It began with the involvement of collaborators who at that time were students or new graduates and who would later have become valid and historical collaborators of Ragni: Mariagrazia Possenti, Marina Gigante and Andrea Sforzi. The project in Maremma acted also as the 'cradle' that helped to 'raise' most of the other researchers who collaborated with Ragni for many years: Alberto Sangiuliano, Domenico Cristofari, Marco Catello, Christian Losso, Daniele Paoloni, Andrea Mandrici, Lolita Bizzarri, Roberta Mazzei and Anna Maria Fabrizi. Some of these researchers are still engaged in projects dealing with the species. The project produced publications and the results were presented at national and international conferences from 1996 to 2017.

Since the beginning of his career, scientific research for Prof. Ragni has never been an end in itself. The knowledge acquired and the results obtained in his studies have always primarily represented a useful tool in wildlife management. In 1988 the work ‘Analysis of genetic variability in some species of carnivores and management applications’ was published, in collaboration with Ettore Randi.

After almost twenty years of studies, in 1990 he finally published ‘Contribution to the ethogram of *Felis silvestris* Schreber, 1777’.

His collaboration with the geneticist Ettore Randi became closer and closer and in 1991, they jointly published ‘Genetic Variability and Biochemical Systematics of Domestic and Wildcat Populations (*Felis silvestris*: Felidae)’.

Compiling all the information available at that time on the presence of *Felis silvestris*, at national level in 1994 Ragni, (together with Possenti, Sforzi, Zavaloni and Ciani) published an article that for many years lasted as a milestone on the distribution of the European wildcat in Italy: ‘The Wildcat in Central-Northern Italian peninsula: a biogeographical dilemma’.

The second milestone was published in 1996, in collaboration with M. Possenti: ‘Variability of coat-color and marking system in *Felis silvestris*’. This is a reference paper, still used today to phenotypically distinguish the European wildcat from the African wildcat and the domestic cat.

In 1997 Prof. Ragni’s research on the European wildcat stepped beyond the Italian borders and reached Crete. The wildcat on the island were thought to be extinct, as the last sighting dated back to the 50’s. The research involving two students (Alessandra Belardinelli and Paola Cicconi) under the coordination of Andrea Sforzi and in collaboration with P. Lymberakis (Natural History Museum of Crete), brought the capture of an adult male on the Greek island. It was released and his movements were followed through a radiotelemetry study. In 1999 Ragni published ‘The Carnivores on the Island of Crete, Greece’, together with the two students, the local researcher T. Roussos and his colleague M. Masseti.

In 2001, the development of a protocol to genetically distinguish the wildcat from the domestic cat was published: ‘Genetic identification of wild and domestic cats (*Felis silvestris*), and their hybrids using Bayesian clustering method’, together with E. Randi, M. Pierpaoli, M. Beaumont and A. Sforzi.

In 2007 a research programme through camera trapping was launched in Sicily, in collaboration with Stefano Anile. The project led, three years later, to a first estimate of the Sicilian population:

‘Estimation of European wildcat population size in Sicily (Italy) using camera trapping and capture – recapture analyze’.

In the same year, under the coordination of Lolita Bizzarri and in collaboration with Moreno Lacrimini, a project of trapping and studying eco-ethology of the European wildcat through radio telemetry was launched in one of the historical areas of presence of the species in the Apennines. Outputs from the project included a protocol for the trapping method used, published in the 2010 paper: ‘Live capture and handling of the European wildcat in central Italy’.

Fieldwork has always been complemented by laboratory studies. Collaboration with Francesca Vercillo enabled numerous necropsies to be carried out, and samples collected for genetic analysis, like those, that allowed the 2013 publication ‘Genetic structure of wildcat (*Felis silvestris*) populations in Italy’.

In 2017, the paper ‘Home-range size of the European wildcat (*Felis silvestris silvestris*): a report from two areas in Central Italy’ was published. The work provided a summary and a comparison of the telemetry studies carried out on the species in two areas of Central Italy- the Apennines and Maremma, representing the two projects that Ragni probably cared most about.

CONCLUSIONS

To sum up, the main results obtained by Prof. Ragni in almost 50 years of scientific research on *Felis silvestris* are:

- the description of the Italian wildcat populations (with particular reference to morphological, genetic, health, ethological aspects and the main conservation problems);
- the reintroduction in the Maremma Regional Park (including a radio telemetry study on the first and subsequent generations);
- the biogeography of the Italian wildcat populations;
- radio telemetry study on an ‘historical’ population in the Apennines.

Bernardino Ragni did not only study wildcats. He was a multifaceted zoologist, who always took the widest ecological perspective. Among the taxa he dealt with can be listed: the golden eagle (his second totemic animal), Eurasian lynx, wolf, beech marten, stone marten, chiroptera, wild boar, ungulates in general, micro-mammals, reptiles and amphibians.

There are over 140 scientific publications bearing his name, of which more than 60 are on *Felis silvestris*. He was a Professor at the University

of Perugia, holding courses on Vertebrate Zoology, Zoogeography and Wildlife Management. Over 30 students and collaborators took part in his research activities over the years.

This wealth of knowledge, skills and interpersonal relationships deserves to be valued. Some of his closest collaborators continue, in his name, some of the work started by Ragni, in order to ensure that what has been sown continues to bear fruit.

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“QUI GATTA CI COVA”¹
A SHORT NATURAL HISTORY OF *FELIS SILVESTRIS* SCHREBER, 1777, IN ITALY

“QUI GATTA CI COVA”¹
BREVE STORIA NATURALE DI *FELIS SILVESTRIS* SCHREBER, 1777, IN ITALIA

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Abstract. A most highly successful carnivore, the wildcat, *Felis silvestris* Schreber, 1777, is today dispersed from the south-central Palearctic Biogeographic Region to the Afro-tropical and Oriental Regions, where several subspecies are recognised. Paleontological evidence suggests that this felid maintains almost unchanged its biological model starting from, at least, the Upper Pliocene and/or the Lower Pleistocene. The Italian territory is among the few in Europe inhabited by two different wildcats: the European wildcat, *Felis silvestris silvestris* Schreber, 1777, dispersed in continental Italy and Sicily, and the African wildcat, *Felis silvestris libyca* Forster, 1780, which occurs in Sardinia (and Corsica) where it has been introduced by man, very likely in protohistoric times. Recent observations indicate a widening of the range of the species within the national boundaries. Though the felid was known for a long time in the western ecumene, it seems that in Italy the domestic cat may not have become fully widespread until the establishment of the Islamic culture. Since ancient times, the repeated inbreeding of domestic cats with wild individuals has eventually altered the genetic and phenotypic characteristics of the Italian population of the species.

Riassunto. Uno dei carnivori di maggiore successo, il gatto selvatico, *Felis silvestris* Schreber, 1777, è oggi disperso dalla Regione Biogeografica Paleartica centro-meridionale alle Regioni afro-tropicali e orientali, dove sono riconosciute diverse sottospecie. Evidenze paleontologiche suggeriscono che questo felide mantenga pressoché inalterato il suo modello biologico a partire, almeno, dal Pliocene superiore e/o dal Pleistocene inferiore. Il territorio italiano è tra i pochi in Europa abitato da due diversi gatti selvatici: il gatto selvatico europeo, *Felis silvestris silvestris* Schreber, 1777, disperso nell'Italia continentale e in Sicilia, e il gatto selvatico africano, *Felis silvestris libyca* Forster, 1780, presente in Sardegna (e Corsica) dove è stato introdotto dall'uomo, molto probabilmente in epoca protostorica. Recenti osservazioni indicano un ampliamento dell'areale della specie all'interno dei confini nazionali. Nonostante il felino fosse conosciuto da molto tempo nell'ecumene occidentale, sembra che in Italia il gatto domestico possa non essere diventato pienamente diffuso fino all'affermarsi della cultura islamica. Fin dall'antichità, i ripetuti incroci tra gatti domestici e individui selvatici hanno alla fine alterato le caratteristiche genetiche e fenotipiche della popolazione italiana della specie.

INTRODUCTION

THE WILDCAT, *Felis silvestris* Schreber, 1777, can be regarded as one of the most biologically successful carnivore (CLUTTON-BROCK 1981), when success is measured in terms of geographical and ecological size of the range (cf. RAGNI *et al.* 1993; MASSETI 2012). According to DRISCOLL *et al.* (2007) and OTTONI *et al.* (2017), the species would be divided into at least 5 groups. Genetic and morphometric investigations have confirmed that these groups belong to the same polymorphic species, differentiating only at a sub-specific level (RAGNI & POSSENTI 1991; HEMMER 1999; YAMAGUCHI

et al. 2004; RANDI 2010, and references therein; cf. MATTUCCI 2014; OTTONI *et al.* 2017). These are dispersed from the south-central Palearctic Region to the Afro-tropical and Oriental Regions, occurring in a broad spectrum of habitats, from deciduous woodland to savannah and steppe and sub-desert zones, as well as coniferous forest (cf. KUMERLOEVE 1967; HUS 1974; HARRISON 1968; GASPARETTI *et al.* 1985; HARRISON & BATES 1991). Wild populations interbreed intensively with domestic individuals throughout their vast range (MASSETI 2000, and references therein; YAMAGUCHI *et al.* 2004), and today the domestic cat is, together with the dog, the most widespread carnivore in the world.

¹ This is an Italian proverb that translates literally the sentence “*here (female) cat hatches there*”, with the meaning of “*I don't know, there's something there!*”.

Fig. 1 - If a metric comparison could not be made, the extreme morphological affinity between the mandible of a lion and that of a cat highlights the difficulty in distinguishing the two species (photo by Saulo Bambi; courtesy Zoological Museum "La Specola" of the University of Florence)

The wildcat represents a biological model common to most species of the Felidae family, regardless of their size and destined to last over a very long chronological period. This would make it not so easy to distinguish the skeletal morphology of a cat from that of a lion, *Panthera leo* L., 1758, if a metric comparison could not be made (Fig. 1). Actually, the species of the genus *Panthera*

Oken, 1816, differ from the smaller felids (genus *Felis* L., 1758, *Priolainurus* Severtzov, 1858, etc.) for some morphological characters, such as the partial ossification of the hyoid apparatus and the substitution of the ceratoid with an elastic bundle, that allow them to roar, but to purr only in exhalation (GRZIMEK *et al.* 1972). When eating, the smaller species stand upright on their legs, while the others lie on the ground and do not hold the food tight with the forelimbs (GRZIMEK *et al.* 1972). The most diffused biological model- characterised by long tail, short ears and a slender body - in the Felidae family repeats itself, varying from the wildcat to the tiger, *Panthera tigris* (L., 1758), and passing through the Pallas' cat, *Otocolobus manul* (Pallas, 1776), the fishing cat, *Prionailurus viverrinus* (Bennett, 1833), the margay, *Leopardus wiedii* (Schinz, 1821), the ocelot, *Leopardus pardalis* (L., 1758), and many others. Somewhat different from this biological model is instead that of the caracal, *Caracal caracal* (Schreber, 1776), the serval, *Leptailurus serval* (Schreber, 1776), or the lynxes (genus *Lynx* Kerr, 1792), characterised by long ears and shorter tails.

EARLY WILDCATS OF THE EUROPEAN SUBCONTINENT

The appearance of wildcats in the fossiliferous horizons of the Western Palearctic is very ancient, perhaps dating back to the final part of the Upper Pliocene or the beginning of the Pleistocene (KURTÉN 1968), almost two million years ago. The remains of the oldest wildcat, *Felis lunensis* Martelli, 1906, from the Villafranchian (Upper Pliocene) fossiliferous horizons of the site of Olivola in Val di Magra (north-western Tuscany) (MARTELLI 1906; STEHLIN 1933), show a great morphological affinity with the extant European wildcat, *Felis silvestris*

Fig. 2 - Partial mandible of the Upper Pliocene *Felis lunensis* Martelli, 1906, from the Villafranchian site of Olivola (Val di Magra, north-western Tuscany), on the left, compared to the mandible of a present day wildcat, *F. silvestris* Schreber, 1777. The original of this last drawing was made on the basis of specimens from the surroundings of Spoleto, kindly made available to the work of Ficarelli & Torre (1974) by Bernardino Ragni (from Ficarelli & Torre, 1974, redesigned)

silvestris Schreber, 1777 (FICCARELLI & TORRE 1974) (Fig. 2). The holotype specimen is now preserved in the palaeontological collection of the University of Florence, in Italy. Another cat osteological fragment was described by Depéret from the Lower Pliocene of Perpignan in France, but it was so much like the extant African wild cat, *F. s. lybica* Forster, 1780, that the author did not propose a special name for it. According to Zeuner (1963), it cannot be, therefore, excluded that the ancestral line of our cat begins with Depéret's felid and passes through Martelli's species to the wildcats of the Pleistocene of Eurasia and Africa. The morphotype could have already settled down in the ancient Pleistocene and, since then, all European wildcat osteological findings would be related to the same single species. In fact, according to Ficarelli & Torre (1974), *F. lunensis* does not differ from the European wildcat and at the most can be considered a subspecies of it. Even the remains found at Lunel Viel (France) by Bonifay (1971), who described them as belonging to the new species *F. monspessulana*, have to be ascribed to the former taxon (FICCARELLI & TORRE 1974). The conservation of the biological model "*Felis silvestris*", which has lasted from the Lower Pleistocene to the present day, would therefore confirm its evolutionary validity, revealing not only its great morphological strength, but also its ethological and genetic stability (RAGNI *et al.* 1995). The biological success of the wildcat can be evaluated also in consideration of the great extension of its geographical diffusion - equivalent

if not superior, within the Felidae family, only to that of the leopard, *Panthera pardus* L., 1758 (WOZENCRAFT 2005; JDEIDI *et al.* 2010) - and of the consequent ecological variations of the area.

Three main subspecies are recognised within its Western Palaearctic range. The European subcontinent, the Caucasus, and Asia Minor are interested by the diffusion of the European wildcat, whereas the African wildcat, is found in northern and Saharan Africa, several Mediterranean islands, and in the Near East, including the Arabian peninsula (MASSETI 2000, 2009b and 2010; YAMAGUCHI *et al.* 2004; DRISCOLL *et al.* 2007). The easternmost area of distribution of the species, which includes Transcaucasia, Central Asia and part of the Indian subcontinent, is instead occupied by the Asiatic wildcat, *F. s. ornata* Gray, 1832 (YAMAGUCHI *et al.* 2004; OTTONI *et al.* 2017), which is characterised by a very peculiar spotted coat. In the ancient Western World, animals of the latter subspecies are perhaps evoked in the artistic representation of an *opus vermiculatum* of the late Roman Republican era (first quarter of the 1st century BC; Rome, National Roman Museum - Palazzo Massimo), or in a mosaic detail from the "House of the Faun" (1st century AD) in the dead city of Pompeii (Naples, Museo Archeologico Nazionale) (Fig. 3). The ancient diffusion of the Asian subspecies beyond its homeland may be also documented in several medieval artistic productions, such as a miniature of the mid-15th century *Master of Game* by Edward duke

Fig. 3 - Detail of a floor mosaic from the House of the Faun (Pompeii), showing a probable Asiatic wildcat, *Felis silvestris ornata* Gray, 1832 (1st century AD; Naples, National Archaeological Museum)

of York (Oxford, Bodleian Library: MS Bodley 546, fol 40 verso) (Fig. 4), English translation of the 14th century *Livre de Chasse* by Gaston Phébus (MASSETI 2011; cf. WALKER-MEIKLE 2011). Once regarded as separate taxonomic entities, all these subspecies are now considered to belong to a single polytypical species (HARRISON 1981; HARRISON & BATES 1991; CORBET & HILL 1992; WOZENCRAFT, 2005). Despite their wide diffusion, they are morphologically very similar and there are no constant craniological differences between them (POCOCK 1951; HEPTNER & SLUDSKII 1992).

DIFFUSION OF THE EUROPEAN WILDCAT IN CONTINENTAL ITALY

In Italy, the European wildcat is dispersed over a large part of the mainland, where it is characterised by four genetically differentiated groups (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2013). Up to about twenty-fifteen years ago, its distribution was reputed to interest the majority of the peninsula from Aspromonte (southern Calabria) to the central Apennines, south of an ideal borderline that roughly joined the town of Piombino on the Tyrrhenian coast, to Ancona on the Adriatic Gulf (RAGNI *et al.* 1994; cf. CAGNOLARO *et al.* 1976). Studies carried out by CRUDELE *et al.* (2001), AGOSTINI *et al.* (2010), RAGNI & PETRUZZI (2010), SANTOLINI *et al.* (2010); RAGNI *et al.* (2014), MATTUCCI *et al.* (2013), VELLI *et al.* (2015), and VELLI *et al.* (2018) in the area of the Riserve Naturali Biogenetiche Casentinesi have revealed the presence of a population of the

carnivore in the territories of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona and Campigna National Park (northern Tuscany), ascertaining a process of recent expansion of the European wildcat in the Italian peninsula. More recent reports would give the presence of wild individuals in even more northern and western areas of Tuscany, including the territory of Mugello (Andrea Sforzi, 2020 *in verbis*, and in the present volume). There is a second population in the Eastern Alps, which appears to belong to the large Dinaric-Balkan core that extends to the countries of former Yugoslavia, Romania, Bulgaria, Greece, Slovakia, Hungary, Ukraine and southern Poland (CAGNOLARO *et al.* 1976; HEMMER 1999; BASHTA & POTISH, 2005; HELTAI *et al.* 2006; RAGNI & PETRUZZI 2010; LOZANO & MALO 2012). A further population is still found in the Gargano promontory (northern Apulia) (CAGNOLARO *et al.* 1976), where it appears to be ecologically isolated (RAGNI & PETRUZZI 2010). Records from western Liguria and Piedmont seem also favorable to the return of the species from the adjacent French territories (CAGNOLARO *et al.* 1976; RAGNI 1981; GAVAGNIN *et al.* 2010; GAVAGNIN *et al.* 2018; Patrizia Gavagnin, 2020 *in verbis*) (Fig. 5).

The absence of the European wildcat from a large portion of the north-central Italian peninsula is not easy to explain. It may be a consequence of the great anthropisation that affected these territories, in relatively recent historical times. This fact, together with the habitat alteration, may have favoured the abnormal spread of inbreeding with the domestic form, seriously diluting the wild phenotypic and

Fig. 4 - Detail of an illuminated page of the 15th century *Master of Game* by Edward, Duke of York, English translation of the *Livre de Chasse* by Gaston Phébus (Oxford, Bodleian Library: MS Bodley 546, fol 40 verso) (cf. Masseti, 2011)

genetic traits until they disappear. Other carnivores have revealed large gaps in their Italian range for long periods of the last century. We must not forget that the former human impact on these same territories has led to the disappearance of the wolf, *Canis lupus* L., 1758. This species reached the minimum of its historical occurrence in Italy in 1970s (SIMONETTA 1968; TASSI 1971; ZIMEN & BOITANI 1975), being already disappeared from the entire central-northern Apennines between 39°N and 43°N of latitude (CIUCCI & BOITANI, 2003, and references therein). Even the fox, *Vulpes vulpes* (L., 1758), was for a long time absent from a large portion of Italy, roughly coinciding with the Po plain (Pianura Padana), from the surroundings of Turin to the Adriatic Gulf, where the species progressively reappeared only during the 1980s (BOITANI, 1981; BOITANI & CIUCCI 2003). This disappearance could be attributed to the combined action of the excessive anthropisation and urbanisation, assiduous control of fox populations on the part of the farmers, and intensive exploitation of all lowland farming environments (cf. BOITANI 1981). At present, the diffusion of the fox appears almost continuous throughout continental Italy, except for a few areas that have yet to be recolonised in the central Po valley (BOITANI & CIUCCI 2003).

The diffusion of *F. s. silvestris* in the Italian mainland interests a wide variety of habitats, which vary both in altitude and latitude. The species is primarily associated with forest and is found in highest numbers in broad-leaved or mixed forests with low densities of humans (cf. NOWELL *et al.* 2010). Oak and beech forests are, as a general rule, the forest biocenoses where European wildcat populations reach optimal densities and are more stable (RAGNI 1981). Its altitudinal dispersion can reach 2,250 m above sea level (GARCÍA-PEREA, 2002). The carnivore is also found in Mediterranean scrubland, riparian forest, marsh boundaries and along sea coasts, but areas of intensive cultivation are avoided. In north-eastern Italy, the extant expansion of the European wildcat seems to be clearly related to the return of the forest, which in the last 40 years has come back to cover the orographic reliefs due to the abandonment of numerous traditional agricultural, zootechnical and silvicultural practices (LAPINI 2006). This would have created favourable conditions for the growth of many forest mammalian populations, which at the end of the 1970s reached high densities even in the areas bordering the plains, thus being able to serve as a reservoir for the colonisation of the latter. The most evident case studied in north-eastern Italy is certainly that of the roe deer, *Capreolus capreolus* (L., 1758) (see Perco, 1987), but during the 1980s and 1990s also the Eurasian badger, *Meles meles* (L., 1758), and the red squirrel, *Sciurus vulgaris* L.,

Fig. 5 - Present distribution of wildcats in Italy and adjacent regions (data from Ragni, 1981; Ragni *et al.*, 1993; Hemmer, 1999; Masseti, 2010; Ragni & Petruzzi, 2010; Gavagnin *et al.*, 2010; Lozano & Malo, 2012; Velli *et al.*, 2015; Gavagnin *et al.*, 2018, and Velli *et al.*, 2018)

1758, have invaded the plains, reaching the sea also along the high Adriatic coasts in the last 30 years. According to Lapini (2006), the model followed for these colonisation seems to be always the same, with the autonomous movement of animals along the main river floodplains, whose function as ecological corridors seems even more remarkable than previously assumed. Very recently, the wild cat has also reached some insular environments, as in the case of the river island *Isola della Cona* at the mouth of the river Isonzo, in the northern Adriatic Gulf (VITIELLO 2020) (Fig. 6).

The distribution of the felid on the circum-Italian islands, including Corsica, deserves however a separate discussion.

INSULAR WILDCATS

Apart from continental islands such as Sicily and Corfu (Greece) where fossil bones of wildcats have been discovered in Upper Pleistocene contexts (MARINOS, 1971; MARINOS & SYMEONODIS 1977; DERMITZAKIS & SONDAAR 1978; MASSETI 2010 and 2012), felids do not figure in the late Quaternary faunal assemblages of the Mediterranean archipelagos (cf. MASSETI & MAZZA 1996; MASSETI 2012). These carnivores seem to have never undergone endemic modifications on islands

Fig. 6 - The recent occurrence of the European wildcat has been documented through a photo trap on the river island *Isola della Cona* at the mouth of the river Isonzo, in the northern Adriatic Gulf (from Vitiello, 2020)

(MAZZA *et al.* 2013). In fact, the differences between insular felids and their mainland ancestors never range beyond the subspecific level (cf. MASUDA & YOSHIDA 1995). Neontological data can show that more resource-demanding hypercarnivores (i.e., those with more than 70% of their diet consisting of meat) are more vulnerable on islands than are meso- (meat between 50% and 70% of their diet) and hypocarnivores (meat less than 50% of their diet) and that they rapidly disappear (O'REGAN *et al.* 2002). It seems therefore that, despite the undoubted swimming abilities of many felids, such as tigers, *Panthera tigris* (L., 1758), jaguars, *Panthera onca* (L., 1758), fishing cats, *Prionailurus viverrinus* (Bennett 1833), or leopard cats, *P. bengalensis* (Kerr 1792), the representatives of this taxonomic group show no endemic adaptations to insular life.

In the light of this, the extant wildcat of Sicily does not seem to differ substantially from its counterpart of continental Italy, if not for some minor phenotypic characters that allowed it to be regarded as a distinct geographic variety (MORABITO, 1987; RAGNI & SEMINARA 1987; RAGNI *et al.* 1995; DI VITTORIO & FALCONE 2008; SIRACUSA 2010; ANILE *et al.* 2014), perhaps an ecotype. Nevertheless, the scientific community has not yet felt the need to describe it at a sub-specific level (cf. RAGNI & SEMINARA 1987).

Together with the British population and, possibly, that of few other continental islands, the Sicilian one is the only European insular population of *F. s. silvestris*. There are no biogeographical elements such as to rule out the possibility of the penetration of this species onto the large Mediterranean island during an unspecified moment of the last glacial episode (see BURGIO 1997), in concomitance with the entry of the remaining mainland fauna of the so-called "Stadio di Castello". The wildcat, however, has never been described among the typical species of the latter faunistic stage (KOTSAKIS 1978; TAGLIACOZZO 1993; VILLARI, 1995). According to Villari (1995), although considering the exiguity and fragmentary of the available archaeological findings, no difference in the osteological morphology of the Sicilian specimens would have been found compared to the continental ones. Only the phenotypic characters of the coat (pattern and colours) of the Sicilian population show some differentiation from the more recurrent continental patterns: increase in eumelanin, detectable in the design and background colour and increase in the white gular, inguinal and digital areas (RAGNI & SEMINARA 1987) (Fig. 7). As far as is presently known, the most ancient remains of *F. silvestris* found in Sicily date between the late Upper Pleistocene and the beginning of the

Holocene, and are documented by findings made in the transition levels between the Mesolithic and Neolithic fauna horizons of the Cave of Uzzo (Trapani) (TAGLIACOZZO 1993). Osteological fragments of the species have also been reported from the Cave of Corruggi (Corruggi, Syracuse), the Neolithic Cave of Stentinello (Syracuse) (VILLARI 1995), and the site of Rocca Palumba. The bones of wildcats are, however, rather rare in Sicilian pre-Neolithic deposits (KOTSAKIS, 1978; TAGLIACOZZO, 1993; VILLARI, 1995; BURGIO, 1997).

Sicily is the only Mediterranean island inhabited by European wildcats while all the other islands are characterised by the occurrence of populations with the phenotypes of the African wildcat (TOSCHI, 1965; CAGNOLARO *et al.* 1976; AZZAROLI, 1977; MASSETI, 1993, 2012). The latter appears to have been exported beyond its natural distribution after it had already experienced some sort of human cultural control since ancient times (MASSETI, 2010, 2012, and references therein). Taxonomists described the felid present in Sardinia as the subspecies *F. silvestris cf. sarda* Lataste, 1885, while the Corsican population

Fig. 7 - Adult male Sicilian wildcat, captured with a photographic trap on the slopes of Mount Etna (photo by Stefano Anile). The black-brilliant pattern of the dorsal colour contrasts with the light-silver background and is a phenotypical trait of the Sicilian population

was assigned to *F. silvestris cf. rey* Lavauden, 1929 (RAGNI, 1981; ARRIGI & SALOTTI 1988; SALOTTI 1992; STAHL & LEGER 1992). The evidence suggests that African wildcats were imported voluntarily by man onto Sardinia and Corsica, that have not been characterised by the Quaternary occurrence of any felid (VIGNE 1988 and 1992; MASSETI 1993; ANGELICI & MASSETI 2003). In fact, these carnivores would not have been able to pass unobserved on board the small boats employed by humans to reach Sardinia and Corsica (*cf.* VIGNE & ALCOVER 1985; MASSETI 1995). The appearance of the wildcat in the former island seems to have occurred prior to the Roman occupation, but probably not before the end of the Iron Age (MASSETI & VIANELLO 1991; MASSETI 1993; *cf.* WILKENS 2003). In Corsica, this introduction may have happened perhaps earlier (VIGNE 1992). In the eastern Mediterranean, the introduction of *F. silvestris* is associated with the cultural horizons of the Pre-Ceramic Neolithic, between the end of the 9th and the 8th millennium BC (VIGNE *et al.* 2004).

Also the extant occurrence of felids which fall within the phenotypic characters of the African wild cat on Mallorca, Crete, and a few other Aegean islands, such as Amorgos and Rhodes (Fig. 8), can be essentially attributed to a more or less ancient human mediation (MASSETI 2012; CHEKE & ASHCROFT 2017) (Fig. 9). Concerning the importation of medium-sized allochthonous carnivores in the insular and continental Western World, we must not forget the diffusion of the domestic cat, the more consistent spread of which appears to coincide with human cultures destined to affirm themselves many millennia later (MASSETI 2009a, 2010 and 2016).

THE DOMESTICATION OF THE CAT

“... *an animal that always keeps something wild in itself, nor can it be completely domesticated*”

(G. Soderini, 1526-1597, *Il trattato degli animali domestici*: 199)

While it would seem that both the Near Eastern and Egyptian populations of *Felis silvestris* contributed to the original gene pool of all the extant domestic breeds (OTTONI *et al.* 2017; *cf.* LINSELEE *et al.* 2009), in prehistoric China the ancestors of the domestic cat appear to have derived from another species, the already mentioned leopard cat, tamed between 5,500 and 4,900 years BP (VIGNE *et al.* 2016). This is a medium-sized felid dispersed in a wide variety of habitats in Asia, from tropical rainforest to temperate broadleaf and, marginally, coniferous forest, as well as shrub forest and successional grasslands (CORBET & HILL 1992; FRANCIS 2008;

Fig. 8 - Present distribution of the wildcat in the Mediterranean region. 1) *Felis silvestris jordansi* Schwarz, 1930 (Mallorca); 2) *F. s. rey* Lavauden, 1929 (Corsica); *F. s. sarda* Lataste, 1885 (Sardinia); *F. s. silvestris* (Schreber, 1777); 5) *F. s. libyca* (Forster, 1780); 6) *F. s. cretensis* Haltenorth, 1953 (Crete); 7) the wildcat of Rhodes? ; 8) the wildcat of Amorgos (from Masseti, 2020, modified)

Ross *et al.* 2015). It is found through parts of the Indian subcontinent (Habibi, 2004), the Himalayan foothills, most of China, north to the Korean peninsula and into the Russian Far East (NOWELL & JACKSON 1996; IUCN Cat Specialist Group, 2002). Leopard cats are excellent swimmers, and have successfully colonised offshore islands throughout their range which includes Sumatra, Java, Borneo, Bali, Lombok, Taiwan, and the Philippines, as well as many small offshore islands of mainland Asia (KITCHENER *et al.* 1990; NOWELL & JACKSON 1996, SUNQUIST & SUNQUIST 2002). The type specimen of the species was caught swimming in the Bay of Bengal (POCOCK 1917). The former occurrence of a carnivore with the phenotypic characters of the leopard cat has also been reported by Wallace (1869) and Tate (1944) from the Indonesian island of Timor, but needs further confirmation.

The early domestication of this felid in China should come as no surprise since the leopard cat can easily be bred in captivity and it has been hybridised with an American shorthair domestic cat in 1963 to produce the famous domestic Bengal breed (HELGREN, 2013; VIGNE *et al.* 2016) (Fig. 10). However, *P. bengalensis* does not appear to have contributed genetically to any lineages of domestic

cats living in China today (DRISCOLL *et al.* 2007; DRISCOLL *et al.* 2009; MONTAGUE *et al.* 2014; see also OTTONI *et al.* 2017). In fact, according to VIGNE *et al.* (2016), domestic cats descendants of *F. silvestris* appears to have completely replaced the leopard cat from its purported commensal role in China, at some point after the Late Neolithic. These data provide wholly new evidence for another possible history of cat domestication, not only by revealing a possible independent process in the Far East, but also by adding a new species to the pantheon of commensal and/or domestic animals who began their relationships with humans at the onset and spread of agriculture during the Holocene (VIGNE *et al.* 2016).

We have already observed that, as far as is known, the only ancestor of all the extant domestic breeds is the African wildcat (ZEUNER 1950; CLUTTON-BROCK 1981; HEMMER 1990; MALEK 1993; MASSETI 2002; RAGNI & RAGNI 2019), all descended from the latter due to artificial selection. In fact, the already noted morphological affinity of the various subspecies of *F. silvestris* does not correspond to similar ethological analogy with respect to susceptibility to domestication (RAGNI & RAGNI, 2019). Any attempt of taming or domesticating the

Fig. 9 - Adult cat characterised by the phenotype of the *F. s. lybica* group, shot on the island of Amorgos, eastern Cyclades (Greece) (photo by Anthony S. Cheke)

European wildcat has never succeeded (TOMKIES 1977, and 1991; LEYHAUSEN 1979; RAGNI 1981), while the taming and/or “relative domestication” of the African-Near Eastern wildcat has been perpetuated for millennia up to the present day (LEYHAUSEN 1979; RAGNI 1981; MENDELSSHON 1989; MASSETI 2002). The earliest certain evidence of a sort of cultural control of *F. silvestris* on the part of early human groups comes from the 9th millennium BC site of Shillourokambos on the island of Cyprus, in the eastern Mediterranean basin (VIGNE *et al.* 2004), where the species resulted completely absent among the Holocene fossil endemics (cf. BOEKSHOTEN & SONDAAR 1972). The introduction of the carnivore from somewhere in continental south-western Anatolia or the Levant may have been a deliberate act on the part of the Pre-Pottery Neolithic settlers to deal with commensal rodents (VIGNE *et al.* 2016, and references therein). Still on Cyprus, another cat remain has been found in the archaeological site of Khirokitia, dated between the end of the 7th and 6th millennium BC (DAVIS 1984 and 1987) (Fig. 11). The measurements of this specimen have confirmed that it belonged to *F. silvestris* and not to the other two species of medium-sized felids that still occur in the Near East. These are the jungle cat, *Felis chaus* Schreber, 1777, and the caracal,

Caracal caracal (Schreber, 1776) (Fig. 12). The Cypriot archaeological findings suggest a much older chronology of the domestication of the cat than the commonly accepted one according to which the felid was first domesticated in ancient Egypt (CLUTTON-BROCK, 1981 and 1988; DAVIS, 1987), at the latest by the 20th to 19th century B.C. (Middle Kingdom, 12th dynasty) (MALEK 1993).

THE DOMESTIC CAT IN ITALY

As far as is presently known, it is still rather difficult to establish the chronology of the first appearance of the domestic cat in the Western World. It has been supposed that the earliest remains of domestic cats in Italy were found in an 8th BC hut at Fidene, an Iron Age site in the surroundings of Rome (central Italy), where the complete skeleton of an adult animal, possibly trapped inside the building during its destruction, was identified (DE GROSSI MAZZORIN 1997). However, this identification is not universally accepted (Masseti 2002, and 2010). The specimen - which showed its osteological remains heavily calcined due to the probable fire of the hut - might even have been a wild animal, brought to the place of discovery from outside, such as a hunting trophy (MASSETI 2002). The possibility of

Fig. 10 - The leopard cat, *Prionailurus bengalensis* (Kerr, 1792), can easily be bred in captivity and it has been hybridised with an American shorthair domestic cat in 1963 to produce the famous domestic Bengal breed (photo by Camilla Saccardi)

dealing with a real wildcat - and not a domestic specimen - would also be favoured by the fact that the archaeological area of Fidene - as well as those of Ficana and Cures, where De Grossi Mazzorin (1989) and Ruffo (1988) respectively recognise the presence of “*other domestic felines*” - is included in the area of diffusion still occupied by the wildcat in

Fig. 11 - Cat mandible from the Pre-Ceramic Neolithic site of Khirokitia, on the island of Cyprus (photo by Odile Le Brun, courtesy of Simon J.M. Davis)

Italy (Masetti, 2010, and present work).

Undoubtedly known in classical antiquity (cf. Herodotus, *The Stories*, II: 66-67, 5th century BC), the domestic cat made its first sporadic appearances in eastern Europe from at least the start of the 6th century B.C. or, possibly, even earlier (cf. TOYNBEE 1973; MALEK 1993; MASSETI 2002). It is suggested that the felid came to Greece from Egypt, where it was an object of worship even before the 5th century B.C. (HUGHES 2003; VOULTSIADOU & TATOLAS 2005). A recent analysis of the Etruscan artistic production conducted by Ragni & Ragni (2019), only on iconographical basis, would suggest the appearance in Italy of the domestic cat between the 7th and 3rd centuries BC. Despite this, however, it seems that the animal was still uncommon in the early Roman Imperial period (KING, 2002; MASSETI, 2009a, 2010 and 2019), becoming slightly more diffused in later times (KING 1994; MACKINNON 2004). At the end of the Roman Empire it is documented more or less everywhere by scattered osteological remains. Bobis (2000) believes that its diffusion was favoured by the trade routes, in particular the tin road that linked the British Isles to the Mediterranean. The Roman army too must have represented a crucial carrier for

Fig. 12 - The measurements of the Khirokitia specimen (M_1 length, left; P_3-M_1 length, right) have confirmed that it belonged to *F. silvestris* and not to other species of medium-sized felids that occur in the Near East, such as the jungle cat, *Felis chaus* Schreber, 1777, or the caracal, *Caracal caracal* (Schreber, 1776) (from Davis, 1987, redesigned)

the penetration of the animal in northern Europe, since several fortresses guarding the Rhine-Danube *limes* were home to cats (Fig. 13). Nevertheless, according to the results of a research carried out by MacKinnon (2004), cat bones were infrequent in most Roman sites of the Italian peninsula between the Republican period and the Late Antiquity (end of the 6th century B.C. - 6th century A.D.), having been found in only 16 of the 146 rural and urban sites considered in the study (approximately 20%). Furthermore, it should be ascertained whether they were all domestic cats or whether they could include even a number of wild specimens.

In Classical Antiquity, another small-sized carnivore was preferred to the cat to be employed for the control of unwanted rodent populations,

namely the weasel, *Mustela nivalis* (L., 1766), as also documented by Bon & Masseti (1995) (Fig. 14). This animal was referred in ancient Greek as *gale* (Masseti 2002). For example, in the encomiastic poem from the 5th century B.C. *Batracomiomachia*, the mouse says to the frog: “There are two beings I fear most on earth: the hawk and the weasel”. In his comedy *The Wasps*, Aristophanes (about 445 - after 388 BC) indicates in the *gale* the domestic hunter of mice *par excellence*, not considering the cat. Still in Roman times, literary documents do not seem to assign to the cat the specialised role of domestic mice hunter. In the comedy *Stichus* (499-501) by the Latin author Plautus (259/251-184 BC approx.) is a weasel and not a cat to catch a mouse at the foot of an actor. Pliny the Elder (1st century A.D.), in his

Fig. 13 - Cat's footprints on brick from the 2nd- 3rd century archaeological context of the Roman site of Silberberg (Pförring, Eichstätt), in Germany (photo by Marco Masseti)

Naturalis historia (XXIX, 60-61), handed down to us that the weasel was allowed to walk inside the houses, where: "... according to Cicero, every day it transports its puppies and changes location..." (cf. CAPITANI & GAROFANO 1986). In antiquity, other carnivores of larger size, such as the stone marten, *Martes foina* (Erxleben, 1777, the pine marten, *Martes martes* (L., 1758), and the polecat, *Mustela putorius* L., 1758 - generically indicated by the ancient Greek term of *ictis* - were also used to defend the domestic larders from the damages produced by rodents (MASSETI 2002). In this regard there is the later witness of Pecci (1760), who explains, still in the 18th century, that on the island of Giglio, in the Tuscan archipelago (Italy), the hunt for martens was: "[...] forbidden at any time due to the fact that they have been properly introduced in ancient times because, together with the many non-poisonous snakes, they diminish the large number of mice that will otherwise devastate all the country".

Although the presence of the domestic cat in Europe is testified by a range of documents dating to the early Middle Ages prior to any

Islamic influence (cf. BOBIS 2000), it may not have become widespread until the establishment of the Arab culture (from the 8th century onwards), in concomitance with which the felid finally became more extensively diffused at least in the countries of the northern Mediterranean, its islands, and western Europe (MASSETI 2010 and 2019). A noticeable diffusion in Sicily of the felid can be traced to shortly after the year 1000 (MASSETI 2009a and 2016), vestiges having been found in the excavations at the "Antonino Salinas" Regional Archaeological Museum of Palermo, in chronological contexts referred to the second half of the 10th - early 11th century (SARÀ 1997). Prior to this discovery, the oldest Sicilian finds of domestic cats dated to the 12th century came from a pit of the castle of Fiumedinisi (VILLARI 1995) and Brucato (BOSSARD-BECK 1984). Both sites yielded remains bearing butchering cut marks and traces of burns (VILLARI 1995), as has also been documented from other Italian sites of 14th-18th century (cf. VILLARI 1995; CORBINO 2009). In Sicily, the domestic cat is also present in 13th century layers in Calathamet (SARÀ 2005), and in the 14th and 15th century contexts of Palazzo Steri, in Palermo (DI PATTI & LUPO, 2009). In the Iberian Peninsula too, the more consistent spread of the domestic cat appears to coincide with the full affirmation of Islamic culture (MASSETI 2009a and 2019). Finds referred to the carnivore have been yielded by the exploration of the Spanish sites of Granada (Califal period, 10th-11th century) (RIQUELME 1992), Calatrava La Vieja (Almohad period) (MORALES MUÑIZ *et al.* 1988), Saltés (Huelva) (12th-13th century) (LENTACKER & ERVYNCK 1999), Motril (Granada) (16th-18th century) (Riquelme Cantal, 1993), and the Portuguese site of Alcáçova de Mértola (second half of the 12th century-first third of the 13th century) (TELLES ANTUNES 1996). In the towns of medieval Britain too there is some evidence that the frequency of domestic cats increased in the years following the Norman conquest (O'CONNOR 1982 and 1992), that is, from the second half of the 11th century (cf. ROWLEY 1999; CROUCH 2002).

Nevertheless, it cannot be ruled out that for the Iberian Peninsula - together with continental Italy and Sicily - the absence of finds for slightly earlier historic periods may very plausibly be attributable to the lack of excavations or the absence of specific archaeozoological studies. Unfortunately, it is not always possible to document the past presence of a certain zoological species in a specific territory and/or a particular cultural context, solely on the basis of the data offered by archaeozoological research (MASSETI 2009a). Consequently, it would be advisable to adopt a different approach to this

Fig. 14 - Skulls of *Mustela nivalis* L., 1766, from the pit IV of the Roman site of Oderzo (Treviso), dated between the end of the 1st century and the 2nd century AD (photo Civic Museum of Natural History of Venice)

subject, taking into account a multidisciplinary view which includes also literature and iconography.

A MATTER OF TAXONOMY. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Since ancient times, the continued and repeated crossbreeding of domestic cats and wild individuals has eventually altered the genetic and phenotypic characteristics of the specific Italian population, both in the mainland and on the islands (RANDI *et al.* 2001; OTTONI *et al.* 2017). The latest techniques for investigating population genetics have shown that the Italian samples are considered to be European wild cats, African cats and domestic cats belonged to the same polymorphic species (RANDI 2010; MATTUCCI *et al.* 2013), although some alleles are peculiar to domestic cats (RAGNI & RANDI 1986; RAGNI & POSSENTI 1991; RANDI & RAGNI, 1991). The presence of domestic mitochondrial haplotypes shared with some wild individuals led Mattucci (2014) and Mattucci *et al.* (2016) to hypothesise the possibility that ancient introgressive events might have occurred, further revealing that the genetic variability of microsatellites would show that European wildcat populations currently distributed in Italy originated from two distinct glacial refuges during the Last Glacial Maximum.

Unfortunately, this last assumption cannot yet be confirmed by the discovery of any fossil remain. Moreover, the wildcats of Mount Etna in Sicily (RAPAZZO *et al.* 2010) and the already mentioned population of the Gargano promontory (RAGNI & PETRUZZI 2010) appear to be respectively genetically and ecologically isolated.

From a taxonomic point of view, there has been almost universal use of *Felis catus* L., 1758, for the domestic cat, and *F. silvestris* for wildcats. This is, however, not only wrong but also misleading. First of all, because Linnaeus described in 1758 *Felis catus* on the basis of the examination of domestic specimens, while the true definition of *Felis silvestris* for the true wildcat was made only several years later by Schreber, in 1777. Personally, I believe that the name given to the description of the wild form should be preferred to denominate the species and not what is ordinarily given to the product of a reiterated artificial selection (see MASSETI 2002 and 2016). But, I understand that this subject can be considered from a different point of view. In any case, the result of thousands of years of artificial selection cannot be defined as a different species compared to its wild ancestor, as Wozencraft (2005) would instead indicate. Many other authors have treated the domestic cat as separate from the wildcats

Fig. 15 - Adult female of domestic cat struggling with a western whip snake, *Hierophis viridiflavus* (Lacépède, 1789) (photo by Stefano Porcinai)

(POCOCK 1951; CORBET & HILL 1992; KITCHENER 1991; DANIELS *et al.* 1998; NOWAK 1999; MATTERN & MCLENNAN 2000; WISEMAN *et al.* 2000; and others). RAGNI & RANDI (1986), ESSOP *et al.* (1997), JOHNSON & O'BRIEN (1997), RAGNI & PETRUZZI (2010), RANDI (2010), MATTUCCI *et al.* (2013) presented instead morphological and genetic evidence to support *catus*, *lybica* and *silvestris* as conspecific. In my opinion, however, it is not possible to say that the product between the domestic and the wild form should be indicated as a hybrid (see e.g. BALLESTEROS-DUPERON *et al.* 2014), that normally occurs between two different species. We must instead regard it as a crossbreeding, the result of the mating between two representatives of the same species (Fig. 15). Also for this reason, I think it would be appropriate to indicate all domestic breeds using the definition of *Felis silvestris* Schreber, 1777, since these races are exclusively the result of a profound, artificial genetic manipulation conducted on the highly elastic capacity of the same species unique genome.

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**CONSERVATION GENETICS OF THE EUROPEAN WILDCAT
(*FELIS SILVESTRIS SILVESTRIS*)**

**GENETICA DELLA CONSERVAZIONE DEL GATTO SELVATICO
(*FELIS SILVESTRIS SILVESTRIS*)**

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Abstract. Introgression of domestic cat genes and habitat fragmentation are the main conservation threats for the European wildcat (*Felis silvestris silvestris*). Highly informative molecular markers combined with advanced statistical approaches were recently used to improve our knowledge on the evolution of the European wildcat populations in Europe and their conservation status. Here we showed some of the results obtained.

Riassunto. L'introgressione di geni di gatto domestico e la frammentazione dell'habitat sono le principali minacce per la conservazione del gatto selvatico europeo (*Felis silvestris silvestris*). Alcuni marcatori molecolari altamente informativi, combinati con approcci statistici avanzati, sono stati recentemente utilizzati per migliorare le nostre conoscenze sull'evoluzione delle popolazioni di gatto selvatico europeo in Europa e sul loro stato di conservazione. Il lavoro riporta alcuni dei risultati ottenuti.

The European wildcat *Felis silvestris silvestris* is a medium-sized carnivore widely spread across Europe (PIERPAOLI *et al.* 2003; O'BRIEN *et al.* 2008; OLIVEIRA *et al.* 2008a,b; HERTWIG *et al.* 2009; MATTUCCI *et al.* 2016) in fragmented populations both at regional and local scales (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2016) resulting from hundreds of years of intense anthropogenic persecution and from the loss of suitable habitat (STAHL & ARTOIS 1995; YAMAGUCHI *et al.* 2015). Although there is recent evidence of increasing population sizes and natural recolonization of the species' historic range in at least some regions (STEYER *et al.* 2016; NUSSBERGER *et al.* 2018; VELLI *et al.* 2015; GAVAGNIN *et al.* 2018), the European wildcat is legally protected in Europe (EC 2015) both under the Bern Convention and the European Habitats Directive, and is listed as "least concern" in the IUCN red list.

Main conservation threats include habitat loss and fragmentation, road mortality, persecution and crossbreeding with free-ranging domestic cats (KLAR *et al.* 2008, 2009; LOZANO & MALO 2012; YAMAGUCHI *et al.* 2015).

The domesticated form originally derived from *Felis silvestris libyca* populations inhabiting the Near East/North Africa which gradually spread around the world following the human-mediated dispersal routes (DRISCOLL *et al.* 2007; OTTONI *et al.* 2017).

The widespread diffusion of stray or feral cat populations, often living in much higher density than

wildcats (SUNQUIST & SUNQUIST 2002) and the full fertility of their hybrid offspring (RAGNI 1993) likely promoted reproductive interaction between the two subspecies, increasing the risk of introgression of domestic alleles into the wildcat genome (RANDI *et al.* 2001; YAMAGUCHI *et al.* 2015).

Even if recent studies documented cases of beneficial introgression of domestic mutations in wild populations (COULSON *et al.* 2011; GROSSEN *et al.* 2014), hybridization between free-ranging domestic animals and their wild conspecifics may spread artificially-selected maladaptive variants causing fitness declines, outbreeding depression and gradual alterations of locally adapted gene complexes, thus increasing the risk of extinction of wild populations or entire species (RANDI 2008; RHYMER & SIMBERLOFF 1996; TUREK *et al.* 2013; TODESCO *et al.* 2016).

Putative wild \times domestic cat hybrids were detected in most regions where hybridization was investigated, but the degree of introgression varied considerably (PIERPAOLI *et al.* 2003; LECIS *et al.* 2006; OLIVEIRA *et al.* 2008a,b; RANDI 2008; SAY *et al.* 2012; NUSSBERGER *et al.* 2014b, 2018; STEYER *et al.* 2018; BEUGIN *et al.* 2020; TIESMEYER *et al.* 2020), leading to a complete hybrid swarm in wild-living cats in Scotland (BEAUMONT *et al.* 2001).

Such geographical heterogeneity in admixture levels might be explained by different environmental conditions and ecological barriers (GIL-SÁNCHEZ *et al.* 2015), or by the choice of markers and sampling design (STEYER *et al.* 2018)

In absence of strong ecological barriers,

hybridization can potentially threaten some of the extant wildcat populations.

Therefore the accurate detection of hybrids and the quantification of introgression in hybridizing populations are needed for developing appropriate wildcat conservation plans and correctly allocate resources for their application (NUSSBERGER *et al.* 2013; OLIVEIRA *et al.* 2015; GIL-SÁNCHEZ *et al.* 2020).

Recently, hybridization has been more reliably assessed using molecular markers, mainly small panels of hypervariable microsatellites (short tandem repeats, STRs) and short mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) sequences. However, the resolution of hybridization is limited due to the relatively low availability, repeatability between laboratories and technical capacity to analyze microsatellite markers (BEAUMONT *et al.* 2001; DANIELS *et al.* 2001; RANDI *et al.* 2001; LECIS *et al.* 2006; OLIVEIRA *et al.* 2008a,b; HERTWIG *et al.* 2009; O'BRIEN *et al.* 2009; SAY *et al.* 2012; DEVILLARD *et al.* 2014; STEYER *et al.* 2016). Consequently, standardized and more powerful panels of molecular markers are required to lower the risk of underestimating the prevalence of introgressive hybridization in natural wildcat populations.

Over the last decades, next-generation sequencing technologies offered the possibility to assemble extensive and cost-effective panels of ancestry-informative markers (AIMs) such as Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs), which represent the most widespread source of genome-wide variation (DAVEY *et al.* 2011).

SNPs have been shown to be highly accurate and sensitive in identifying hybrid individuals between wildcats and domestic cats, irrespective of origin and available reference database, and quality of biological samples (OLIVEIRA *et al.* 2015; STEYER *et al.* 2018; MATTUCCI *et al.* 2019; TIESMEYER *et al.* 2020; VON THADEN *et al.* 2020).

In particular, the recently released Illumina Infinium iSelect 63k DNA cat array containing 62,897 variants that are mostly polymorphic within the domestic cats (GANDOLFI *et al.* 2018) offered a suitable molecular tool to further investigate the ancestry of European wildcat populations in conservation and monitoring projects (GANDOLFI *et al.* 2018).

Recent studies showed how the employment of thousands of markers might help to unveil previously undetectable backcrosses (older than two–three generations in the past), estimate the timing from the admixture events (HOHENLOHE *et al.* 2013; GALAVERNI *et al.* 2017), and allow researchers to better understand the dynamics and consequences of anthropogenic hybridization, helping to face specific management and conservation issues (MCFARLANE & PEMBERTON 2019).

A wide sampling ($n = 182$) of European wildcats, domestic cats and known or putative admixed cats from a large part of the European wildcat home range distribution ($n = 10$ European countries) was genotyped with the Illumina Infinium iSelect 63k DNA and analysed by applying

Fig. 1. - PC1 versus PC2 results from an exploratory principal component analysis (PCA) computed in SVS on the 57k SNP panel set (after quality pruning procedures) and including domestic cats (blue dots; DC), putatively admixed wildcats (orange dots; HY) and European wildcats (green dots; WC). The two axes are not to scale, in order to better distinguish individuals along PC2.

multivariate, Bayesian and gene-search analysis tools (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2019).

Results of a preliminary genomic screening, based on pairwise F_{ST} values, multivariate (Fig.1) and assignment tools, showed that wild and domestic cats remain highly differentiated and well-distinguished.

On average, 17% of the analyzed putative admixed wildcats show genomic domestic ancestry which likely originated from hybridization events occurring from 6 to 22 generations before sampling (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2019). The most ancient admixture traces were detected in individuals which had been misclassified as pure in previous microsatellite-based analyses (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2016), confirming the deeper diagnostic power of genomic data in detecting past backcrossing.

The availability of efficient AIMs widely distributed across the entire genome can allow us to identify introgressed linkage blocks hosting candidate genes that may be associated with functional traits that are still unknown (TWYFORD & ENNOS 2012; MCFARLANE & PEMBERTON 2019), further help to unravel historical and contemporary admixture (PAYSEUR & RIESEBERG 2016) by analyzing the distribution of haplotype block lengths (PALAMARA *et al.* 2012; MCFARLANE & PEMBERTON 2019).

Approximately more than 600 coding genes with an excess of wild or domestic ancestry were identified in the admixed wildcats. These genes were significantly enriched for Gene Ontology categories mainly related to social behavior, functional and metabolic adaptive processes (wild-like genes), involved in cognition and neural crest development (domestic-like genes), or associated with immune system functions and lipid metabolism (parental-like genes; MATTUCCI *et al.* 2019)

However, such genes provide just a preliminary insight on the inheritance patterns of domestic and wild ancestry block. Hence, in the future all these data will need to be integrated with information on fitness, survival and breeding rates of the admixed individuals, in order to better understand the adaptive patterns of wild-living admixed individuals.

Genomic ancestry analyses could be reliably applied to unravel dynamics, direction and consequences of anthropogenic hybridization (MCFARLANE & PEMBERTON 2019), helping to face specific management and conservation issues.

However, to design more efficient conservation plans in European wildcats and other hybridizing populations, knowledge of population dynamics, species' distribution, and natural/anthropogenic causes of genetic structure are further needed (BURGMAN *et al.* 1993; LANCIA *et al.* 1994).

Past climate changes, historical evolutionary events and, eventually, more recent anthropogenic pressures shaped the genetic diversity within and among populations (HEWITT 1999) in Europe. In addition, the fragmentation of populations due to habitats loss and alterations, may have eroded the neutral and adaptive genetic diversity, reducing the effective population size and the inter-population connectivity (JOHANSSON *et al.* 2007), and increasing the risk of genetic bottleneck.

Extant populations of European wildcat are fragmented across the continent.

A comprehensive range-wide study of their population structure ($n = 668$ from 15 European countries) was designed aiming at quantifying their genetic variability, reconstructing patterns of population clustering and fragmentation, and obtaining estimates of population divergence times (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2016).

Results of Model-based structure analyses and non-model multivariate clustering using a panel of 31 domestic cat-derived microsatellites concordantly identified five main biogeographic clusters, respectively: the Iberian Peninsula, central Europe, central Germany, Italian Peninsula and the island of Sicily, and the Dinaric Alps (north-eastern Italy and northern Balkan regions), Fig. 2A-B. Approximate Bayesian Computation simulations suggested a model of late Pleistocene–early Holocene population splittings (from c. 60k to 10k years ago), contemporary to the last Ice Age climatic changes. At a smaller geographic scale, wildcats in peninsular Italy are differentiated into three genetic groups coherently distributed in Sicily, peninsular Italy and the Alps, following a model of LGM isolation and genetic diversification into Mediterranean glacial refuges (HEWITT 1999; Fig. 3A-B).

A more recent differentiation have been described in the Maremma area of the central peninsular Italy, where the population might have experienced periods of isolation and local adaptation to a peculiar Mediterranean-type habitat (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2013; Fig. 3C). The studied populations of the European wildcat have maintained relative high levels of genetic diversity, nevertheless some isolated small patches within these groups might have been exposed to the deleterious consequences of genetic drift and inbreeding (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2016).

Hence, the use of powerful computational tools and hypervariable molecular markers proved to be efficient for assessing species' phylogeographic pattern which might be used to improve our understanding, thus helping to identify the most appropriate conservation issues (HICKERSON *et al.* 2010).

A

B

Fig. 2 - A) Approximate distributions of five European wildcat (*F. s. silvestris*) biogeographic groups identified through multivariate and Bayesian cluster analyses across Europe with 31 autosomal microsatellite loci. The grey areas represent the European wildcats distributions (obtained from © IUCN-International Union for Conservation of Nature- Red List 2015 *Felis silvestris* Downloaded on 09 May 2019; YAMAGUCHI *et al.* 2015). B) Patterns of hierarchical splitting of European wildcat populations assuming $K = 5$, the “admixture” and the “F” models in STRUCTURE; PRITCHARD & WEN 2003). Each cat genotype is represented by a vertical bar split in K colored sections, according to its relative assignment to the K genetic clusters.

Long-term monitoring programs and legal protection of this endangered species should focus on saving the local functional wildcats (see also DANIELS & CORBETT 2003), for instance, protecting the environmental conditions that favor pure wildcats, guaranteeing natural ecological corridor to interconnect fragmented habitats, mapping the distribution of non-introgressed natural populations, providing information on the health status of wild-living individuals (through the analysis of genes related to illness, immune response, reproductive patterns or adaptation to specific ecological pressure, ALLENDORF *et al.* 2010), and identifying appropriate evolutionary and management units (ESU and MU; FUNK *et al.* 2012) where apply appropriate local management practices.

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Fig. 3 - A) European wildcats (*F. s. silvestris*) biogeographic distribution identified through Bayesian cluster analyses across Italy with 35 autosomal microsatellite loci: Eastern Alps (in green), Maremma (areas in Tuscany and Lazio Maremma in the western Italian peninsula, in orange), Apennines (areas in Marche, Umbria, Abruzzo, Campania, and Basilicata regions, in blue), and Sicily (in red). The gray areas indicate the approximate wildcat distribution ranges in Italy. African wildcats living in Sardinia (*F. s. lybica*) are further showed in light blue. B) Scatterplot of a Discriminant Analysis of Principal Component (DAPC) obtained with ADEGENET showing genetic distinctions among the four European wildcat subpopulations identified in Italy: The proportion of genetic diversity described by each Principal Component (PCA eigenvalues) is showed in the barplots (see the insert). C) Spatial Principal Component Analysis (sPCA, obtained with ADEGENET) of European wildcats sampled in central Apennines. Individual genotype scores are interpolated and represented by circles. Contour lines quantified the degree of genetic differentiation among individuals.

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**CORTISOL AND CAMERA-TRAPPING AS USEFUL TOOLS TO EXPLORE
ECOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE EUROPEAN WILDCAT (*FELIS SILVESTRIS SILVESTRIS*)**

***IL CORTISOLO E IL FOTORAPPOLAGGIO QUALI STRUMENTI UTILI AD APPROFONDIRE
ASPETTI DELL'ECOLOGIA DEL GATTO SELVATICO EUROPEO (*FELIS SILVESTRIS SILVESTRIS*)***

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Abstract. The combined use of different monitoring techniques for wildlife studies (with particular attention dedicated to felids) assumes remarkable importance to the knowledge of all those ecological and physiological variables which may affect the welfare of the target species. The quantification of glucocorticoid metabolites in hair is a non-invasive tool that provides important information regarding the endocrine status and represents a valuable method for studying potential stressors that may affect carnivores under both natural and non-natural conditions. Cortisol is the main glucocorticoid hormone of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal gland axis and is considered a standard stress indicator for animal welfare. Differences in hair cortisol concentration between subspecies such as wild and feral cats is related to either physiological and/or ecological conditions. Wildcats generally have to cope with ecological pressures (e.g., hunting for food, competition, anthropic disturbance) that may lead to an increasing allostatic load. Nevertheless, hair cortisol comparisons between felid species or subspecies in response to both natural and non-natural factors is still poorly considered. Therefore, further studies are strongly suggested. At the same time, camera-trapping, i.e., the use of remotely triggered cameras that automatically take images and/or videos of animals transiting in front of them, represents a useful tool to study species' population parameters, as well as the interactions among species within a specific area. Such data may be combined to cortisol analyses to provide further insights on species (e.g., wildcat) welfare within different wildlife communities. Therefore, this information might be used by conservationists to delineate adequate management plans aimed at fostering wildcat conservation.

Riassunto. L'utilizzo combinato di differenti tecniche di monitoraggio per lo studio della fauna (con particolare riferimento ai felini) assume un'importanza rilevante ai fini della conoscenza di tutte quelle variabili di natura ecologica e fisiologica che possono influire sul benessere delle specie in esame. La misura dell'accumulo di glucocorticoidi all'interno del pelo rappresenta un metodo non invasivo che fornisce importanti informazioni in merito ai potenziali fattori stressogeni di origine naturale e artificiale che influenzano la sopravvivenza di varie specie di carnivori a livello globale. Il cortisolo rappresenta il principale ormone glucocorticoido prodotto dall'asse ipotalamo-ipofisi che viene riconosciuto come indicatore standard del benessere animale. Differenze in termini di concentrazioni di cortisolo accumulatosi nel pelo tra sottospecie sono dovute a differenti risposte metaboliche basali e pressioni ecologiche. I gatti selvatici generalmente sono sottoposti a pressioni ecologiche (e.g., caccia, competizione, disturbo antropico) che possono indurre un aumento del carico allostatico. Tuttavia, confronti fra livelli di cortisolo tra specie o sottospecie appartenenti alla Famiglia Felidae sono ancora ampiamente assenti. Di conseguenza, ulteriori studi sono fortemente consigliati. Parallelamente, il foto/video-trappolaggio, ovvero l'utilizzo di macchine fotografiche in grado di scattare foto e video ogni qualvolta un animale passa dinnanzi ad esse, rappresenta un'importante tecnica per lo studio sia dei parametri di popolazione delle specie, che delle interazioni tra esse in una data area. Questi dati potenzialmente possono essere combinati all'analisi del cortisolo per fornire ulteriori evidenze sullo stato di salute delle specie (es. il gatto selvatico) all'interno di diverse comunità animali. Tali informazioni possono quindi essere utilizzate a favore della conservazione del gatto selvatico.

INTRODUCTION

The combined use of different monitoring techniques for wildlife conservation purposes assumes notable importance in the light of the potential effects that either ecological and/or physiological variables may exert on animal welfare. Abiotic and biotic changes are common within the environment, and animals may respond through temporal variation in their vital rate and/or an alteration in their physiological response

(DARLINGTON *et al.* 1990). Another common response used by wild species in response to a potential distress condition is the modification in terms of behavioural pattern (MELBERG 2012; CENTORE *et al.* 2018). For instance, throughout the use of camera-trapping the effects derived from the competition among species could be highlighted. For instance, MELBERG (2012) observed spatial and temporal segregation between roe deers (*Capreolus capreolus*) and wild boars (*Sus scrofa*). It was showed that roe deer fawns tended to be spatially

segregated in relation to wild boar activity. Furthermore, roe deer displayed a non-random movement pattern towards wild boar rooting behaviour. In addition, a lower roe deer presence at rubbing trees was found, suggesting that adult individuals avoided sites often frequented by wild boar. Finally, a pattern of temporal avoidance was found between the two species in which both roe deer and wild boar were active during the same hours but with different frequency. Therefore, the combination of camera-trap surveys along with physiological analyses may provide further and detailed insights concerning the ecological interactions among species as well as in terms of the effect of potential distress conditions (MILLSPAUGH *et al.* 2001; ZWIJACZ-KOZICA *et al.* 2013; EWACHA *et al.* 2017).

CORTISOL: THE “STRESS HORMONE”

The ability of an organism to adapt to changes in environmental conditions has been receiving increased attention in recent years (RUIZ-GOMEZ *et al.* 2011; MONTIGLIO *et al.* 2012). A *stressor* is defined as a stimulus which leads to the activation of the acute stress response system (WINGFIELD *et al.* 2011). A stimulus becomes a stressor when an individual cope with it with uncertainty due to the absence of information (LEVINE & URSIN 1991). The acute stress response consists in the temporary interruption of the normal functions to counteract the impact of the stressor and to re-establish the homeostasis (SAPOLSKY *et al.* 2000). As opposed to acute stress, chronic stress occurs when the prolonged exposition to a stressor leads to the breakdown of physiological systems (SAPOLSKY *et al.* 2000; MCEWEN & WINGFIELD 2003; ROMERO *et al.* 2009). The most common physiological response toward a distress situation is the activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) gland axis which culminates in the secretion of glucocorticoids from the adrenal cortex (SAPOLSKI *et al.* 2000). These hormones facilitate increased energy mobilization and suppression of several system processes (i.e., digestion, immunity, growth and reproduction) as well as a return to baseline conditions via negative feedback to the brain (WINGFIELD *et al.* 1998). Nevertheless, prolonged stimulation of the HPA axis may lead to chronic consequences such as muscle wastage, growth suppression, inhibition of reproduction, neuronal cell death, and suppression of the immune system (SAPOLSKY *et al.* 2000). Such chronic stimulation could be significant in animals living in human-altered habitats (MILLSPAUGH *et al.* 2001; ZWIJACZ-KOZICA *et al.* 2013; EWACHA

et al. 2017) or during particular life stages (e.g., reproduction, pregnancy, lactation) (REEDER & KRAMER 2005). Assessing the glucocorticoid levels may, thus, represent a useful tool to monitor the physiological status of a population under both natural and non-natural conditions. Cortisol is recognized as the first stress hormone involved in allostasis (an active process involved in maintaining and/or re-establishing homeostasis) and is frequently measured to assess adrenocortical activity in vertebrates (MCEWEN 1998), but it is further involved in a wide range of metabolic functions such as metabolism regulation, growth rate, reproductive and immune system regulation (HAMILTON *et al.* 2008). Moreover, within an organism that suffers from acute or chronic stress various other mechanisms spanning from molecular (e.g., heat shock proteins) to organismal (e.g., sympathetic nervous system activation) functions are activated. In this sense, considering cortisol as a simple stress hormone oversimplifies its function (DICKENS & ROMERO 2013; MACDOUGALL-SHACKLETON *et al.* 2019). Cortisol concentrations can be measured with invasive and non-invasive techniques in several matrices such as blood (GARDINER & HALL 1997), faeces (MILLSPAUGH *et al.* 2001, 2004), urine (REHBINDER & HAU 2006), milk (GYGAX *et al.* 2006), saliva (NEGRÃO *et al.* 2004), eggs (MINGIST *et al.* 2007), claws (COMIN *et al.* 2014), feathers (FRONGIA *et al.* 2020), and hair (PRANDI *et al.* 2018). However, compared to other matrices (i.e., blood) that provide a short-term measure of glucocorticoids concentration (< 3 min.), measurements of glucocorticoid metabolites in matrices such as hair represents a valuable method to trace an individual’s ‘stress history’ in the long-term period, as cortisol concentration in hair is deposited over an extended time frame (variable from weeks to years, depending on the hair length) (MEYER & NOVAK 2012). Additionally, hair is a relatively stable matrix that does not decompose as rapidly as other body fluids or tissues do (BALÍKOVÁ 2005). Hair growth rate consists of three phases: anagen (active growth), catagen (transition) and telogen (resting) (HARKEY 1993), and hormones can only be accumulated within the hair shaft during the anagen phase via passive diffusion from blood vessels (MEYER & NOVAK 2012). The accumulation occurs within the hair follicle located several millimetres below the skin surface (HARKEY 1993). Therefore, there is a time delay between cortisol incorporation into the hair and the time spent by this hair section arriving at the skin surface (STALDER & KIRSCHBAUM 2012; MONTILLO *et al.* 2019).

MEASURING LONG-TERM PHYSIOLOGICAL RESPONSE
IN WILD FELIDS

Within the *Felidae* Family cortisol-level analysis have received little attention in the last decade (NAIDENKO *et al.* 2011, 2019; FANSON *et al.* 2012; CREEL *et al.* 2013; NARAYAN *et al.* 2013; BHATTACHARJEE *et al.* 2015; MONDOL *et al.* 2020) and as far as concerns the European wildcat (*Felis silvestris silvestris*) such analyses have been rarely treated and mostly on faecal matrices (PINEIRO *et al.* 2012, 2015). To the best of our knowledge, the only studies in which hair cortisol was analysed within the *Felis silvestris* subspecies was carried out by FRANCHINI *et al.* (2019) and FILACORDA *et al.* (2021), in which they compared hair cortisol concentrations

(HCC) between wild and feral cats (*Felis silvestris catus*) living in different environmental conditions (Fig. 1), and the physiological response of wildcats towards habitat fragmentation and interspecific competition (Fig. 2), respectively. Beyond the existence of species-specific differences in the secretion of metabolic hormones there may be several either environmental or ecological factors that may induce different cortisol accumulations between subspecies or individuals belonging to the same species but living in different environmental contexts. For instance, NAIDENKO *et al.* (2011) obtained a significant difference in terms of HPA gland axis activity between wild and captive Amur tigers (*Panthera tigris altaica*) where wild specimens, probably due to unfavourable environmental

Fig. 1 - Boxplot showing the difference in terms of hair cortisol concentration (pg cortisol/mg hair) between subspecies.

conditions in which they lived, showed significantly higher cortisol levels compared with captive ones. In our case, the difference recorded in terms of HCCs between wild and feral cats may be related to various factors. The first explanation could be related to underlying differences in metabolism, diet, and/or energy regulation which may have affected steroid production (ROMERO *et al.* 2009).

A second explanation might be related to differing degrees of tolerance of each subspecies toward anthropic disturbance or towards other con(sub)specifics. Feral cats are known to live in close contact with humans (and each other), although only in relation to foraging behaviour (NATOLI 1994). In this sense, they may be more tolerant toward humans and intraspecific presence than wild individuals which are instead forced to live in less suitable or unsuitable habitats. The effect of anthropic disturbance on cortisol accumulation has received considerable attention in recent years and has been studied in various species. For instance, NAIDENKO *et al.* (2019) compared faecal glucocorticoid levels between two tiger subspecies, the Amur tiger and Bengal tiger (*Panthera tigris tigris*) living in two extreme habitats. From the analysis, they recorded that faecal cortisol metabolites (FCMs) were significantly higher in Bengal tigers living in India than in Amur tigers living in the Russian Far East and, as explained by the authors, these reasons might be related to tiger density or anthropogenic disturbance.

A third explanation may be related to differences in terms of environmental pressures to which each subspecies was subjected. For instance, NAIDENKO *et al.* (2011) compared cortisol levels between wild and captive Amur tigers, showing that wild tigers had significantly higher cortisol concentrations compared with captive ones and that the reason might be related to the unfavourable influences of low temperatures and deep snow cover. As the feral cats lived in colonies in close contact with human beings who regularly supplied them with food, they were not subjected to stressors (i.e. hunting for food) which might have led to increased HPA gland axis activity. Moreover, factors such as inter-specific and intraspecific competition might have affected individual wildcats' welfare resulting in higher hair cortisol accumulations. In Friuli Venezia Giulia, the main medium-sized carnivores which may compete with the wildcat for territory and/or food resources are the beech marten (*Martes foina*), the pine marten (*Martes martes*), the red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), and the golden jackal (*Canis aureus*). However, research focused on assessing the impact of inter-specific competition on wildcat welfare is still rather sparse. A research realized by FILACORDA *et al.* (2021) has been revealing an increasing trend

in terms of HCC measured in wildcats in response to increased golden jackals' density (Fig. 2). Following the mesopredator suppression theory (SOULÉ *et al.* 1988) the biggest carnivore living within the area behave as apex predator killing the smaller sized competitors for competition reduction and, occasionally, for feeding (SOTO & PALOMARES 2013). The presence of domestic cats in the diet of jackals has been reported in other studies (PENEZIĆ & ČIROVIĆ 2015; LANSZKI *et al.* 2016; VLASSEVA *et al.* 2017). Moreover, interspecific competition between jackals and other wildcat species has been recorded as well (PETERSEN *et al.* 2019; SELVAN *et al.* 2019). To our knowledge, to date, no bibliographic information is available regarding the interspecific killing between golden jackals and European wildcats. However, since both species present a similar trophic niche feeding mainly over small mammals and birds (FRANCHINI *et al.* 2017; VLASSEVA *et al.* 2017) the competition for trophic resources is very likely.

CAMERA-TRAPPING AS USEFUL TOOL FOR WILDCAT PRESENCE AND PUPULATION ESTIMATION

Monitoring wildlife populations is important for conservation management but is often difficult to achieve effectively, particularly for rare and cryptic species such as carnivores, which are often threatened and exist at low densities and in fragmented populations (GESE 2001). The use of camera trapping, i.e., remotely triggered cameras that automatically take images and/or videos of animals transiting in front of them (ROVERO *et al.* 2013), as a technique to survey and monitor wildlife has increased dramatically in recent years (O'CONNELL *et al.* 2011). The technological advances in infrared sensors and digital photography have led to cost-effective, non-invasive means of generating reliable detection of elusive wildlife (KUCERA & BARRETT, 2011). Camera trap (CT) methodology now encompasses a wide range of equipment and ecological applications: CTs are now being used to assess wildlife distribution, abundance, behaviour and community structure (ROVERO *et al.* 2013; MEEK *et al.* 2014).

In this sense, despite the species is widely (but patchily) distributed (Africa, Asia, Europe) and globally categorized as "Least Concern" by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) (YAMAGUCHI *et al.* 2015) data on presence, abundance and distribution of European wildcats are extremely valuable because this species is subject to several global threats including local extinctions and population fragmentation, especially in Europe (NOWELL & JACKSON, 1996), ROVERO *et al.* (2013) reviewed the sampling designs for different research aims using CTs. They suggest a grid arrangement of

Fig. 2 - Hair cortisol level variations in response to (a) golden jackal, and (b) red fox subdivided into classes of abundance (golden jackal: class 0 = absence of the species, class 1 = hunters/technician reports or collection of carcasses during one year, class 2 = acoustic stimulation, hunters/technician reports and/or collection of carcasses during two years; red fox: class 0 = 0–0.99 ind./100 ha, class 1 = 1–1.99 ind./100 ha, class 2 = more than 2 ind./100 ha). The only significant effect was recorded for the golden jackal.

CTs as good for species inventories and occupancy studies. In the latter case, occupancy can be used as a surrogate of abundance for species with relatively small home ranges, such as wildcats (ROVERO *et al.* 2013). Furthermore, a ‘capture-mark-recapture’ (CMR) approach, which relies on individual recognition of members of the studied population based on coat pattern, allows population abundance estimates (ROVERO *et al.* 2013) and can be used for wildcats (ANILE *et al.* 2010; KILSHAW *et al.* 2015). In these ways, wildcat presence, density and abundance have been determined from camera-trapping studies (MONTERROSO *et al.* 2005; SARMENTO *et al.* 2009; ANILE *et al.* 2010; CAFARIELLO *et al.* 2012; KILSHAW *et al.* 2015). Indeed, a grid arrangement for CTs was used (MONTERROSO *et al.* 2005; SARMENTO *et al.* 2009; KILSHAW *et al.* 2015) and/or they were deployed in order to obtain the same density of CTs in the sample area for wildcat density estimations (ANILE *et al.* 2010; KILSHAW *et al.* 2015). Although in the occupancy studies camera placement should be ideally random, in other sampling designs CTs should be deployed in order to maximize species

detection such as along trails, near drinking sites, etc. This is particularly true for CMR approaches (ROVERO *et al.* 2013). For this reason, preliminary explorations of the study area should be carried out in order to find good places where CTs can be placed (ANILE *et al.* 2010; KILSHAW *et al.* 2015). Further controversial results (KÉRY *et al.* 2011; ANILE *et al.* 2012; STEYER *et al.* 2013; KILSHAW *et al.* 2015; VELLI *et al.* 2015), and this may have genetic bases. In fact, it has been shown that felids’ response to catnip is genetically determined (BRADSHAW 1992). Therefore, assuming that even in the case of valerian attractants the response is driven by genetic factors, the lack of attractiveness in small populations, such as the Sicilian (ANILE *et al.* 2012) and the Scottish one (KILSHAW *et al.* 2015), compared to the others (VELLI *et al.* 2015) may be attributable to genetic bases.

A FUTURE PROSPECTIVE: INTEGRATING CAMERA-TRAPPING TO CORTISOL ANALYSES

Further information that CTs provide is the date and time at which each photograph is taken,

allowing analysis of activity patterns and niche partitioning (RIDOUT & LINKIE, 2009). Due to the niche differentiation that occurs among sympatric species, understanding the coexistence mechanisms of species will contribute to the conservation and management of ecological communities (cited in ZHAO *et al.* 2020). This is particularly true for medium-sized carnivores at intermediate trophic levels (PRUGH *et al.* 2009) which generally show high species richness, resource partitioning and different habitat use (ROEMER *et al.* 2009). The aggressive interactions among medium-sized carnivores normally influence their activity patterns and are expected to be stronger for species with high dietary overlap, (SCHOENER 1974; DONADIO & BUSKIRK, 2006; RITCHIE & JOHNSON, 2009). Such studies have been carried out, focusing even on wildcat. For instance MONTERROSO *et al.* (2014) found that temporal segregation among wildcat, Iberian lynx (*Lynx pardinus*), red fox and pine marten may play an important role in facilitating medium-size coexistence, especially with increasing community complexity.

Moreover, not only interactions among different species should be considered, but also those within the same group, i.e., among wildcats, feral domestic cats and hybrids (BIRÒ *et al.* 2005). In Hungary, Birò and colleagues (2005) found similar wildcats' and hybrids' prey characteristics, as well as high trophic niche overlap (77-88%) among the above-cited cat groups. These findings led the authors to conclude that wildcat populations may be negatively affected by trophic relations with feral cats and hybrid cats, especially where high feral domestic cat densities or low wildcat densities occur.

On the other hand, even the presence and abundance of ungulates may affect wildcat welfare. Indeed, the negative effect on vegetation cover due to overgrazing produced by large ungulate species has been reported in other studies (FLOWERDEW & ELLWOOD 2001; SMIT *et al.* 2001; MASSEI & GENOV 2004; LOZANO *et al.* 2007). LOZANO *et al.* (2007) showed that in some areas overgrazing was so intense that have led to the jeopardization of wildcat populations by reducing rabbits' availability.

Therefore, it is easy to understand that in highly complex communities stressful direct or indirect interactions may occur.

To the best of our knowledge few works were focused in assessing the relation between cortisol concentrations and both presence and densities of competitors, predators or other species (MONCLÚS *et al.* 2009; FILACORDA *et al.* (2021). The preliminary results presented by FILACORDA *et al.* (2021) revealed that in those areas in which wildcats showed higher HCCs, data obtained from camera traps apparently showed lower wildcat densities and, on the contrary, higher densities of both wild boar and golden jackal. Populations parameters and activity patterns among species can be evaluated through camera-trapping (Fig. 3) (ROVERO *et al.* 2013), and therefore their effect on wildlife (e.g., wildcat) welfare can be tested, providing useful information on species interactions and conservation management.

CONCLUSION

Hair cortisol analysis assumes remarkable importance in the assessment of the long-term physiological response of wild species, hence, contributing to lay the foundation for future works focused in assessing the various physiological and ecological factors affecting the HPA gland axis activity of those populations living under a range of environmental conditions and leading to the establishment of adequate conservation plans toward the most endangered species (or subspecies).

Furthermore, camera-trapping may represent a useful tool to investigate wildcat's population parameters, as well as the interactions that might occur among the species in a specific area.

Most importantly, through a multidisciplinary approach, cortisol and camera-trapping data may be combined to provide further insights on wildcat welfare within different wildlife communities. Such an information may represent an important scientific baseline for managers and conservationists to delineate adequate management plans aimed at fostering the conservation of wildcat populations.

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Fig. 3 - Use of camera trap to monitor wildcat presence as well as the presence of competitors, potential predators, preys and other species within a specific area. (a) Red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), (b) Common pheasant (*Phasianus colchicus*), (c) Roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*), (d) and (e) Wildcat (*Felis silvestris silvestris*), and (f) Golden jackal (*Canis aureus*). Images a-d were recorded in a different site of images e-f

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**THE EUROPEAN WILDCAT (*Felis silvestris silvestris*, SCHREBER, 1777)
IN THE VENETO REGION (ITALY)**

**IL GATTO SELVATICO EUROPEO (*Felis silvestris silvestris*, SCHREBER, 1777)
IN VENETO**

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Abstract. The European wildcat became probably extinct in the Veneto Region from the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries. The expansion of the wildcat Dinaric -Balkan population in the eastern Italian Alps has been well documented for many decades. In 1983, an adult male was illegally killed in the Cansiglio Forest, thus documenting his return for the first time. This paper is a summary of the knowledge gathered on the species over the last 37 years. To assess the current range of the felid we have used known, unpublished observations and carcasses recovered for accidental or illegal killings. A total of 124 objective findings have been documented, most of them 114 (92%), collected using the camera trapping method. Some surveys in recent years have considerably contributed to increase the knowledge on the species. One of these has demonstrated the presence of a vital population in the Eastern Venetian Prealps, confirmed by two reproductive events. Thanks to the analysis of all the data collected, it has been possible to delineate the current western limit of the European Wildcat distribution range in north-eastern Italy, placing it in the southern part of the province of Belluno.

Riassunto. Il Gatto selvatico europeo è scomparso probabilmente dal Veneto tra il 19° e il 20° secolo. L'espansione della popolazione dinarico-balcanica del felide nel nord-est Italia è ben documentata ormai da qualche decennio. Nel 1983 un maschio adulto è stato abbattuto illegalmente nella Foresta del Cansiglio, documentando in questo modo il suo ritorno. Questo lavoro è una sintesi delle conoscenze raccolte sulla specie negli ultimi 37 anni. Per valutare l'areale attuale del felide abbiamo utilizzato osservazioni note, inedite e carcasse recuperate per uccisioni accidentali o illegali. Sono stati documentati complessivamente 124 reperti oggettivi, la maggior parte dei quali, 114 (92%), raccolti utilizzando la tecnica del fototrappolaggio. Alcune ricerche negli ultimi anni hanno contribuito considerevolmente ad aumentare le conoscenze sulla specie. Una di queste ha dimostrato la presenza di una popolazione vitale nelle Prealpi Venete orientali, confermata da due eventi riproduttivi. Grazie all'analisi di tutti i dati raccolti è stato possibile delineare l'attuale limite occidentale dell'areale del Gatto selvatico europeo nel nord-est Italia, situandolo nella parte meridionale della provincia di Belluno.

INTRODUCTION

This contribution is a synthesis of the current distribution knowledge of the European wildcat *Felis silvestris* in the Veneto Region. Some of the data presented here have been previously published, but many others are new and they are currently part of a database that was updated in May 2020.

In the last 37 years, from the first documented specimen in Veneto in 1983 until today, a considerable amount of information has been collected. Thanks to the strict and standardized criteria of coat traits, morphological and genetic analysis, that gives us a clear and objective picture of the population dynamics. Considering the summary nature of this work, we have also integrated the most recent data with the historical knowledge of the felid, although many of these are sometimes difficult to evaluate.

Currently, there are only two areas where the wildcat is monitored with a certain continuity; in the Eastern Venetian Prealps and within the Dolomiti Bellunesi National Park (DBNP). In the rest of the Veneto territory, data are obtained in a passive way, without a systematic approach, where the events collected are therefore completely random. Almost all the surveys carried out in Veneto have used the camera trapping (CT) method, a non-invasive approach that considerably contributed to increase our knowledge on the distribution of the species, improving the ability over time and space to monitor even very elusive animals.

The European wildcat *Felis silvestris* is a carnivore of conservation concern in Europe and has a wide and fragmented distribution, occupying a variety of different habitats. (DRISCOLL & NOWELL 2010, LOZANO 2010). The Italian population is

present from the Tuscan-Emilian Apennines to Calabria. To the Cispadane population also belong the specimens living in Sicily. (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2013, RAGNI *et al.* 2014). The species in the north-eastern Italy and Dinaric Alps (Slovenia and Croatia) are joined into a unique genetic cluster (Fig. 1), indicating recent shared ancestry (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2015).

The wildcat is one of the 96 mammals currently present in Veneto and also the only felid with a stable presence, as that of the Eurasian *Lynx lynx* can be considered occasional (BON 2017, CATELLO & MOLINARI 2017).

It has been included in the lists of the Bern Convention (App. II), Habitats Directive (App. IV) and CITES (App. II). In Italy the European wildcat is protected by L.N. 157/92. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species considers the European wildcat least concern, but with a declining population trend.

Although the expansion of the species in the northeast of Italy is known and well documented for a few decades (RAGNI *et al.* 1987, LAPINI 2006), the European wildcat remains a poorly studied carnivore. Despite the considerable amount of data collected, many aspects of its dynamics are still unexplored and important biological parameters, in the Alpine environment, have not been sufficiently investigated so far. We therefore believe it is important to outline the current distribution area of the felid in Veneto, not only to update and complete previous publications, but also to assess the development of the population and possible directions of expansion, aspects that play a fundamental role in the conservation measures of the species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We have briefly illustrated the main researches carried out in Veneto, remembering the most significant methodologies and results. The numerous data obtained from these surveys, also completed by those collected randomly (e.g. by hikers or CT enthusiasts) and all the carcasses recovered, were the basis for delineating the distribution of the species in the Region.

Veneto is the 8th largest region in Italy (Fig. 1), with a total area of 18,398.9 km². It is located in the North-Eastern part of Italy and is bordered to the east by Friuli-Venezia Giulia, to the south by Emilia-Romagna, to the west by Lombardy and to the north by Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol. In its northernmost corner it also borders Austria.

By area, 29,1% of its surface is mountainous (Carnic Alps, Eastern Dolomites and Venetian Prealps), hills 14,5 % and plains 56,4%. The prevailing climate in the Veneto is the ‘temperate subcontinental’, covering the whole area of the plain, the pre-alpine valleys and the Valbelluna. Mountain areas are mainly located within the ‘cool-cold temperate’ and only the culminating Alpine areas within the ‘cold climate’.

All wildcats, whether run over or killed illegally, have been assessed on a phenotype-based taxonomic diagnosis; three of these were also morphologically examined and genotyped. During one hair trapping project it was possible to genotype a fourth specimen as well.

The many video-picture documents, obtained largely by camera traps, have been analysed for the differential diagnosis and only those that clearly

Fig. 1 - (A) Approximate distribution range of the European wildcat (*Felis silvestris*) adapted from IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, version 2013.2 and the five European wildcat (*F.s. silvestris*) biogeographic groups (BGU) (adapted from MATTUCCI *et al.* 2015 and OLIVEIRA *et al.* 2018): BGU 1 (north-eastern Alps, Dinaric Alps, Bulgaria and Poland); BGU2 (peninsular Italy, Sicily); BGU3 (central Germany); BCU4 (south-western Germany, France, Belgium, Switzerland and Luxembourg); BCU5 (Portugal and Spain). The two introgressed populations (Scotland and Hungary) are excluded. (B) The Veneto Region (in black) in north-eastern Italy.

showed with sufficient quality the distinctive somatic features of the European wildcat, have been taken into consideration; we used two different classification systems based on Ragni and Possenti (1996) and on Kitchener *et al.* (2005). The pictures had clearly present at least two of the pelage characters (GÖTZ 2015), such as shape of tail tip and its distinct banding (*Caudalis*), stripes on nape (*Occipitalis-Cervicalis*), stripes on shoulder (*Scapularis*) and dorsal line (*Dorsalis*). The flanks & hindquarters somatic zone (*Lateralis*) have also been considered, even if, these together with just one of the above-mentioned identification criteria, were not considered sufficient to correctly perform the taxonomic analysis. Picture-video data that do not have these requirements have been removed from the overall analysis. Other somatic regions were objectively difficult to evaluate from the collected pictures. Moreover, since the quality of the documents obtained by the cameras is important to obtain reliable data, we evaluated for each picture how many diagnostic characters were visible. All the ones that showed distinct pelage characteristics of domestic cat (e.g. white extensive on paw and flank, tail bands absent etc.) have been discarded and are therefore not part of the wildcat database. Finally, in order to standardize the numerous data obtained by camera traps, we have retrospectively defined the single capture event (detection event), such as the picture or video with a time interval of at least 1 hour from the following event. With this information we have outlined the distribution of the species in the Veneto Region, using the UTM 10X10 km mapping system.

HISTORICAL DATA

The European wildcat disappeared from Veneto between the 19th and 20th centuries. The historical information is fragmentary and rather confusing. Catullo himself, the most important naturalistic historical source for the territory of Belluno, although confirming its presence in the 19th century did not define its consistency and exact distribution (CATULLO 1838). Also, for De Betta (DE BETTA 1863) the species would have been present in Cansiglio and in any case Dal Piaz considered it, extinct from the eastern Alps, in the first decades of the last century (DAL PIAZ 1928).

A survey carried out between 1978-80 on the objective findings known at that time for the Friuli Venezia Giulia area, but also in that of Belluno (Veneto), allows us to ascertain the presence of the felid in the Trieste and Gorizia Karst up to the course of the Isonzo River (RAGNI 1981).

Among the historical data, although anecdotal

and without certainty that it was actually *Felis silvestris*, we would like to point out Fossa (FOSSA 1988), which reports about ten putative wildcat specimens caught in the Belluno area between 1938 and 1983.

The causes of its extinction were multiple and essentially due to the combination of direct persecution by man and at the same time, the drastic reduction of its elective habitat, the forest. At the turn of the fifties and sixties, with the abandonment of the medium-high mountains, the arboreal vegetation recovered the spaces of the past and this allowed its gradual return in a spontaneous way. But the slow and constant recolonization was made possible above all by the status of protected and not huntable species.

The European wildcat has recolonized the Italian Alps of the northeast thanks to the dynamic and consistent Dinaric-Balkan population, appearing for the first time in Friuli Venezia Giulia during the 60's. The expansion of the species' range has slowly, but constantly continued, as to reach, in 1983, the Veneto Region. In the second half of the 80's it was thought that the edge of the area of the wildcat was no longer on the Gorizia Karst, but about 60 km northwest, where geographically the Julian Prealps ended and the Carnic ones began. The Veneto figure was positioned, compared to this new margin, more southwest of another 40 km. In the survey conducted by Ragni, Lapini and Perco, no evidence of its presence was found in other areas of Veneto or in Trentino-Alto Adige (RAGNI *et al.* 1987).

OVERVIEW FROM 1983 TO 2015

The first data collected in Veneto territory is an adult male killed in the area of Monte Millifret in Cansiglio Forest in 1983 and was the only objective finding in 19 years. In October 2002 a second record is reported, a young female found on the side of the road near Serravalle (Vittorio Veneto - TV), run over (LOMBARDO *et al.* 2003). In Lombardo *et al.* (2003), it is also mentioned that specimens were often killed during fox hunts on the southern and western slopes of the Cansiglio Forest; on other occasions dead wildcats were found along the railway line from Vittorio Veneto up to the Fadalto Pass. These findings, however, have never been collected or photographed.

Between 2011 and 2012 the first survey with camera traps was carried out on small and medium-sized carnivores in the Eastern Prealps, in four areas between Cansiglio plateau and Monte Cesen, in the Eastern Venetian Prealps (SPADA *et al.* 2014). No wildcats were documented during this project, which took place from a minimum of 21 days to a

maximum of 30 days. For each study area 4 cameras with lures were used.

In 2013 a study with camera traps was started in the DBNP with the aim of monitoring mesocarnivores (SPADA *et al.* 2016). The survey, which ran for three years, ascertained the presence of the felid in the northern sector of the Park, municipality of Longarone, thus confirming the extemporaneous data previously collected in the same area (Sacchet C., Provincial Police Corps of Belluno). This research was also carried out using lures. During the study, the species was documented 11 times, demonstrating unequivocally its stable presence on the orographic right of the Piave River.

In 2015 a wildcat was recorded for the first time on the northern side of Col Visentin, Eastern Venetian Prealps, in the Faverghera area.

From the data collected until 2015, it therefore seemed that the presence of the species, with temporal continuity, was limited in the northernmost part of the DBNP, in the Cansiglio Forest, Lapisina Valley and on the steep northern slopes of Col Visentin (BON & SPADA 2017) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 – The known data of the European wildcat (*Felis silvestris*) in Veneto Region until 2015, using the UTM 10X10 km mapping system. The full black dot (●) represents at least one wildcat data. The black dot with white centre (○) represents the first data collected in 1983.

RECENT SURVEYS (2016 -2020)

After having documented the presence of the wildcat on the ridge of Col Visentin, some of the authors (DEON & TORMEN) started a short monitoring with camera traps and lures between January and May 2016. This is the first targeted, albeit short

and limited, survey of the species. This brief study not only confirmed the presence of the wildcat on this dorsal with 16 capture events of 5 different individuals (RAGNI 2016 pers. comm.), but above all documented the first reproduction in Veneto, when in May 2016 at least one kitten of about 2-2,5 months of age, was caught at the considerable altitude of 1500 m above sea level.

On the basis of previous data collected until spring 2016, the Venetian Prealpine Range was considered the most favourable area for a systematic research on the spread of wildcats. This mountains chain represents in fact, for the biogeographic dynamics of the species, a high value as a faunal corridor in the process of area expansion towards the west. From July 2016 to November 2018 a CT project was conducted on the north-western side of the Venetian Prealps. 23 camera traps were used in different stations without lures, in the municipalities of Belluno, Limana, Vittorio Veneto and Revine Lago. To determine the number of different recorded specimens, morphological criteria were used to distinguish between free-ranging domestic cat (*Felis catus*) and European wildcat (*F. silvestris*) (RAGNI 1981, RAGNI & POSSENTI 1996). Throughout the monitoring, 34 pictures of wildcats were obtained. A minimum of nine different specimens, excluding two kittens, were identified. The estimated wildcat annual density was 0,12 wildcats/100 ha. The rate of capture success for the European wildcats was 1 capture/199 trap-days. Nine stations out of 23 captured at least one wildcat (CATELLO *et al.* 2021a).

In December 2018 a pilot study of hair trapping was started in the prealpine area of Valbelluna (Limana), where each lure-stick was combined with a camera trap (CATELLO *et al.* 2022 (b), Catello *et al.*, this volume). The aim was to test this method on the population of north-eastern Italy and to match genotype to phenotype of documented individuals, trying in this way to increase the knowledge necessary to improve the analysis based on pictures and videos. A total of 10 rough wooden stick of European spruce (*Picea abies*) were used in front of which 10 camera traps were placed. The lure-sticks with their respective cameras were distributed over an area of 12,2 km². They were sprayed with valerian tincture and controlled every 7-10 days. During the survey 5 samples of wildcat hair were collected and allowed the genotyping of a specimen.

Two other investigations are currently underway, within the DBNP and in the Eastern Venetian Prealps, both are applying the CT methods and other surveys are in the planning.

Tab. 1 - m = male, f = female - Immature (IM) = 5-10 months, subadult (SA) = 11-24 months, adult (AD) = specimen over two years (GÖTZ 2015). * Lack of distinction in one or more of the tail bands

	Date	Place	Coordinates	Altitude (m asl)	Cause of death	Gender	Age	Weight (gr)	Phenotype	Genotype
1	1983	M.te Millifret (Vittorio Veneto TV)	46° 03' 02'' N 12° 20' 36'' E	1490	shooting	m	AD	/	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	/
2	25.10.2002	Serravalle (Vittorio Veneto TV)	46° 00' 01'' N 12° 17' 23'' E	148	roadkill	f	IM	3100	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	<i>Felis silvestris</i>
3	02.04.2017	Poiatte (Farra d'Alpago BL)	46° 06' 18'' N 12° 21' 13'' E	411	roadkill	m	AD	3990	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	<i>Felis silvestris</i>
4	28.09.2019	Scalon (Vas BL)	45° 57' 03'' N 11° 55' 59'' E	216	roadkill	m	IM	2500	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	<i>Felis silvestris</i>
5	04.12.2019	Col Indes (Tambre BL)	46° 07' 36'' N 12° 27' 04'' E	1290	shooting	f	AD	4750	<i>Felis silvestris</i> *	ongoing
6	11.02.2020	Fener (Alano di Piave BL)	45° 53' 52'' N 11° 57' 09'' E	186	roadkill	f	IM	?	<i>Felis silvestris</i> *	ongoing

DATA COLLECTED BY ILLEGAL OR INCIDENTAL KILLING

A total of 6 wildcats have been run over or illegally killed in the Veneto Region in the last 37 years (Tab. 1). We describe them briefly in chronological order:

1) The first specimen for Veneto was an adult male shot down in 1983 (RAGNI *et al.* 1987) at Monte Millifret (Vittorio Veneto – Treviso), along the edge of the Cansiglio plateau, on the eastern side of the Lapisina Valley, opposite Col Visentin. The skin specimen is the property of a private collection.

2) In October 2002 a young European wildcat female was found on the side of a road on the northern outskirts of Vittorio Veneto (Serravalle). The cause of death is attributable to the roadkill (Lombardo *et al.* 2003). The specimen was subjected to both genetic and morphological analysis.

3) In April 2017 a specimen of a wildcat was found run over along the edge of the road along the Santa Croce Lake near Poiatte (Farra d'Alpago). The death occurred following the crushing of the ribcage and liver caused by an investment.

The specimen collected (COMIOTTO D.) and preserved by the Provincial Police Corps of Belluno, was later examined by Prof. Bernardino Ragni. Two

biological samples of muscle tissue were also sent to the Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA) which conducted the genetic analysis for the genotype determination. The subject, an adult male of 3/4 years of age (weighed 3990 gr) and was found to be in perfect health on necroscopic examination.

3) In September 2019 at the edge of the Provincial Road near Scalon (municipality of Vas), a young male was found (weight: 2500 g). The specimen had traumas on the head compatible with car accident, that plausibly represents the cause of death. The individual was recovered by the Provincial Police Corps of Belluno and then taken to the Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA) for the morphological and genetic analysis.

5) An act of poaching killed on December 4th, 2019, an adult female (4750 g). The killing took place at the edge of the Cansiglio Forest (Col Indes), in the municipality of Tambre d'Alpago. The presence of the female wildcat was documented by a camera trap only a few days before, a few meters from the place where she was killed later. In this case the specimen was also recovered by the Provincial Police Corps of Belluno. To date the

* Shortly before the review phase of this paper, we received 6 new videos of wildcat caught by camera traps placed in the study area of Col Visentin.

results of the genetic and morphological analysis have not yet been received.

6) The first roadkill for 2020 it is a young female and was collected near Fener (Alano di Piave) along the Piave River, in the Venetian Prealps on the border between the provinces of Belluno and Treviso. The carcass has been recovered in order to determine the genotype and to conduct the morphological analysis (BISSONI 2020, pers. comm.). In this case as well, their results are not available at the moment.

RESULTS

Overall, the data collected in Veneto, from 1983 to May 2020, are 137, of which 9,5 % (13 findings) were discarded for a lack of the requirements established during pre-analysis. Out the 124* data, most of them, 93 (75,1%), were collected along the Col Visentin - Monte Cesen Ridge, due to the intensive research effort carried out in this area in recent years. On the orographic right side of the Piave River there are 17 (13,7%), most of them in the northernmost valleys of the DBNP, such as the Costa dei Nass and Ross Valley. Eleven data (8,8%) came from the area that has the Cansiglio Forest and the Alpage Basin as its fulcrum. The remaining 3 data (2,4%) were collected between Monte Cesen and Monte Grappa.

In recent years, some cameras have documented the presence of the species in new areas, considerably widening the margins of the known range: two data

from January 2018, the first in the Cordevole Valley, near Salet, the second on the southern slopes of Monte Serva (CANAL 2018, pers. comm.) and in June again in 2018, when a camera trap located in Monte Grappa (FERRARO 2018, pers. comm.) documented a wildcat that currently represents the most southwest biogeographic station in the Veneto Prealps. If compared with the known data up to 2015, these have increased significantly in recent years (18 vs. 124; + 588%), certainly thanks to the considerable research effort, but also due to the greater general attention to species by the hunting world, simple hikers, etc. (Fig. 3).

Altogether 114 (92%) capture events were collected by camera traps (Fig. 4). Of these, 107 events have been viewed by us, a small part of the data collected and already published were not accessible.

Overall, 38 pictures (35%) have 5 diagnosable coat patters (shape of tail tip and its distinct banding - *Caudalis*, stripes on nape - *Occipitalis-Cervicalis*, stripes on shoulder - *Scapularis*, dorsal line - *Dorsalis* and flanks & hindquarters - *Lateralis*), 21 pictures (20%) have 4 visible criterions, 30 (28%) have 3 visible characters and the remaining 18 (17%) only two. It's worth noting that 89 (83%) have at least 3 diagnosable coat patters.

Of the four pictures/videos collected not by camera traps (i.e. other, Fig. 4), three clearly have 5 visible diagnostic characters, while one has three.

The six recovered carcasses in the last 37 years come from the of the Eastern Venetian Prealps chain,

Fig. 3 - Number and type of European wildcat *Felis silvestris* data recorded in Veneto from 1983 until May 2020.

Fig. 4 - Type of data collected about the European wild cat *Felis silvestris* in Veneto from 1983 to May 2020.

four from the Cansiglio Forest, Alpago, Vittorioese and the remaining two from the narrow valley of the Piave River between Feltre and Pederobba. The phenotype analyses of all these specimens indicate the subjects as belonging to the species *Felis silvestris*.

For three of them, Serravalle (2), Poiatte (3) and Scalon (4) there are also genetic and morphological analyses that confirm the taxonomic diagnosis based on the pelage characters. For the specimens of Col Indes (5) and Fener (6), genetic investigations have been started, but at the time this paper was written, the results have not yet been available. In spite of some discrepancies in the *Caudalis* somatic region of two subjects (Col Indes and Fener), we have considered, waiting for more detailed analysis, to classify them both as *Felis silvestris* (Tab. 1). The adult male shot in 1983 in Cansiglio (1), a skin specimen, the only given indications of the pelage characters do exist.

DISCUSSION

All these figures suggest that the distribution range of the species at the moment only concerns the northern part of the Region, with the provinces of Belluno and Treviso. These data, however, considerably expand the known range until 2015 (Fig. 2 and Fig. 5).

The new finds demonstrate the presence of the felid with a vital deme (the two documented reproductions, in 2016 and 2017, have to

be considered very important events for the recolonization of the species) along the entire ridge of the eastern Veneto Prealps, on Monte Grappa, in the lower Cordevole Valley, Monte Serva, the Longarone side of the DBNP, Gallina Valley, Alpago-Cansiglio-Vittorioese.

It is predictable, therefore, that the expansion of the species from Friuli Venezia Giulia towards the southwest, after having crossed the ecological corridors of the pre-Alpine forests, with prevalence of broad-leaved trees, of the Eastern Veneto Prealps, can reach the Asiago plateau, the Vicenza Prealps and then the Lessinia. The four wildcat carcasses found after roadkill were recovered along the Cansiglio Forest-Col Visentin-Monte Cesen route, demonstrating the importance of this corridor in the south-western expansion of the species.

An interesting record, from a biogeographical point of view and which probably shows how the Valsugana is an interesting junction between Veneto and the Adige Valley, is given by a wildcat documented by a camera trap on December 5th, 2017, not far from Trento, on the eastern slopes of Monte Bondone, on the orographic right of the Adige River. This is the first data of presence of this species in Trentino and at the moment, the westernmost in the Italian Alps. Its origin is most likely linked to the present population in the province of Belluno. With this new record so far to the west we are faced with an apparent lack of data for about 55 km from the nearest known station, wildcat of Monte Grappa

(municipality of Seren del Grappa - Belluno), while it is about 80 km compared to that of Cordevole Valley (municipality of Sedico - Belluno).

Compared to the biogeographic limit of the species located in 1987 on the westernmost side of the Julian Prealps (RAGNI *et al.* 1987), we now have sufficient evidence to say that the current geographical boundary of the species seems to have moved southwest of 80-90 km, in the southern part of the province of Belluno (Fig. 5). On the other hand, already from the data indicated by Lapini (2006), it was clear that the margin of the species had shifted further west, as the specimens were constantly reported in the pre-Alpine area on the border with Veneto.

The vitality of the wildcat in the Carnic Prealps of Pordenone (Friuli Venezia Giulia) is also indicated by a recent survey conducted with the CT method, which estimates the average annual density in 0.47 individuals/100ha (FONDA, 2015), almost four times (0,47 vs. 0,12) the density found in the Veneto Prealps (CATELLO *et al.* 2021 (a)).

In any case, considering the dynamics of the species, the current margin in Veneto is considered to be completely provisional, as demonstrated by the specimens documented on Monte Grappa and Monte Bondone in the province of Trento.

Fig. 5 - The known data of the European wildcat (*Felis silvestris*) in Veneto Region until May 2020, using the UTM 10X10 km mapping system. The full black dot (●) represents at least one wildcat data.

CONCLUSION

The data collected shows the presence of the European wildcat in two provinces of Veneto; In the southern part of the province of Belluno and in the northwest of the province of Treviso. The southernmost data we know is located about 1 km from the province of Vicenza. The medium-low density (0.12 wildcats/100ha) found during a three-year CT survey in the Venetian Prealps (CATELLO *et al.* 2021 (a)) is coherent with the density of a population on the fringe of the distribution area. The expansion of the European wildcat *Felis silvestris* in Veneto territory towards southwest is still believed to be taking place.

The main factors limiting the survival and conservation of the wildcat are road mortality and poaching, habitat fragmentation and potentially hybridization with the domestic cat.

In north-eastern Italy, Friuli Venezia Giulia and Veneto numerous wildcats have been killed accidentally (roadkill), or illegally (shooting). Hybridization, on the contrary, even if it has been documented, does not seem to represent a problem at the moment. All the genetic and biometric analyses, until 2006, performed on 50 specimens from Friuli Venezia Giulia (LAPINI 2006) and the four from Veneto, the Vittorio Veneto specimen of 2002, the one from Poiate (Farra d'Alpago) of 2017, Scalon (Vas) 2019 and the wildcat genotyped during the hair trapping pilot project (Valpiana – Limana) (CATELLO *et al.* 2022 (b), Catello *et al.*, this volume), exclude the presence of DNA sequences typical of the domestic form. These data are also supported by recent study (TIESMEYER *et al.* 2020) which confirms that hybridization is for the time being a marginal aspect in the population in the Eastern Alps. Hybridization is often observed in expanding marginal micro populations (CURRAT *et al.* 2008): this phenomenon could even facilitate the colonization process of new territories, since the less mobile specimens, the females in the case of the European wildcat, can, at least temporarily, be replaced by the females of domestic cat (PETIT *et al.* 2004).

During the research carried out in the Eastern Veneto Prealps, the results showed some phenotypic anomalies in at least five specimens, suggesting that this could be the result of the introgression of domestic cat (*Felis catus*) genes into the genotypes of the population. But we also have to consider that the origin of this population can only be from the one present in Friuli Venezia Giulia, therefore with traits more variable than the Apennine/Sicilian population (RAGNI *et al.* 1987, RAGNI B. 2017 pers. comm.).

Since most of the data (92 %) were collected using camera traps, it is important to underline that even if coat patterns can serve as a good surrogate of genetic markers during taxonomic diagnosis (BALLESTEROS-DUPERÓN *et al.* 2014, KITCHENER *et al.* 2005, KRÜGER *et al.* 2009 and RAGNI & POSSENTI 1996), in some cases, where the quality of the document is not high, there is a concrete possibility of misinterpretation between European wildcat and domestic cat with striped-tabby pelage. For this reason, this type of data, although fundamental, still has a lower degree of validity than the morphological/genetic analyses. However, we have to emphasize that in 83% of the data collected with the camera traps at least three diagnostic characters of the coat are visible, thus facilitating the differential diagnosis and making it unambiguously. Our data thus indicated that the camera trapping method is a valuable technique for monitoring an elusive carnivore with low population density such as the wildcat. Therefore, we believe that our results can reliably represent the current distribution of the species in the Veneto Region.

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THE USE OF HAIR TRAPPING AND CAMERA TRAPS FOR MONITORING THE EUROPEAN WILDCAT (*Felis silvestris silvestris* Schreber, 1777) IN THE EASTERN VENETIAN PREALPS (ITALY)

USO DI TRAPPOLE PER LA CATTURA DI PELI E TRAPPOLAGGIO FOTOGRAFICO PER MONITORARE IL GATTO SELVATICO EUROPEO (*Felis silvestris silvestris* Schreber, 1777) NELLE PREALPI ORIENTALI VENETE

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Abstract. In this pilot project two non-invasive techniques, hair trapping and camera trapping, were tested at the same time to monitor the European wildcat in a study area in the Eastern Veneto Prealps. Between December 2018 and March 2019, 10 rough-sawn spruce sticks matching 10 cameras were used. The objectives of the project were: to verify the effectiveness of valerian tincture as an attractant, both on wildcats and other animal species, to increase our knowledge about the species in an anthropized area with high presence of free-ranging domestic cats and to combine the two investigative methods, to improve the reliability of taxonomic diagnosis based on phenotype. Valerian tincture has proved to be an effective olfactory attractant for the wildcat, obtaining in all documented cases an interaction with the stick. Our results demonstrated the high potential of hair trapping, when combined with genetic analysis and camera traps. The simultaneous use of these methods not only allowed to detect the presence of wildcats in low density and recently colonized areas, but also enabled individual identification, associating the genetic data to the distinctive traits of the specimen's coat. Finally, our survey also significantly facilitated the collection of hair samples, providing evidences to immediately discard those of non-target species.

Riassunto. In questo progetto pilota sono state testate contemporaneamente due tecniche non-invasive, trappolaggio di pelo (hair trapping) e fototrappolaggio, per monitorare il Gatto selvatico europeo in un'area di studio nelle Prealpi Venete orientali. Tra dicembre 2018 e marzo 2019 sono stati utilizzati 10 paletti di abete abbinando ad ognuno di essi una fototrappola. Gli obiettivi del progetto erano poter verificare l'efficacia della tintura di valeriana come attrattivo, sia sul gatto selvatico che su altre specie animali, incrementare le nostre conoscenze sulla specie in un'area antropizzata con elevata presenza di gatti domestici e infine, combinando i due metodi investigativi, migliorare l'affidabilità della diagnosi tassonomica basata sul fenotipo. La tintura di valeriana ha dimostrato di essere un efficace attrattivo olfattivo per il gatto selvatico, ottenendo in tutti i casi documentati un'interazione con il paletto. I nostri risultati hanno provato l'alto potenziale del trappolaggio di pelo, se combinato con l'analisi genetica e le fototrappole. L'utilizzo simultaneo di questi metodi non solo ha permesso di rilevare la presenza del gatto selvatico in un'area a bassa densità recentemente colonizzata, ma ha consentito pure l'identificazione individuale, associando il dato genetico ai caratteri distintivi del mantello dell'esemplare. La nostra indagine è stata infine notevolmente agevolata durante la raccolta dei campioni di pelo, potendo scartare immediatamente i campioni delle specie non-target.

INTRODUCTION

The European wildcat *Felis silvestris* has a wide and fragmented distribution in Europe and occupies a variety of very different habitats (DRISCOLL & NOWELL 2010, LOZANO 2010). In Italy, the Cispadana population ranges from the Tuscan-Emilian Apennines to Calabria, but also in Sicily (RAGNI *et al.* 2014). The species is well documented also in north-eastern Italy and it is connected with the Dinaric-Balkan population (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2015). Recent observations have also documented the presence of the felid in Liguria (GAVAGNIN 2020 pers. comm.).

From the most recent researches carried out

in north-eastern Italy, it seems that the westernmost margin of the distribution area of the species is located in the southern part of the province of Belluno and along the pre-Alpine ridge of the province of Treviso (CATELLO *et al.* 2022 (a), Catello *et al.*, this volume).

Within the Felidae family, small species, such as the European wildcat, are relatively poorly studied.

In the last years, however, the implementation of numerous targeted researches has significantly improved our knowledge on this carnivore. A remarkable contribution to level the gap with larger species, such as the Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) or the Iberian lynx (*Lynx pardinus*), has been given

mainly by the use of the camera traps, a method that can successfully monitor carnivores with nocturnal, elusive and low-density habits.

Camera trapping, although it has significantly increased our data collection capabilities, requires to provide reliable, good quality images. However, there is always the possibility of incorrect taxonomic analysis, given the potential similarity of the characters with domestic cats with striped-tabby pelage.

The simultaneous application of several investigative techniques (e.g. camera trapping and genetics) can reduce this bias and improve the reliability of the taxonomic diagnosis based on distinctive traits of the specimen's coat visible from the picture.

Considering the results of previous surveys carried out in Italy (ANILE *et al.* 2012, VELLI *et al.* 2015), we wanted to test the effectiveness of hair trapping in the Eastern Prealps of Veneto, where the European wildcat population shows medium-low density (CATELLO *et al.* 2021). A pilot project was then started, using lure sticks and camera traps at each station at the same time. The objectives were to increase the knowledge of the species in Veneto Region and to verify the response to the attractant for each detected species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Between 01.12.2018 and 31.03.2019 in a study area located in the Eastern Veneto Prealps (Fig. 1), a research of hair trapping was conducted by matching each stick with a camera trap. The study area is located within the municipality of Limana, on the edge of the small plateau of Valpiana, at an average height of 756 m above sea level (range: 650-900). There are some artificial plants of larch (*Larix decidua*), spruce (*Picea abies*), beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) and a widespread renewal of

ash (*Fraxinus spp.*) with sporadic sycamore (*Acer pseudoplatanus*). The extensive lawn areas are interrupted by birches (*Betula spp.*). Along the edges of the plateau there are numerous limestone outcrops. In the area, the wildcat had already been documented in the past, as the presence of numerous free-ranging domestic cats. These characteristics and the fact that almost all the stations are well accessible, even during the winter period, make this area in the Belluno Prealps extremely interesting for an investigation.

A total of 9 sticks with 9 camera traps were used in the study area. A tenth stick with a camera, was positioned inside the municipality of Lentiai (Stabie), also in the eastern Prealps of Veneto. The sticks were made of rough-sawn spruce of 70 cm in height and 5 X 3 cm and have been buried in a vertical position for 20 cm and positioned at a distance of 618 m \pm 248.6 (range: 250-1100) meters from each other. Each stick was identified with a code and geo-localized. As lure has been used valerian (*Valeriana officinalis*) root extracted into ethanol 70% (Dronania pharmaceuticals GmbH) which has been shown to have a good effectiveness in attracting the wildcat (HUPE & SIMON 2007, STEYER *et al.* 2013) and get a good rubbing response on the stick (MONTERROSO *et al.* 2011). The sticks were sprayed with valerian tincture on all four sides. In an attempt to achieve a more lasting effect, a hole of 1.5 cm of diameter and 5 cm of depth was drilled in the apex of the stick, which was filled with valerian-impregnated sawdust. The hole was then plugged with a piece of wood. On the sides were also made holes with a diameter of 0.4 cm to facilitate the exit of the valerian essence. In order to optimize the capture of the hair, numerous cuts were also made along the four edges of the stick (STEYER *et al.* 2013).

The stick inspection was done every 7-10

Fig. 1 - Distribution ranges of the European wildcat *Felis silvestris* (A) and the Veneto Region (Italy) (B), where we conducted our research in 2018-2019

Fig. 2 - Study area (Valpiana) with the minimum convex polygon (continuous line) and the additional buffer strip (dotted line). ▲ Hair trap/camera trap with wildcat capture event (46,084 N 12, 2052 E). ● hair trap/camera trap without wildcat capture event

days. The camera traps were checked on site to immediately ascertain which animals rubbed themselves on the stick. The hairs were collected with forceps and placed in plastic envelopes, and then stored in the dark with silica gel in a non-humid environment away from heat sources to avoid degradation of DNA. After each sampling event, the stick was then cleaned with a brush with metal bristles to remove any unseen organic hair or remains. The valerian tincture was renewed by spraying the stick with a nebulizer and drenching the sawdust present in the apical hole again. The cameras were placed at a height of 40-70 cm and at a distance of 2-3 meters from the stick.

The traced minimum convex polygon, obtained considering the outermost nine stations in our study's area (Valpiana) is 4 km². Considering that our study's area, although in the Alpine environment, develops at a low mountain altitude with little difference in altitude and that the smallest known home ranges for the species vary considerably from 1.5 km² (GERMAIN 2008) to 2.7 Km² (BIZZARRI *et al.* 2010), we further created a buffer strip of 900 m to the MCP, thus obtaining an area of 12.2 km² (Fig. 2).

From the collected images, on the basis of phenotype analysis (RAGNI & POSSENTI 1996) it was possible to select the hair samples belonging to the European wildcat and subsequently extracted and analysed their DNA using 10 species-specific autosomal microsatellites markers as described in Mattucci *et al.* (2013).

All the videos collected by the cameras were examined to evaluate the behaviour of each single animal in the presence of the valerian-impregnated stick. To standardize the analysis an ethogram (VELLI *et al.* 2015) was used, where its possible reactions are indicated (Tab. 1). The data collected from Stabie's stick are part of the ethological analysis, but not in the calculation of the other parameters (e.g. capture success rate etc.), since it is not part of the Valpiana study area.

RESULTS

Ten sticks were used during the survey, nine were placed in the municipality of Limana (Valpiana) at an average height of 756 m above sea level, while the tenth stick was placed in the

Tab. 1 - Ethogram of the reactions at the sticks recorded by the camera traps (from VELLI *et al.* 2015). The percentage of occurrence concerns only the reactions of domestic cats and the wildcat specimen.

Label	Name	Behaviour	Percentage of occurrence
I	Indifference	The individual shows no interest in the lure	9
C	Curiosity	The individual is somehow attracted by the lure. It sniffs and remains next to the picket for a while. It does not touch the trap	5
FM	Facial marking	The individual shows a typical facial marking behaviour rubbing the cheeks and the forehead on the picket	32
SM	Spray marking	The individual marks the picket by spraying on the trap	9
SI	Strong interaction	The individual strongly interacts with the lure by rubbing the face and the body, sitting by the picket and scratching it with the nails	45
D	Diffidence	The individual looks at the lure appearing suspicious and insecure. It does not get too close to the pickets	0
F	Fear	The individual reacts suddenly leaving the sampling station.	0

municipality of Lentiai (Stabie) at an altitude of 310 m above sea level.

The sampling events were 79, with an average control every 9 days (9.4). The total hair trap-days were 727, average 72.7, while for the camera traps they were 641, average 64.1. This difference is explained by the fact that one camera was stolen and others (3) were recovered earlier than expected to avoid further thefts. Altogether on the stations (Valpiana and Stabie), only one was positive for the wildcat, both for camera trapping and hair trapping, while in 6 stations the domestic cat was documented.

A total of 13 hair samples were collected in the study area of Valpiana, but only 6 have been genetically analysed. Examining the videos, we were able to discard the samples of the non-target species, only selecting the 5 hair samples, where the rubbing of the wildcat on the stick had been documented by the camera, plus a sixth hair sampled, where the camera had not worked. Of the six samples, one was successfully genotyped with a capture success rate of 0.14 genotyped hair samples per 100 trap-days.

The cameras have documented within the study area of Valpiana 5 subjects of domestic cat and one of wildcat. From the characteristics of the coat, it can be seen that all five captures are from the same specimen. The rate of capture success was 0.78 ind./100 trap-days, slightly higher than the one found in a neighbouring area during a 3-year survey of 0.5 ind./100 trap-days (CATELLO *et al.* 2021).

Overall there were 85 captures of 9 different species during the study period: fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) 5, beech marten (*Martes foina*) 7, badger (*Meles*

meles) 15, domestic cat (*Felis catus*) 17, wild cat (*Felis silvestris*) 5, red deer (*Cervus elaphus*) 5, roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*) 16, brown hare (*Lepus europaeus*) 6, red squirrel (*Sciurus vulgaris*) 9. Among the documented species, the reaction to the lure was very different (Fig. 3). A strong interaction was recorded only for the felids. In the 5 documented occasions on the wildcat, 4 happened at night and only one during the day and occurred in December (2) and January (3). The 17 domestic cat captures are distributed over the entire research period December (2), January (3), February (6) and March (6). In 45% of the cases where the felids were documented, a strong interaction (FI) was recorded (Tab. 1). For the wildcat, this type of interaction occurred in 80 % of cases (4 out of 5) (Fig. 3).

DISCUSSION

The data collected in the Valpiana study area, with the simultaneous use of the two survey systems, made it possible to identify an European wildcat density of 0.08 ind./1Km², a slightly lower value than that found in a three-year survey of the Eastern Veneto Prealps, 0.12 ind./1Km² (CATELLO *et al.* 2021a). From the pictures we identified 5 different domestic cats, 0.4 ind./1Km², therefore a higher presence than the already mentioned three-year survey carried out about 3 Km away from Valpiana with 0.04 ind./Km². Although considering the limits of the pilot project, its results document the constant presence of the wildcat, recorded in the area since June 2018, in

Fig. 3 - Ethogram of the behaviours detected by the camera traps. I = Indifference, C = Curiosity, FM = Facial marking, SM = Spray marking, SI = Strong interaction, D = Diffidence, F = Fear

Fig. 4 – Species that have had an interaction with the picket: FM+SM+SI

an anthropized area with a high presence of free-ranging domestic cats. Both were recorded on two occasions on the same site a few hours apart from each other.

The hair trapping success rate (0.14/100 trap days) was slightly higher than other studies (0.07/100 trap days STEYER *et al.* 2013, 0.08/100 trap days VELLI *et al.* 2015). This parameter is related to the behaviour of wildcats towards sticks, in our study there were always interactions (Fig. 4), but Monterroso *et al.* (2011) found that only 11.5% showed investigative behaviour.

A research by Anile *et al.* (2012) in Sicily documented the total lack of interest of wildcats in valerian, while in Velli *et al.* (2015), this has been documented in 51,7 % of cases. There were positive results, however, both in Switzerland Kéry *et al.* (2011) and in Germany Steyer *et al.* (2013). This variation in the response to valerian may have genetic bases.

In the present pilot project only one hair sample out of five (20%) provided reliable individual genotypes. This is mainly related to DNA degradation caused by weathering exposure. Other studies showed lower results (10% MONTERROSO *et al.* 2014, 11% VELLI *et al.* 2015). However, despite the few samples collected, it was possible to associate the genetic data with the picture of only one individual (Fig. 5). A similar result, but with a higher research effort, was obtained in the survey of Velli *et al.* (2015).

The analysis of the ethogram shows that only 5 species had contact with the stick impregnated with valerian, red squirrel, badger, beech marten, domestic cat and wildcat, but only with the last two there was a strong interaction. The wildcat specimen rubbed itself on the stick in two cases for more than 6 minutes, covering a large surface of the body. However, still underlining the limited case history of our pilot project, we can say that the wildcat

Fig. 5 - The genotyped wildcat by the picket

specimen had 100% of the capture events a contact with the stick. Velli *et al.* (2015) found that 44.4% of the subjects documented in a study area in the Foreste Casentinesi National Park left hair on the sticks.

CONCLUSION

In this study we have integrated two research systems, hair trapping and camera trapping to document the presence of the European wildcat in an anthropized area of the Veneto pre-Alps in the province of Belluno. Valerian tincture has proved to be an excellent attractant for the target species, allowing to capture several times a specimen and the collection of 6 hair samples that enabled to characterize the genetic profile, confirming in this way the initial taxonomic analysis and the belonging to the species *Felis silvestris*. Our investigation was also significantly facilitated during the collection of hair samples, being able to immediately discard those of non-target species.

The knowledge about the European wildcat in Veneto is still very limited, due to the objective difficulties of obtaining data, given its presence at low densities and its extremely elusive habits. For this reason, new genetic, morphological and ecological data are very important, especially in areas where the felid has been recently confirmed.

Further investigations are therefore hoped for,

in order to better understand the dynamics of the species in an area so highly frequented by domestic cats and possibly implement conservation measures.

The pilot project, while demonstrating the validity of the method, has presented some limitations.

The first is the limited use of sticks. Weber and Hintermann (2008) recommend using 3 of them for each square kilometre in order to have in this way a good chance of capture.

Second, Valpiana is a very anthropized area, with a large presence of hikers, hunters etc. The monitoring stations, composed of rough-sawn spruce sticks and cameras, can sometimes be very visible and lead to vandalism or theft, thus limiting the sampling effort.

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THE EUROPEAN WILDCAT IN THE ITALIAN WESTERN RANGE: SOMETHING NEW?

IL GATTO SELVATICO EUROPEO NEL SUB AREALE OCCIDENTALE ITALIANO: QUALCOSA DI NUOVO?

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Abstract. Herein the results of an investigation conducted in these two regions are reported, representing a revision of the sub-area in order to facilitate distribution data updating.

Specimens identified in Museum collections attest wildcat presence in plain woods near Turin up to the early decades of the 20th century. The presence in the Ligurian and Maritime Prealps is confirmed at least until legal protection (1977). The European wildcat absence from Po river areas is linked to forest cover disappearance in plains, hills and mid-mountains. Deforestation of the Po area for agricultural purposes is a remote process that has become pushed over the last two centuries, causing theriocenoses modification and forestry species disappearance. The wild felid, considered harmful like all carnivores and raptors, was huntable, caught with traps to sell the fur, and collectors sought after him; there was also locally food consumption. After decades of missing data, two distinct events in Liguria allowed the identification of two specimens: a male in the western mountains and a female in Ligurian-Piedmontese Apennines - where a clear wild heritage can be found. It is important in this regard to update the distribution framework and contrast risk of variability loss due to hybridization with domestic cats.

Riassunto. L'areale italiano del gatto selvatico europeo include una sub-popolazione storica segnalata nelle province liguri occidentali e piemontesi a ridosso delle Alpi. Vengono qui descritti i risultati di una indagine condotta in queste due regioni, al fine di fornire una revisione delle conoscenze sulla specie in questo sub-areale storico, ed aggiornare quindi i dati di distribuzione. Esemplari presenti in collezioni museali attestano la presenza del gatto selvatico nei boschi della pianura torinese fino ai primi decenni del XX secolo. La presenza nelle Prealpi Liguri e Marittime è confermata almeno fino alla tutela legale della specie (1977). L'assenza del gatto selvatico europeo dalle aree fluviali del Po è invece probabilmente legata alla scomparsa della copertura forestale in pianura, collina e media montagna. La deforestazione dell'area padana a fini agricoli è un processo remoto che si è realizzato negli ultimi due secoli, causando una modifica nelle teriocenosi, con la scomparsa delle specie forestali. In passato il gatto selvatico, considerato dannoso come tutti i carnivori e i rapaci, era cacciabile, catturato con trappole per la pelliccia, e ricercato dai collezionisti; da segnalare anche il suo consumo come cibo, a livello locale. Dopo decenni di dati mancanti, due distinti eventi in Liguria consentono di identificare due esemplari: un maschio trovato nelle montagne occidentali e una femmina proveniente dall'Appennino ligure-piemontese, a conferma della presenza del genotipo selvatico. È importante a questo proposito aggiornare il quadro di distribuzione e contrastare il rischio di perdita di variabilità dovuta alla possibile ibridazione con i gatti domestici.

INTRODUCTION

The European wildcat (*Felis s. silvestris*, Schreber 1777) is a carnivore of particular interest in the Italian fauna. The felid distribution is not continuous in Italy, as the risk of hybridization with domestic cats induces variability loss increasing fragmentation problems.

For this reason the conservation *status* of the Italian population is classified as NT *Near Threatened* and it is important to encourage any actions for updating distribution framework.

EUROPEAN WILDCAT ITALIAN RANGE AND ITS EVOLUTION

According to the distribution model proposed by Ragni (RAGNI *et al.* 1993), the European wildcat

range in Italy is subdivided in three distinct sub-areas: the largest concerns the Apennines, including Sicily; the second concerns Friulian Prealps; a third one refers to the mountains and western valleys between Liguria and Piedmont.

Compared by the initial model described by Bernardino Ragni, in recent years the Apennines range and the Eastern range have showed some evident expansion phenomena: this carnivore has been spotted in the Foreste Casentinesi National Park, in Pratomagno Aretino and Tuscany Tyrrhenian areas.

This framework expands significantly the central areas of distribution and offers interesting perspectives for Northern Apennines, where the carnivore was not reported in the past and where a suitable habitat can be found.

In the eastern side, the Veneto areas of colonization dates back to about twenty years, as recently the wild felid has been found in Dolomiti Bellunesi National Park (Catello *et al.*, this volume); also recently an observation near Trento was achieved by cameratrapping.

The western distribution does not seem to show similar expansion phenomena.

Agricultural Forestry Ministry D.M. May, 4 1971 and Hunting Law n° 968/1977 have decreed the end of carnivore hunting that was an important cause of rarefaction and local disappearance for the species.

In western Ligurian-Piedmontese areas, objective findings have not been reported for a long time.

The western population isolation is an important critical factor, since wildcat does not occur in the French areas immediately nearby.

French distribution offers actually positive prospects due to a stable presence for about fifteen years in several Departments near the Alps, such as Savoie, Isère, Chartreuse, Vercors, and a South progression towards the Mediterranean areas.

Swiss Jura colonization, by French Jura recently occupied areas, represents an additional potential source areas for the North-West - Central Italian sector and for lowers alpine valleys.

THE EUROPEAN WILDCAT HISTORICAL DISTRIBUTION IN THE WESTERN AREA: BORDERS NEEDS TO BE REDEFINED

In his report on biogeographical distribution of *Felis s. silvestris* in Italy (RAGNI *et al.*, 1993), Bernardino Ragni defined the western sub-range as the territory corresponding to the Imperia province and part of the Savona and Cuneo provinces. The boundaries of this sub-area were rigidly specified by establishing the limit at Monte Settepani in Savona province and at the watershed between the upper Tanaro basin in the Cuneo province and the Ligurian basins of Argentina and Arroscia.

Source of this information was the evaluation of finds preserved at “Giacomo Doria” Museum in Genoa and others collections of Northern Italy.

As a first consequence of these territorial limits, the cartographic representation of the wildcat distribution in Italy has so far been limited to the extreme portion of the Ligurian territory, describing a very restricted, almost residual, sub-area.

The distribution map by REN (National Ecological Network for Italian vertebrates Conservation, 2002) similarly only reports the Ligurian portion; the distribution maps relating to Piedmontese carnivores produced by Piedmont Region shows also only a trace of regional historical records.

This representation must be modified, because

it appears to be of little significance and indirectly affects the lack of information on the animal, leading to difficulties to promote actions with local authorities in order to update distribution data and improve its conservation *status*.

In year 2008, a new investigation conducted in Liguria and Piedmont regions partially re-defined the western distribution borders (GAVAGNIN *et al.*, 2010). In this research two skins from Valle d’Aosta were included. The survey was conducted by checking Museums, public and private collections in the three Regions cited above. Investigations were also carried out in other museums (Milan, Rome, Florence, Nice), 15 civic collections, Protected Areas and naturalistic collections kept at some Religious Scholastic Institutes of the area. In total, 32 collections were examined.

In addition, some historiographical texts, descriptive of the environmental context of 19th and 20th centuries, such as Chabrol de Volvic (1826), Casalis (1853), Verany (1862) and other works in bibliography, were analyzed. A particular attention was paid to works of specifically zoological nature, such as notes by Ghigi (1911), Balletto (1977) and Vigna-Taglianti (1988).

In addition, annals of the hunting magazines “Diana” and “Rivista di Federaccia”, available until 1964, have been examined to detect reports on pest carnivores killing campaigns. Documents on royal hunts in the hunting domains of Savoia

Fig. 1 - Historical specimen from the Royal Hunting Estate La Mandria

Royal House, in the Turin State Archives and Royal Hunting Reserves in Piedmont were also consulted.

Results were presented at the National Conference on the Conservation of Felidae in Italy in 2008 (GAVAGNIN *et al.*, 2010). We obtained a distribution map that included western Ligurian valleys of Imperia and Savona provinces, up to the Alps-Apennine limit and the Cuneo province, where the presence concerned the medium-lower part of the valleys, not affected by a consistent and lasting snow cover.

Naturalized specimens coming from this geographical area are often accompanied by a fair set of indirect (even if not conspicuous) information, such as old photographs and newspaper clippings and oral testimonies, including also a literary quotation (the famous writer Italo Calvino described a wildcat in his novel “Il Barone Rampante”, set in the western Liguria woods).

An area of past presence was found in the residual woods of the Torinese plain and the low valleys, thus creating a belt around Royal Hunting Reserve of “La Mandria”. These finds date from the late 1800s to the early 1900s (Fig. 1).

Before 1971, the European wildcat was included in the list of “harmful animals”, that contained all carnivores and birds of prey. The animal was hunted also for the fur, which had a small trade and was sought after by collectors (Fig. 2). Locally, at least in western Liguria valleys, food consumption was also reported, an habit described even in other areas of Europe, such as France and Spain.

The European wildcat capture, when its coat had to be kept intact for commercialization or naturalization, did not take place by a traditional hunt, but with stalking and use of traps to avoid damaging the fur. It was a specialized hunting game. Baits and poisoned morsels were of little use, as the felid eating habit is the active search for live prey. This factor has largely contributed to the loss of knowledge on the carnivore, even in the hunting world, leading to a scarce information on its presence.

We can find information on the animal by identifying people who managed a market for the sale of the skin or sold specimens to collectors. Despite wildcat was considered “harmful”, no capture rewards were paid. The list of the historical specimens that were found is shown in Tab. 1. It has been double-checked and updated, the catalog numbers and sources have been verified and the Regional Museum of Natural Sciences of Turin collection has been reviewed for this purpose.

Based on the specimens provenance, it is possible to state the following:

The past presence of a western sub-area, including the western Piedmont (provinces of Cuneo and Turin). The information about Turin comes from

Fig. 2 - Ligurian hunter (Imperia province) with european wilcats and foxes for coat commercialization

the area located between the plain and the lower Lanzo valley, where the edges of the Po forest cover and surroundings have been longer preserved, kept as a Savoyard Hunting Reserve;

no specimens were reported from the plain woods between Turin and Cuneo (Bosco del Merlino, Caramagna Piemonte), from which there were only bibliographic reports;

no specimens resulted from the Ossola area, despite some bibliographic information was referred to;

The Ligurian side is confirmed as Ragni described it, and in the Savona area it reaches Cadibona. There are no examples or probative historical information coming from the Levant of the Liguria region.

The Imperia sector provides most information, dating back to the 19th century and more recent; it is very likely that the greater isolation in the geographical area of the Ligurian Alps and the southern mountains, favored the carnivore conservation.

Specimens and news from the Savona area are quite limited, as it was difficult to find memories and tales among elderly hunters. Finds from that area, namely the skins and skeletal parts that Ragni had examined at the Giacomo Doria Museum, date back to the early decades of the 1900s; we examined only

Tab. 1 - Specimens List

SAMPLE TYPE	ORIGIN	COLLOCATION	REGION-PROVINCE	CATALOG NUMBER
1 - Naturalized specimen	Valdieri, 1911 Gesso Valley	Natural Sciences Museum Turin	Piedmont- Cuneo	N. 2218 CG 1
2 - Naturalized specimen	Valdieri Gesso Valley	Natural History Museum Milan	Piedmont - Cuneo	N. MSNM MA 3676
3 - Naturalized specimen	South Western Maritime Alps, 1932	National Mountain Museum "Duca degli Abruzzi" Turin	Piedmont - Cuneo	N. 124
4 - Naturalized specimen	"Maritime Alps"	National. Mountain Museum "Duca degli Abruzzi" Turin	Piedmont - Cuneo	N. 124 A
5 - Naturalized specimen	Ormea, Tanaro Valley	Private collection Cuneo (Naturalized specimen List Cuneo Province Bureau)	Piedmont - Cuneo	Private collection - naturalized by Angelo Giuliano, Borgo S. Dalmazzo
6 - Unprepared skin	Cuneo Province Locality/year not specified	Natural Sciences Museum Turin	Piedmont - Cuneo	N. 14/306 CG 1
7 - Skin + skeletal parts Only in catalog	Valdellatorre, 1898 Val Casternone (Lanzo Valley)	Natural Sciences Museum Turin	Piedmont - Turin	N. 1533 CG skin + N. 4072 CG skeletal parts
8 - Naturalized specimen	Royal Hunting Estate La Mandria	Estate La Mandria Royal Parks Protected Areas	Piedmont - Turin	Royal Apartments
9 - Naturalized specimen	Venaria Reale, Year not specified	Private school collection Istituto Scolastico S.Giuseppe Turin	Piedmont - Turin	Late 19th century
10 - Naturalized specimen	Year not specified "Torinese"	Wild fauna collection Italian Hunting Federation Turin	Piedmont - Turin	Italian Hunting Federation – Turin 21, Mantova Street
11 - Naturalized specimen	La Mandria (TO) Year not specified	Natural Sciences Museum Turin	Piedmont - Turin	N. 1678 CG
12 - Naturalized specimen	Near La Mandria, late 19th century	Institute and Museum of Ethnography and Natural Sciences Missioni della Consolata	Piedmont - Turin	-----
13 - Skin + skeletal parts	Calizzano (SV) 18/1/1914 (Hunter Agostino Vacca)	G.Doria, Natural History Museum. Genova	Liguria - Savona	N. 10516 skull + 10515 skin
14 - Skull	Rocca Carpanea (Carpe, SV) 18/4/1983 (Hunter Agostino Vacca)	G.Doria, Natural History Museum Genova	Liguria - Savona	N. 47888 SKULL (Ragni 1986 Cranial Index)
15 - Naturalized specimen	Cadibona, year 1960	Taxidermist Ugo Sapetti (Contrada S. Bernardino, Ceva). (Naturalized specimen List Savona Province Bureau)	Liguria - Savona	-----
16 - Skin + skeletal parts	Bric Cornnarea, Ligurian Alps (IM), 26-1-1915 (Hunter Agaccio)	G.Doria, Natural History Museum. Genova	Liguria - Imperia	N. 2333 skull + N. 2332 skin (Ragni, Cranial Index 1986)
17 - Naturalized specimen	Tavole (IM) December 1972 (Hunter Mario Vassallo)	G.Doria, Natural History Museum. Genova	Liguria - Imperia	N. 47531
18 - Naturalized specimen	Agaggio Argentina Valley (Hunter Antonio Oliva - years 1930-40)	Voghera Natural History Museum, Coming from Giribaldi Collection, Bordighera	Liguria - Imperia	N. V870 Naturalized by Michelangelo Giuliano (Borgo S. Dalmazzo - Milano)
19 - Naturalized specimen	S. Bernardo Bosco di Rezzo, Rezzo (IM)	At private home, not reported Imperia	Liguria - Imperia	Reviewed thanks to intermediaries
21 – Naturalized specimen	Glori, Molini di Triora Argentina Valley	At private home not reported Arma di Taggia	Liguria - Imperia	Reviewed thanks to intermediaries
22 – Naturalized specimen	Volpiaira, Arroscia Valley	At private home not reported Pornassio	Liguria - Imperia	Reviewed thanks to intermediaries

23 – Skin	Argentina Valley Locality non specified	Naturalized specimen List Imperia Province Bureau)	Liguria - Imperia	Imperia Province Hunting and Fishing Bureau
24 - Naturalized specimen	Bosco di Rezzo, Rezzo (IM)	Naturalized specimen List Savona Province Bureau)	Liguria - Imperia	Private collection hunter Giardini Ubaldo Alassio (SV)
25 – Skin	Locality not specified	Regional Natural Sciences Museum. St Pierre	Aosta Valley	N. M7211 (Regional Natural Sciences Museum)
26 – Skin	Locality not specified	Regional Natural Sciences Museum St Pierre	Aosta Valley	N. M7411 (Società de la Flore Valdotaine)

a single specimen that shows a more recent date.

Most likely wildcats were preserved at the Natural History Museum of Savona (MINGOZZI *et al.*, 1988), whose collections were unfortunately lost in a bombing attack during 1943; only few finds of birds remain, and the incomplete registers do not allow to verify the data.

At the Provincial Administration there are four complaints of ownership by private individuals, but only one of them could be verified.

Several quotations from zoologists (Ghigi, Vigna Taglianti, Balletto), historical-ethnographic descriptions (Casalis, Chabrol de Volvic, Diana), and also stories and statements by hunters concern the Imperia- Savona areas. From Monregalese, Cuneo province, there are testimonies from hunters and tanners who had prepared leathers but there are not objective specimens.

Gamekeepers registers in La Mandria Royal Reserve, near Turin, show that wildcats were caught and apparently distinguished from feral cats (PASSERIN D'ENTREVES, 2000).

The two leathers from Valle d'Aosta are a separate mention: they have a relatively recent dating and their real origin is doubtful. There are no other news or reports of catches.

THE FRAGMENTATION OF NORTHERN SUB-AREAS: HABITAT LOSS IN HISTORICAL TIMES?

The European wildcat is a carnivore associated to forest habitats and this ecological preference usually influences the probability of presence in a specific area.

Highly disjointed areas can be found in several countries in Europe, and for this reason the conservation status of European wildcat is not homogeneous and in some areas it is classified as NT "Near Threatened".

French distribution has the greatest interest for N-W Italy, as it describes a consolidated presence in central-northern regions (Alsace, Lorraine), in continuity with the populations of Germany and

Belgium; a cluster in progressive expansion towards south on the eastern side of the country, near the Alps and a further area of presence very separate and distant, located in the Pyrenees, currently also expanding towards the Southwest.

The Northern Italian distribution shows a similar fragmentation model.

Cagnolaro (CAGNOLARO *et al.*, 1976) provides a detailed distribution framework for the period prior to the achievement of full protection. In years 1968-1972, a still significant presence is described in western Liguria and southwestern Piedmont (Cuneo province), and more remote data are found for the Turin area. BALLETO (1977) provides further details for Western Ligurian provinces.

CAGNOLARO *et al.*, (1976) carried out a national survey distributing specific questionnaires accompanied by a descriptive card of the wildcat and its identifying characteristics. The widespread diffusion of the questionnaires was guaranteed by the National Forestry Corps Stations, Provincial Administrations and hunting associations. Doubtful results were discussed and furtherly investigated; in some areas sightings were eventually classified as feral cats.

CAGNOLARO *et al.*, (1976) highlighted "the European wildcat disappearance in almost the entire Alpine arc, an absence dating back to over a century, for many areas even more, and supported by very little historical information". They also reported the complete data lack from the Emilian Apennines.

The distribution model is the same classically described by Ragni (RAGNI *et al.* 1993) and confirmed for this contribution purposes: there are not specimens from central Po area in museum collections and there is no historical and bibliographic information relating to this felid in the naturalistic works and historical-naturalistic publications referring central northern Italy.

What possible explanation can we give?

Productive transformation of the Po Valley has been a remote process over the centuries that progressively involved profound changes in the natural environment. Starting the 15th century, after

the demographic crisis caused by the plague, a period of reorganization of the countryside started, driven by the emerging of new urban and rural classes; at that time small properties, canals, canals dug and livestock farms began to develop. In the following centuries, this process became more and more evident, with the progressive concentration of small properties in larger agricultural estates. Plain woods disappeared from the Po area, and a forest cover remained only in the valleys; this phenomenon caused an evident fragmentation in many animal communities. BOGLIANI (2014) provided a naturalistic description of the environmental change in the central Po area over the centuries. The progressive forest cover elimination in the Po plains led to the gradual disappearance of the theriofauna inhabiting this horizon, and the replacement with species linked to open environments, such as the hare, and to ecotonal zones, such as roe deer. Some species of mammals - ungulates as deer, wild boar, roe deer and carnivores such as the wolf - managed to survive longer until the 18th century, thanks to their greater ecological plasticity, while mammals more specifically dependent to the forest habitat were among the first to succumb.

The European wildcat is a forest carnivore, not adapted to a live in a particularly open environment. Because of its ecological needs and the fact that it suffers from a long lasting snow cover, he has not been able to occupy, if not in a limited way, more mountainous areas.

Low alpine valleys may have constituted refuge areas, but such areas are not sufficient to preserve viable populations. A report by Cornalia (Fauna d'Italia, 1870) reveals that a specimen dated 1868 from the Maccagno Mountains, near Lake Maggiore, would have been kept at the Natural History Museum in Milan. However, there are no documented signs of this specimen, as confirmed also by a recent check. Part of the old collections and registers was lost after the damage suffered by the Museum during World War II. The relentless hunting exercised against carnivores is added to the habitat loss. BOGLIANI (2014) recalls that in the Ticino valley predators have been object of control actions for centuries and that the territory not strictly dedicated to agriculture was occupied by noble hunting reserves, later replaced by the private reserves of large industrial and land properties, whose guardsmen exercised a real persecution towards the species considered harmful.

TWO RECENT CASES SUGGEST THAT THE NW POPULATION IS NOT EXTINCT

In March 2017 on the Imperia side of Ligurian Alps, hikers reported the death of two dogs due to alleged poisoning. The area is located on the mountain ridge on the border between the Nervia Valley and the French Roya Valley. In order to identify the presence of poisoned morsels and dead

Fig. 3 - Ligurian Alps specimen necropsy May, 25 2017

animals, an inspection of the Anti-poison Dog Operative Unit by Carabinieri Forestali of Cuneo was urged. A first check on March 23th carried out with molecular dogs allowed the find of three dead foxes and morsels consisting of chicken wings. A second excursion on the same path was conducted on April 8th, and other morsels and a specimen of felid, not present before, were identified (Fig. 4).

The cat-specimen has been taken over by the Forestry Police of the competent station, and frozen to be stored. On April 13th a first examination of the carcass has been performed, keeping it frozen in order to avoid further decomposition processes. Evident diagnostic characteristics of *silvestris*

resulted: Caudal drawing; the distal part of the tail has four black rings (the fourth is less pronounced) not connected to each other; scapular drawing and occipito-cervical drawing are present. The basic color of the coat is compatible with that of an European wildcat; remarkably, a single dorsal band (not a particularly defined one) ends at the base of the tail.

On May 25th the necropsy has been performed at the Giacomo Doria Museum in Genoa (Fig. 3). The specimen has been evaluated according to the dorsal norm, the only one possible due to bad conditions of cat body.

The information framework achieved is detailed in table below.

Tab. 2 - Ligurian Alps Cat

Table 2	Ligurian Alps specimen	
April 8 2017	Ligurian Alps - Gola del Corvo Passo Muratone (Pigna IM)	Anti-poison Dog Operative Unit Carabinieri Forestali Cuneo
Preliminary examination Aprile 11 2017 Carabinieri Forestali Station (Rocchetta Nervina IM)		Patrizia Gavagnin
Necropsy May 25 2017 G.Doria, Natural History Museum Genova		Patrizia Gavagnin Walter Mignone Zooprophyllactic Institute Enrico Borgo Giuliano Doria G.Doria, Natural History Museum Sebastiano Salvidio DISTAV UNIGE
<i>Felis silvestris</i> ssp. Sex: M Presumable age: 2-3 years Weight (g): 3208	Total lenght TL (mm) : 835 Tail lenght (mm): 290 Head-trunk lenght (mm): 545 Hind leg lenght (mm): 116 Auricle height (mm): 57 Intestinal lenght cardias-anus (mm): 1435	Ectoparasites : Diptera Endoparasites : Ascaridae (stomach) Skeletal musculature: good state Coat and skin: advanced state of decomposition Good condition of plantar pads and nails
Stomach: <i>Apodemus</i> sp. + Bird tissues (chicken)	Toxicology outcomes: organochlorine pesticides	Zooprophyllactic Institute Piedmont-Ligury-Aosta Valley
Stomach: <i>Apodemus</i> sp		DISTAV UNIGE Sebastiano Salvidio Patrizia Gavagnin
Intestinal Index (intestinal lenght cardias-anus / Head Body Lenght) mm = 1435 /545 = 2,63	Schauenberg, 1977 <3,15 range <i>silvestris</i> >3,15 range <i>catus</i>	Patrizia Gavagnin Enrico Borgo
Osteometric findings July 11 2017. G.Doria, Natural History Museum Genoa	Skull total lenght (mm) = 99,3 Neurocranium capacity (cc) = 36,8	Patrizia Gavagnin Enrico Borgo
Cranial Index: 99,3/36,8 = 2,70	Schauenberg, 1969 <2,75 range <i>silvestris</i> >2,75 range <i>catus</i>	
Foramen occipitalis area= 132,75; Zygomatic apophysis distance: Sn <1,4 , Dx 1,4	Jaw stability test = <i>silvestris</i> Nose-frontal suture = <i>silvestris</i>	
Prot. 26623/2017 – Molecular markers Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research - ISPRA		Wild component very close to that of the Central European wild population and domestic component <i>F.s. silvestris</i> x <i>F.s.catus</i>
10DG122- Genetic markers for forensic use Zooprophyllactic Institute Piedmont- Ligury-Aosta Valley	Mitochondrial fraction analysis : examination polymorphisms in mitochondrial genes sequences : ND5, ND6, cytb. Primer: F1CR4; F2BR3; F3BR2A; F4BR1C x 13 polymorphic sites.	In female parental line it is found <i>Felis s. catus</i>

Fig. 4 - Dead cat found April, 8 2017 Ligurian Alps, Passo Muratone (IM)

In the same period, many kilometers away, another cat has been identified. It is an animal that died of collision with a vehicle found in a lay-by of the A26 motorway in Rossiglione, near Turchino Pass on Ligurian-Piedmontese Apennines. The carcass has been collected by a volunteer and delivered it to the Siena University. A portion of the tongue was sent to ISPRA Genetics Laboratory for biomolecular analysis, then the animal was given to the Maremma Natural History Museum where the necropsy has been performed on 31st July 2017 by Bernardino Ragni, Andrea Sforzi and Emiliano Mori.

The relevant information is shown in the table below.

Tab. 3 - Turchino Cat

Table 3	Chat Passo del Turchino	
11 april 2017	Rossiglione (GE) Piazzola di sosta Autostrada A26	Walter Marini
Preliminary examination: april 2017	Research Unit f Behavioural Ecology, Ethology and Wildlife Management, Department of Life Sciences, University of Siena. Via P.A. Mattioli, 4 53100 Siena.	Emiliano Mori
Removal of tissue flap (tongue) for biomolecular marker research.	ISPRA	Exemplary <i>F.s. silvestris</i> x <i>F.s.catus</i> (Edoardo Velli- ISPRA)
Necropsy – 31 july 2017	Maremma Natural History Museum (GR)	Bernardino Ragni Andrea Sforzi Emiliano Mori
<i>Felis silvestris</i> ssp. Sex: F Presumable age: 3 years	Occipito cervical design = <i>silvestris</i> Scapular drawing = <i>silvestris</i> Dorsal drawing = <i>silvestris</i> Caudal drawing = <i>silvestris</i> Rinario = <i>silvestris</i> Gulare = <i>silvestris</i> Pinnae = <i>silvestris</i> Lateral drawing Sn = <i>catus</i> Lateral drawing Dx = <i>catus</i>	Pregnant 2 phoetuses 40 gg (male, female), Everted nipples (previous pregnancies) Subcutaneous fat (traces) Stomach: 3 <i>Apodemus</i> sp. Pattern of the coat reveals dominance of eumelanin, a character related with <i>catus</i> .
Intestinal Index = 3,20	Schauenberg, 1977 <3,15 range <i>silvestris</i> >3,15 range <i>catus</i>	

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In the framework of the historical findings related to the European wildcat distribution in the NW sub-area, the two specimens found in 2017 allow various food for thought. Both are adult individuals of about 2-3 years; in both cases the *silvestris* inheritance is evident, as most of the pelage markings suggest, that means that at least some truly wild specimens might be still present in the area. Hybridization with *catus* has been demonstrated, the variability loss due to introgression with domestic cat is one of the major risk factors for the European wildcat population in Europe. Remarkably, hybridization is a particularly critical factor for a very isolated, potentially relict, population, like the western one. In the male specimen from the Ligurian Alps the set of diagnostic characters is placed in the *silvestris* range, as referred to the coat-color system and Schauenberg's diagnostic indices, in particular Intestinal Index, which is robustly in the wild range. *Pinnae* show an almost imperceptible dark apex instead of a uniform ocher color and an equally almost imperceptible outline of hair. This characteristic could perhaps be part of the geographical variability found in other sub-populations; there is currently not enough information to prove it. This cat is the first carcass found after a long time.

Genetic *status* of the western population is not known because we can rely only on (often quite old)

naturalized specimens, for which genetic analyses can be a challenge. The existence of different allelic frequencies can be assumed in this population, as it was found in other Italian subpopulations (MATTUCCI *et al.*, 2013). The isolation of the North-Western population dates back to past centuries, probably following the historical disappearance of the species from the central Po areas. Information framework of the North-Western area in Liguria and Piedmont needs to be increased; also there's need to improve systems to describe the genetics of this population.

The control of possible hybridization events by promoting sterilizations of rural feline colonies and the limitation of the free-ranging behaviour of rural cats is very important for the European wildcat conservation.

The female from Turchino Pass has an intestinal index in the *catus* range (3.20), but this value is very close to the wild / domestic discriminating limit, which is 3.15. The dominance of eumelanin in the coat is evident, despite the markings typical of the wild phenotype is clearly visible. This specimen comes from an area outside the known historical distribution model.

There is no past information about European wildcats from Central Levante Liguria and Piedmontese Apennines, as no naturalized specimens come from these geographical areas. The absence of wildcats from the Ligurian Levant was discussed by RAGNI *et al.* (1993); CAGNOLARO *et al.*, (1976) also reported of a dubious specimen coming from the Aveto area, concluding that that specimen was ultimately considered not wild. In a survey conducted in 2008 (GAVAGNIN *et al.*, 2010) and for the current data update, Cagnolaro's notes were reviewed, a former taxidermist of the G. Doria Museum was contacted and the documentation about the samples kept at the La Spezia Museum was reviewed, confirming absence of any objective data.

Lack of information and the absence of stuffed specimens does not demonstrate the real absolute absence of the wildcat from the NW area during the past decades, when the carnivore hunting was allowed; the wildcat could be hunted as harmful without leaving a particular trace.

However, the European wildcat does not seem to be a known carnivore in the Levante area, among hunters. The specimen preserved in the Federaccia

wildlife fauna collection in Genoa is classified as a "wild cat" but, according with the examination carried out in 2013, it is in fact by no means *silvestris*.

In recent years, through amateurs and photographers some camera-trapping images have been produced, highlighting traits of probable wild ancestry in the coat and in the tail of the specimens. The geographical location of these shots describes a probable north-Apennine expansion close to the Liguria borders.

Camera-trapping shots from the Parma Apennines, near Monchio delle Corti, are also very interesting and open new scenarios that deserve to be studied.

Some interest have also other videos about a cat female, clearly *silvestris*, with cubs in a beech and chestnut trees mixed forest, reported for the Trebbia valley.

In order to increase the conservation status of the European wildcat in Italy, it is important to update and deepen the distribution framework, particularly to clarify the existence of the North-Western population that, due to the long-lasting geographic isolation, can provide interesting bio molecular information.

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POPULATION SURVEY OF THE EUROPEAN WILDCAT IN THE NATURAL BIOGENETIC RESERVE OF THE FORESTE CASENTINESI NATIONAL PARK (NORTHERN APPENINES)

INDAGINE GENETICA SULLA POPOLAZIONE DI GATTO SELVATICO EUROPEO NELLE RISERVE NATURALI BIOGENETICHE CASENTINESI (APPENNINO SETTENTRIONALE)

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Abstract. The European wildcat (*Felis silvestris silvestris*) is one of the most elusive carnivores in the Italian peninsula. It is mainly threatened by habitat fragmentation and especially hybridization with the domestic cat. Effective actions for its conservation are strictly related to a sound knowledge of its population parameters and genetic status. In this study we present a systematic monitoring that provided an informative framework on the wildcat distribution in the Biogenetic Casentinesi Reserves inside the Foreste Casentinesi National Park, the northernmost border of its ascertained peninsular range. We applied an extensive camera-trapping protocol based on a systematic grid in order to approach the same capture probability for all the individuals in the study area. Furthermore, we used valerian-baited hair-traps to verify the reliability of this technique in attracting wildcat individuals, lead them to rub against the hair-traps in order to catch biological samples for genetic analyses. We collected a total of 99 wildcat pictures identifying a minimum number of 13 individuals (capture density 6.6/10 km²) and detecting the presence of at least one domestic cat and a putative hybrid in the study area. The use of lures proved to be effective in increasing the capture probability of the target species in camera-trapping based studies ($p < 0,05$). However, only some individuals showed a clear rubbing behavior and left hair in the hair-traps, supporting the hypothesis of a different individual genetically-mediated reaction. Genetic survey identified seven individuals (four males and three females), all belonging to *Felis silvestris silvestris* population. Five of them showed putative introgressed mitochondrial haplotypes.

Riassunto. Il gatto selvatico europeo (*Felis silvestris silvestris*) è uno dei carnivori più elusivi della penisola italiana. È principalmente minacciato dalla frammentazione dell'habitat e soprattutto dall'ibridazione con il gatto domestico. Le azioni efficaci per la sua conservazione sono strettamente legate a una solida conoscenza dei parametri di popolazione e del suo status genetico. Questo studio presenta i risultati di un monitoraggio sistematico finalizzato a definire la distribuzione del gatto selvatico nelle Riserve Biogenetiche Casentinesi, all'interno del Parco Nazionale delle Foreste Casentinesi, confine più settentrionale del suo accertato areale peninsulare. Abbiamo applicato un ampio protocollo di fototrappolaggio basato su una griglia sistematica, per avvicinarci alla stessa probabilità di cattura per tutti gli individui nell'area di studio. Inoltre abbiamo utilizzato trappole per peli con estratto di valeriana, per verificare l'affidabilità di questa tecnica nell'attrarre individui di gatto selvatico, inducendoli a strofinarsi contro le trappole, al fine di catturare campioni biologici per analisi genetiche. Abbiamo raccolto in totale 99 immagini di gatto selvatico, identificando un numero minimo di 13 individui (densità di cattura 6,6/10 km²) e rilevando la presenza di almeno un gatto domestico e un ibrido putativo nell'area di studio. L'uso di esche si è dimostrato efficace nell'aumentare la probabilità di cattura delle specie bersaglio in studi basati su fototrappole ($p < 0,05$). Tuttavia, solo alcuni individui hanno mostrato un evidente comportamento di sfregamento e hanno lasciato i peli nelle trappole, supportando l'ipotesi di una diversa reazione geneticamente mediata dell'individuo. L'indagine genetica ha identificato sette esemplari (quattro maschi e tre femmine), tutti appartenenti alla popolazione di *Felis silvestris silvestris*. Cinque di loro mostravano aplotipi mitocondriali introgressi.

INTRODUCTION

The wildcat *Felis silvestris* is a polytypic species comprising six morphologically, ecologically and genetically differentiated subspecies that inhabit Palearctic and Afrotropical Regions (see DRISCOLL *et al.* 2007 for details). In Europe, three of them coexist: the European wildcat (*Felis silvestris silvestris* Schreber,

1777), whose distribution is scattered throughout the continent; the African wildcat (*Felis silvestris libyca*, Forster 1780), living in the Mediterranean islands of Corsica and Sardinia, (RANDI & RAGNI 1991, DRISCOLL *et al.* 2007); and the domestic descendant of *libyca* North African cats, the domestic cat (*Felis silvestris catus*) that spread throughout the entire continent, as well as in the entire World.

The species' distribution range Italy covers the entire Apennines (RAGNI *et al.* 1994), including Sicily (ANILE *et al.* 2012a; 2014), with confirmed consistent populations in the first sectors of northern Apennines (Foreste Casentinesi National Park, VELLI *et al.* 2015).

Results of a national survey carried out by Cagnolaro (1976) in the '70 using indirect methods, compared with more recent findings (AGOSTINI *et al.* 2010; TEDALDI 2012; RAGNI *et al.* 2014; VELLI *et al.* 2015) suggest a northwards wildcat expansion, likely promoted by suitable forested habitat corridors in protected areas along the Apennine ridge (SANTOLINI *et al.* 2010). The European wildcat population in north-eastern Italy is genetically connected with the Dinaric-Balkan population (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2013).

Recent observations (GAVAGNIN *et al.* 2018) suggest the persistence of a north-western population in connection with a French source.

The European wildcat is a 'strictly protected' species included in Annex IV of the European Habitats Directive (92/43/CEE). It is included in Annex II of the Bern Convention, and it is classified as Least Concern by the IUCN (DRISCOLL & NOWELL, 2010) and near threatened in the Italian Red List (RONDININI *et al.* 2013). Main threats are the loss of suitable habitat (KLAR *et al.* 2009; 2012), human-caused mortality, in particular road kills (NOWELL & JACKSON 1996; LÜPS *et al.* 2002; SCHULENBERG 2005; KRONE *et al.* 2008) overgrazing by large game species (LOZANO *et al.* 2007) and especially hybridization with the domestic cat (*Felis silvestris catus*; RANDI 2008; OLIVEIRA *et al.* 2008).

Reliable estimates of population abundance and trends are the key baseline data to assess the impact of threatening factors needed to outline sound conservation guidelines (see Council of Europe 1993). This is particularly relevant when dealing with expanding populations, in which the risk of hybridization increases (cfr. wolf, GALAVERNI *et al.* 2017).

The lower portion of the northern Apennines has been investigated in the last 10 years by a few studies (AGOSTINI *et al.* 2010; TEDALDI 2012; RAGNI *et al.* 2014; VELLI *et al.* 2015) using different techniques, however an integrated survey of the Natural Reserves is still lacking.

In this work, we present the results of a non-invasive European wildcat survey carried out in the fully protected area of the Natural Biogenetic Reserve in the Foreste Casentinesi National Park aiming at investigating the presence of the subspecies in the northernmost area of its ascertained Apennine distribution by integrating hair-trapping, camera-trapping and scat collection methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out between July 2014 and July 2015. We selected a 20 km² wide area in the fully protected Sasso Fratino Natural Reserve (Fig. 1), one of the most biodiverse spots in the Foreste Casentinesi National Park. Following the monitoring protocol reported in Velli *et al.* (2015) and the information of previous surveys (2009-2013; RAGNI *et al.* 2014) we applied a 1 x 1 km grid over the sampling area and systematically placed 21 raw pine sticks (60 x 4 x 4 cm), trying to uniformly cover the grid and placing, when possible, at least a lure in each square (HUPE & SIMON 2007; KÉRY *et al.* 2011, HARTMANN *et al.* 2013; STEYER *et al.* 2013; VELLI *et al.* 2015). Each picket was identified with a code, geo-localized and drenched with valerian (*Valeriana officinalis*) hydroalcoholic tincture (70%); in addition, longitudinally at the top of it, we made a hole of about 2 x 7 cm, and two smaller ones transversely on each side and filled them with valerian root powder to obtain a stronger, uniform and longer-lasting effect even during rainy days. Valerian has been proved to induce not only a significant investigative response from wildcats, but also to promote a strong rubbing behaviour (MONTERROSO *et al.* 2011) and has been used in several studies on wildcat (KÉRY *et al.* 2011, STEYER *et al.* 2013; VELLI *et al.* 2015). In order to catch as many hairs as possible, we scratched the surface of the wood applying a strip of Velcro tape. We equipped 17 of 21 sampling stations with a camera-trap. Cameras were tied to trees at about 2 m to the lured pickets and set on both video and photo modes, trying to get high quality pictures as well as behavioural informative videos. Each camera was equipped with a 4-GB SDHC card and was powered by four rechargeable AA batteries. Sampling stations were placed along the trails used for collecting faecal samples. We performed two different sampling sessions: the first one from 8th of July to 23th of October 2014 and the second one from 28th April to 29th July 2015. Sampling stations were visited each 7-10 days. During each session we replaced SD cards and batteries of camera-traps, collected possible hair samples and scratched the wood stick with an iron brush to remove any residual hairs, preventing contaminations in the following session. Finally, a new Velcro tape was applied. Hair samples were stored in silica envelopes while scats were conserved in 96% ethanol and frozen as soon as possible. Sample collection was performed using disposable gloves and flaming the forceps used to collect hair. A preliminary subspecies and individual identification were obtained by analysing coat colour patterns and body proportions of the animals

Fig. 1: boundaries of the Sasso Fratino Integral Reserve in which was carried out the survey

(FRENCH *et al.* 1988; RAGNI & POSSENTI 1996). The presence and shape of any additional sign on the pelage (ANILE *et al.* 2012a), behaviour and body proportions were further considered. Each collected video of *Felis sp.* was analysed by three different independent operators. In order to investigate the reactions toward the bait we compiled an ethogram (WELLS & EGLI 2004; ELLIS & WELLS 2010) in which we listed seven different definitions that could cover the range of behaviours displayed: indifference (I), curiosity (C), facial marking (FM), strong interaction and rubbing (SI), only spray marking (SM), diffidence (D) and fear (F). If during the same shooting different behaviours occurred, we considered only the stronger one (i.e., if a cat displayed curiosity followed by facial marking and strong interaction, we considered only the “strong interaction” event) except for the urinary marking that could follow (or not) preview behaviours.

Genetic Analyses

DNA extraction was performed using the Blood&Tissue Kit® (Quiagen) protocol following manufacturer instructions. Furthermore, hair samples were processed adding to the digestion mix 20µl of dithiothreitol required to efficiently degrade the keratin skeleton of hairs (MCNEVIN *et al.* 2005).

All samples were preliminarily analysed at the mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) in order to discard samples belonging to non-target species using a 719 bp fragment of the mtDNA control-region (hence CR; sites 16236 - 16955) and primers CHF3 (5'-CTC CCT AAG ACT TCA AGG AAG-3'; Freeman *et al.* 2001) and CHR3 (5'-CCT GAA GTA AGA ACC AGA TG-3'; Tiedemann *et al.* 1996).

All samples belonging to the target species were then amplified at 10 autosomal microsatellite (STR) loci FCA23, FCA26, FCA43, FCA58, FCA77, FCA88, FCA96, FCA126, FCA132, FCA149 (MENOTTI-RAYMOND & O'BRIEN 1995, MENOTTI-RAYMOND *et al.* 1997) and one microsatellite locus SMCY-7 STR on Y chromosome showing a polymorphism that seems to be fixed with different alleles in the two subspecies studied (LUO *et al.* 2007, NUSSBERGER *et al.* 2013). PCR conditions follow Velli *et al.* 2015 procedures. PCR products were analysed in an ABI 3130 XL (Applied Biosystems) automated sequencer, and allele sizes were determined with GENEMAPPER 4.0 (Applied Biosystems). We used a multiple tube approach with a minimum number of four replicates per sample in order to assess the rate of allelic dropout (ADO) and false alleles (FA) (TABERLET *et al.* 1999) The reliability value for each sample was assessed with RELIOTYPE (MILLER *et*

al. 2002). Using the match function in GENALEX 6.501 (PEAKALL & SMOUSE 2012) we detected individuals sampled more than once. Discrimination between the wild and the domestic subspecies was performed in STRUCTURE 2.3.4 (PRITCHARD *et al.* 2000), setting the genetic clusters $K=2$ (OLIVEIRA *et al.* 2008; O'BRIEN *et al.* 2009). Analyses were based on 400 000 MCMC steps after discarding the first 40 000 steps as burn-in, under the admixture model with correlated allele frequencies (HERTWIG *et al.* 2009; ECKERT *et al.* 2010). The power of markers to identify each unique genotype was evaluated calculating the probability of identity values (PID and PIDSibs; MILLS *et al.* 2000; WAITS *et al.* 2001) in GENALEX 6.501 (PEAKALL & SMOUSE 2012). We used a panel of 77 free-living or house domestic cats, 235 putative European wildcats and 17 previously described *silvestris* x *catus* hybrids, collected in Italy from 2003 to 2010 and already analysed at 35 loci (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2013), as reference data set for calculation of PIDSibs (the probability of identity among siblings), chromosome Y subspecies assessment, mitochondrial and STRUCTURE analysis. Assignment threshold was set to $q_i > 0.8$ for subspecies identification (PIERPAOLI *et al.* 2003; OLIVEIRA *et al.* 2008). We sequenced 877 bp (including the primers) of the mtDNA NADH dehydrogenase subunit 5 (hence ND5; nucleotides 13131 - 14007 mapped on the mitochondrial genome of the domestic cat; NCBI Reference Sequence NC001700), which, according to Driscoll

et al. (2011), contains seven diagnostic SNPs discriminating European wildcats (*Felis silvestris silvestris*) and domestic cats (*Felis silvestris catus*). Sequences were amplified using PCR primers F2B (5'-TGCCGCCCTACAAGCAAT-3') and R3B (5'-TAAGAGACGTTTAAATGGAGTTGAT-3') (DRISCOLL *et al.* 2011) and aligned using SEQSCAPE software v2.5 (Life Technologies). The mtDNA genome of the domestic cat (NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_001700), trimmed at the above-mentioned positions, was used as the reference sequence. In order to assign the samples to the correct subspecies lineage we analysed the ND5 sequences performing a median joining network using NETWORK 4.6 (Fluxus Technology Ltd).

RESULTS

Camera trapping

Camera-traps worked for a total of 3220 trap-nights. We obtained a total of 99 *Felis silvestris* captures (269 events) with a capture frequency of 3.07% (Tab. 1). Based on size and proportion of the body, behaviour and coat colour marking patterns (RAGNI & POSSENTI 1996), we identified 13 different individuals of *Felis silvestris silvestris*, and two individuals showing signs of possible hybridization (white paws and belly). Considering a study area of 20 km² we calculated a capture density of *Felis silvestris silvestris* of 6.6 individuals / 10 km² and a capture rate of 3.1/100 trap-nights.

Tab. 1: synoptic table resuming the genetic individual assignments using different genetic markers: microsatellites (STR genotype), mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) and Y-chromosome haplotype (Chr Y). Individuals with question marks are samples that did not yielded reliable individual nuclear genotype but returned different mitochondrial haplotype.

ID genotype	ID samples	ID trap station	STR genotype	mtDNA	Chr Y
1	2005 (hair) 2006 (hair) 2007 (hair)	11 11 11	<i>F. s. silvestris</i>	D-intr	<i>F. s. silvestris</i>
2	2014 (hair) 2015 (hair) 2016 (hair)	12 12 11	<i>F. s. silvestris</i>	W	<i>F. s. silvestris</i>
3	2004 (hair) 2008 (hair) 2020 (hair) 2023 (hair)	11 11 11 11	<i>F. s. silvestris</i>	D-intr	<i>F. s. silvestris</i>
4	1981 (scat)	Fosso delle Macine	<i>F. s. silvestris</i>	D-intr	-
5	1983 (scat)	Pian del Pero	<i>F. s. silvestris</i>	D-intr	-
6	1994 (hair)	13	<i>F. s. silvestris</i>	D-intr	<i>F. s. silvestris</i>
7	2000 (hair)	11	<i>F. s. silvestris</i>	W	-
8(?)	1829 (scat)	Pian del Pero	-	W	-
9(?)	1831 (scat)	Pozza del Cervo	-	D	-

Fig. 2 - histogram showing the proportion of different behaviours towards the lure among all sampled individuals. indifference (I), curiosity (C), facial marking (FM), strong interaction and rubbing (SI), only spray marking (SM), diffidence (D) and fear (F).

Activity patterns of wildcats in the study area were mainly nocturnal (more than 90% of capture between 9:00 pm and 5:00 am). In 20% of cases the individuals showed no interest (I) for the lures and a total of 69.09% individuals acted out the expected behaviour, leaving hair samples (SI) (Fig. 2). Two individuals didn't show any interest toward the lures, while nine scratched on the picket leaving hair-samples (FM or SI). To investigate the effectiveness of valerian tincture in increasing capture probability, we compared the capture mean rates for three sites used in both 2009-2013 (mean = 2.66 ± 1.76 , without lures) and 2014-2015 (mean = 29.57 ± 29.20 , with valerian scent lure) monitoring programs. Fisher's test confirmed a high significant ($p\text{-value} = 1.99 \times 10^{-7}$) influence of valerian lures in increasing capture probability, although this effect was likely not evenly distributed among wildcat individuals.

Genetic analyses

We collected 54 non-invasive samples (39 hair samples and 15 scats). Preliminary mitochondrial screening identified 11 samples belonging to non-target species that were discarded for subsequently analyses. Of the remaining 43 *Felis* samples, we successfully genotyped the 32.4% ($n = 14$), of which

the majority ($n = 12$) deriving from hair trapping. Ten autosomal loci yielded a value of $PID_{sib} = 0.0001$. Absence of samples presenting more than two alleles guaranteed that no contamination occurred among samples. We identified at least seven different individuals, all belonging to the *Felis s. silvestris* subspecies (Tab. 1). According to the chr-Y analyses, four of them were male, with a wildcat associated Y-haplotype. We calculated a capture density of 3.5 individuals / 10 km². Regarding the mitochondrial analyses of ND5 subunit, the samples fell into two main different haplogroups (W, D) that, according to the previous assignation of reference samples, correspond respectively to the wildcat haplogroup (W) and the domestic haplogroup (D). Combining the information derived from the three types of markers (STR, mtDNA and SMCY-STR) we were able to confirm as pure wildcats the individuals with concordant attribution through the different markers. We also detected five individuals with putative introgressed mitochondrial haplotypes (D-intr) as they were featured by a nuclear genotype attributed to the wildcat ($q_i > 0.8$) but a mtDNA haplotypes presenting all the domestic / *Felis s. lybica* cat polymorphisms. In six occasions (Tab. 2) we were able to associate the genotype to the putative phenotype captured by the camera-traps.

Tab. 2: table resuming the phenotype-genotype association integrating the information from camera trapping and non-invasive genetic survey

ID trap station	ID individual from camera trapping	ID genotype
2	A-B-F	
4	C-E	
7	G	5/8
8	G	5/8
9	N	
10		9
11	A-H-I-L-O	1/2/3/7
12		2
13		6
14	D	
15	L	4
16	M	

DISCUSSION

In this work we applied a multidisciplinary non-invasive methodology to monitor the presence of the European wildcat in the Natural Biogenetic Reserve of the Foreste Casentinesi National Park. Integrating camera trapping, scat survey and hair-trapping with valerian lures we were able to collect information about the minimum consistency of wildcat population, impact of free ranging domestic cats and possible presence of hybrids. We detected 13 different wildcat individuals through camera trapping with a capture rate of 3.1/100 night-traps and seven different wildcat genotypes from non-invasive genetic monitoring. Two putative hybrids were identified using camera traps. Although none genotype showed sign of recent hybridization, five individuals showed domestic mitochondrial signature. Capture density showed different values depending on the used technique: using camera-trapping we calculated 6.6 individuals / 10 km² that is almost two times the values coming from genetic monitoring of 3.5 individuals / 10 km². Capture densities were comparable with a similar study carried out in similar ecological conditions (4.5 individuals / 10 km² for camera trapping and 2.6 individuals / 10 km² for non-invasive genetic; Velli *et al.* 2015) and also capture rates (1.8/100 trap-nights, CAN *et al.* 2011; 2.3/100 trap-nights, KILSHAW & MACDONALD 2011; 2.9/100 trap-nights, ANILE *et al.* 2012b; 3.1/100 trap-nights, VELLI *et al.* 2015). Genotyping success rates (32.4%) was slightly lower but still comparable with previous works (36%, ANILE *et al.* 2014; 37.2%, VELLI *et al.* 2015). The use of an integrated monitoring tool allowed us to collect heterogeneous data by using single sampling

effort and to offset the weaknesses of each method. In particular, camera trapping is one of the most functional methods for monitoring several species (SILVEIRA *et al.* 2003) and in our study contributed to detect possible hybridization events that would have been left unveiled using only non-invasive genetics. However, it may suffer from overestimation errors, in particular in the abundance estimate reached with capture-recapture methods, especially in studies of elusive animals with few identification marks in low-density areas (FOSTER & HARMSSEN 2012). Non-invasive genetics monitoring, instead, provide a more accurate individual detection and a deeper insight on population ancestry, although it suffers from genotyping errors and low success rates. The application of integrated monitoring techniques allows to avoid the risk of an underestimation of the population due to the heterogeneity in the response to the bait. A total of 69.09 % of detected wildcat positively reacted to valerian lures. This result slightly differs from other similar application of this method. A study by Monterroso *et al.* (2011) highlights that only 11.5% of the wildcats identified showed an investigative behaviour towards the bait. While Velli *et al.* (2015) found that 20.6% of individuals reacted with the expected behaviour, leaving hair samples on the picket. A work by Anile *et al.* (2012b) in Sicily, found no reactions at all. Monterroso *et al.* (2011) also evidenced the greater attractive power of the lynx (*Lynx lynx*) urine. However, in order to avoid any interference in the spatial behaviour and in other ethological features of the target-species, we preferred not to use such intensive substance belonging to a species not present in the study area. The integration of non-invasive genetic sampling with the camera

trapping allows to successfully associate the genetic data with the picture of an individual.

Current results suggest the presence of a well established population in the study area, reinforcing the hypothesis of a northward expansion of the subspecies (RAGNI *et al.* 2014; VELLI *et al.* 2015). Nonetheless, the presence of putative hybrids, in a fully protected area such as the Sasso Fratino Natural Reserve arises concern about the long term conservation of the subspecies, often sharing the territory with its domestic counterpart, in a medium anthropized environment such as the northern Apennines. However, mitochondrial results should be taken with caution since domestic cats and their strictly related progenitors, the North African wildcats, *Felis s. lybica*, share most of the mitochondrial variation (DRISCOLL *et al.*

2007). Hence, the presence of putative domestic polymorphisms in European wildcat individuals might derive from haplotype sharing with ancient populations of *Felis s. lybica*. Further studies are currently underway.

In conclusion, in this study we improved the knowledge on the population dynamics of the European wildcat living in an expanding area such as the northern Apennines. We provided a preliminary insight on its genetic status by using an integrated protocol of different monitoring techniques. Since the European wildcat areal seems to keep advancing northward, future study aimed at ascertaining the presence/absence of the subspecies even in other areas of northern Apennines are, therefore, strongly recommended.

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EVALUATING HABITAT USE AND DETECTION PROBABILITY OF THE EUROPEAN WILDCAT (*FELIS SILVESTRIS*): A CAMERA TRAPPING STUDY IN SOUTHERN ITALY

VALUTAZIONE DI USO DELL'HABITAT E RILEVABILITÀ NEL GATTO SELVATICO EUROPEO (*FELIS SILVESTRIS*): UNO STUDIO DI FOTOTRAPPOLAGGIO IN SUD ITALIA

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Abstract. The European wildcat (*Felis silvestris*) is a medium-sized carnivore of conservation concern, considered nearly threatened in Italy. There were few studies about habitat ecology and distribution of this species in Italy in the early 2000s, especially in Southern regions. In an attempt to fill this gap of knowledge, we conducted a camera trapping study of *Felis silvestris* in the National Park of Cilento and Vallo di Diano (Campania region) during 2008-2010. Our aims were to evaluate the role of forests and shrublands in the habitat use pattern of the felid and produce information applicable to its conservation. Camera traps were deployed at 71 sampling sites in a 1020 km² study area. We obtained 61 photographic captures of *Felis silvestris* from 19 cameras, over a total of 5983 camera trapping nights. We fit a suite of competitive single-season occupancy models to wildcat detection/non-detection data to evaluate site use and detection probabilities. We estimated an average wildcat site use probability of 0.716 (0.231 SE), a value that was 2.7 higher than the naïve proportion of sites used (0.267), due to very low probability of detection (0.084 [0.052 SE]). Model selection analysis supported the view of *Felis silvestris* as a forest carnivore in Mediterranean regions, partially in contrast to some other studies. In our study, wildcat use probability increased in sites with higher forest cover proportions, irrespective of the forest type. Predicted detection probability largely increased in sites with repeated applications of scent lure. Results suggested the importance of maintaining residual forests in shrub-dominated landscapes for wildcat conservation. Moreover, we provided evidence that use of scent lures could improve the efficiency of wildcat camera trapping surveys, by increasing the wildcat detectability. This in turn reduces the uncertainty around parameter estimates and improve inference about distribution and habitat requirements of wildcat.

Riassunto. Il gatto selvatico europeo (*Felis silvestris*) è un mesocarnivoro considerato “quasi minacciato” in Italia. Studi sull'habitat e distribuzione di questo felide erano ancora limitati agli inizi del 2000. Tra il 2008 ed il 2010 abbiamo realizzato uno studio di fototrappolaggio nel Parco Nazionale del Cilento e Vallo di Diano (regione Campania) per valutare il ruolo degli habitat forestali e arbustivi nell'uso dell'habitat del gatto selvatico. Nel corso dello studio abbiamo attivato 71 siti di fototrappolaggio in un'area di 1020 km², ottenendo nel complesso 61 immagini del felide da 19 fototrappole. I dati di presenza acquisiti nei siti di campionamento sono stati utilizzati per costruire modelli di probabilità d'uso (occupancy models) valutando un set di ipotesi alternative. La probabilità media d'uso dei siti stimata dai modelli è 0.716 (0.231 ES), un valore 2.7 superiore alla proporzione osservata di siti utilizzati (0.267) dal gatto selvatico. La cospicua differenza tra dato osservato e stima è dipesa dalla bassa probabilità di cattura fotografica (0.084 [0.052 SE], per 7 giorni di rilevazione fotografica). La probabilità d'uso del gatto selvatico incrementa con l'incremento della estensione relativa delle foreste decidue miste. L'analisi di selezione dei modelli non supporta gli effetti della copertura di foreste d'alto fusto, arbustive e della densità ecotonale sulla probabilità d'uso. La probabilità di cattura fotografica stimata è risultata molto più alta nei siti in cui abbiamo rinnovato ripetutamente le esche olfattive. Differentemente da quanto emerso in alcuni ricerche europee il nostro studio supporta la visione del gatto selvatico come carnivoro primariamente forestale, anche in contesti mediterranei. I risultati suggeriscono inoltre l'importanza di preservare residue aree forestate in paesaggi dominati da vegetazione arbustiva. L'uso di attrattivi olfattivi può migliorare l'efficienza del fototrappolaggio del gatto selvatico, in termini di incremento di precisione delle stime dei parametri dei modelli di uso dell'habitat, associato all'incremento di rilevabilità.

INTRODUCTION

The European wildcat (*Felis silvestris*) is a medium-sized carnivore of conservation concern, listed in Annexes IV of the EU Habitat Directive (92/43/EEC). Although widely distributed and considered of Least Concern at global level

(YAMAGUCHI *et al.* 2015), this species has suffered population declines and range fragmentation in Europe, mainly due to habitat reduction and persecution (NOWELL & JACKSON 1996, SUNQUIST & SUNQUIST 2002). The species is also threatened by vulnerability to pathologies and, importantly, by hybridisation with feral domestic cats (LECIS

et al. 2006). In Italy *Felis silvestris* is classified as Near Threatened according to IUCN Red List categories (RONDININI *et al.*, 2013). Italian populations of *F. silvestris* (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2013) are considered a genotypic stronghold of this species in Europe as they are among the least genetically admixed throughout their range (LECIS *et al.* 2006).

A relevant obstacle to the conservation of wildcats in some European countries is the lack of adequate data on the spatial distribution and basic ecological requirements, particularly habitat and landscape.

The wildcat has been traditionally described as associated with forest habitats in Europe (BIRÓ *et al.* 2005; HARTMANN *et al.* 2013; KLAR *et al.*, 2008; PIECHOCKI 1990); however studies conducted at the beginning of this century suggested the importance of scrubland and mosaic landscapes for wildcats in Mediterranean areas (e.g. LOZANO *et al.* 2003, 2010; MONTERROSO *et al.* 2009).

In Italy a very few investigations of the habitat ecology and distribution of the wildcat were available in the early 2000s, especially in the Southern regions. The National Park of Cilento and Vallo di Diano and its buffer zones, cover an area of about 3000 square kilometers, located in the south of the Italian peninsula (Salerno province). This protected area is characterized by a low human density and a heterogeneous landscape that includes large forested areas in the interior of the park, scrubland and cultivated areas at lower altitudes towards the coast. These conditions offer the opportunity to evaluate the relative importance of forested areas for wildcats at an adequate spatial scale.

In attempting to reduce the gap of knowledge on distribution and habitat requirements of the wildcat in Southern Italian peninsula, a camera-trapping research project was conducted in 2008-2010 in the National Park of Cilento and Vallo di Diano, Campania region. (FUSILLO & MARCELLI 2014).

Camera-trapping is a powerful non-invasive method for sampling mammals. Its use in wildlife studies has grown exponentially in recent decades (O'CONNELL *et al.* 2011) in conjunction with the technological advance of these devices and the development of methods for estimating population parameters from photographic observations (e.g. LINDEN *et al.* 2017). For species that cannot be individually identified, as the majority of carnivore species, camera-trapping still allows the easy collection of detection/non-detection data for the estimation of occupancy as a surrogate for abundance or density (MACKENZIE *et al.* 2006; ELLIS, IVAN & SCHWARTZ 2014). Occupancy modeling

estimates the probability of site occupation by a species and the detection probability of a species given its presence. This modelling approach accounts for imperfect detection of the species (i.e. the species is present at a site but it is not detected), enabling an unbiased estimation of the relationships between occupancy and habitat features (e.g. WINTLE *et al.* 2005).

Here we report the main results and conclusions of the study conducted in the NPCVD. Our aims were to evaluate the role of forest habitats in the site occupancy pattern of the felid and provide information applicable to conservation of forest ecosystems in the protected area.

We investigated the relationship between the probability that a site is occupied by the species and habitat amount, structure and quality in an area approximating the species home range.

We hypothesized that wildcats establish the home range in landscapes with a higher percentage of forest cover than unoccupied areas. We also evaluated the importance of habitat ecotones and unmanaged-mature forests on wildcat occupancy. Moreover, we used the density of livestock as an index of impacts of free grazing on forest habitat, as a covariate for wildcat occupancy.

METHODS

Study area

The study area (1020 km²) included three adjacent Natura 2000 sites (Sites of Community Importance or SCIs IT8050030 “Monte Sacro e dintorni”, IT8050024 “Monte Cervati, Centaurino e Montagne di Laurino”, and IT8050022 “Montagne di Casalbuono”) dominated by forests, and an area of heterogeneous habitats characterized by Mediterranean maquis (shrublands), mixed forests and small agricultural fields (Fig. 1).

Forests in the SCIs were mainly native single-species stands of *Fagus sylvatica* (13% of the study area), *Quercus cerris* (23%) and *Alnus cordata* (9%); most were managed as high forests and had no signs of recent logging (mature or “Near old-growth” forests). Mixed woods made up 15% of the study area and scrublands 28%. Woods of *Q. ilex* covered 7% of the study area.

Human density averaged 67 inhabitants/km² (range 12 – 511 inh./km²) at the township level (ISTAT, 2005). Elevations of camera trapping sites range from 83 to 1396 m a.s.l.

Camera-trapping

Seventy-one camera trap stations were randomly placed in the study area between December 2008 and June 2010. Camera trap sites

were located ≥ 2 km apart in potential habitats for the wildcat. Potential habitat were identified by a GIS analysis of a vegetation cover map of the Park and its buffer zones. One camera trap was set up per station. We used Cuddeback Capture 3.0 and Natura Service Fototrap DFV. Both these cameras have PIR sensor and white flash capturing colour images at night. We fixed each camera trap to a tree 2 m from the targeted area, usually with the sensor 20-30 cm off the ground. Camera traps were set across evident animal trails. Nevertheless, we used canned mackerel bait and both catnip and valerian tincture as scent lures to attract animals to the trapping station and increase the probability of photographic capture.

At each station a camera trap was active for 7 weeks on average (range 2 – 21 weeks). Stations equipped with Fototrap DFV were visited approximately bi-weekly to replace batteries. Cuddeback cameras were visited bi-monthly to remove them, or in some cases, to replace batteries and extend the period of deployment. On these occasions we also re-applied scent lures. Therefore scent lures were renewed less frequently in the Cuddeback stations.

Wildcat identification

We identified cat images captured by camera traps as wildcats when the coat colour and marking pattern matched those reported in RAGNI & POSSENTI (1996) and BEAUMONT *et al.* (2001).

Occupancy modeling and habitat analysis

We fit single-season occupancy models (MACKENZIE *et al.* 2006) to examine the relationships between wildcat probability of use (ψ) of a sampling site (i.e., the camera field of view) and habitat factors, while accounting for detection probability (p ; MACKENZIE *et al.* 2006). We interpreted the occupancy parameter as the probability the site is used (i.e., the sampling site is included in a least one home range) because the sampling site is much smaller than a wildcat home range. Models were fitted to detection histories constructed on a 7 days basis. For each site we assigned 1 (detection) or 0 (non-detection) to consecutive 7 days periods with or without ≥ 1 images of wildcats. Thus, the parameter p is the probability to capture at least one wildcat image in a 7-days camera trapping interval.

We considered a set of landscape variables to evaluate model predictions of competing a

Fig. 1 - Study area and camera trapping sites

priori hypotheses about wildcat habitat selection. Preliminary modeling revealed no importance of anthropogenic variables (e.g., human density, distance to roads) on wildcat use, and we did not consider those further. We used the vegetation map of the CVD National Park 1:25.000 (BLASI *et al.* 2008) to derive raster maps (cell size 100 m) of the following vegetation categories: 1) Forests. It included all forest types mapped in the study area, irrespective of their management, tree composition or age structure; 2) High forests. This layer included singles-species stands of *Fagus sylvatica*, *Alnus cordata* and *Quercus cerris* widely unaffected by recent management practices or logging. Several stands were classified as “Near old-growth” (BLASI *et al.* 2008); 3) Shrublands. It included all shrubland types mapped in the study area, mainly represented by Mediterranean maquis; 4) Forests and shrublands. It was created by merging all forest and shrubland polygons, to represent entirely the potential habitat for wildcat.

Moreover, we used the Atlas of Municipalities (ISTAT 2009) to derive a raster map of the density of livestock (cattle, sheep and goats all together). The practice of grazing livestock in forests is common in the study area (pers. obs.). Grazing in forests may impact soil structure and vegetation; in particular understorey plants (trees and shrubs), and herbaceous layer may be absent or heavily modified (TASKER & BRADSTOCK 2006). We hypothesized that such alterations may reduce habitat cover and prey availability for wildcats.

We quantified the proportion of forests (variable “Forests”), high forests (variable “High-forests”), and the proportion of the total amount of forests and shrublands (variable “Habitat”) within a radius of 3 km from each camera trap station. At the same scale we quantified also the density of livestock (variable “Livestock”). We used the “Forests and shrublands” map layer to measure habitat edge density within the 3 km buffer as the ratio of the total perimeter and the total area of habitat patches (variable “Habitat edge”). We chose the 3-km buffer area because this spatial scale approximates an average home range of male wildcats (MONTERROSO *et al.* 2009; KLAR *et al.* 2008; ANILE *et al.* 2017). All variables were calculated using Arc GIS 9.3 (ESRI, Redlands, CA, USA).

We opted to examine the effect of all forest types on probability of use, rather than the independent (additive) effects of high forests and non-high forest types, to reduce the number of competing models and parameters. For the same reason we examined the overall effect of shrubs and forests (Habitat).

We developed 19 competing models for

wildcat probability of use by considering the additive effects of single vegetation proportions, edge density and livestock density. The model set included single-covariate models and a null model (appendix S1). We predicted site use probability to be positively related with forest cover and negatively related with livestock density. According to recent studies in Mediterranean habitats, we expected use probability of wildcat to increase with increase in extension of shrublands and habitat edge density. We modeled detection probability as a function of a binary variable that coded whether a camera trapping site had a single or multiple applications of scent lures. Rate of movement by wildcats on trails, and thus detection probability, could be a function of the amount of shrub cover and different types of forest. Therefore, to avoid misidentification or underestimation of factors predicted to affect site use (GU & SWIHART 2004, MACKENZIE *et al.* 2006), we accounted for the effects of forest and shrub covariates on detection. Thus, detection models included the additive effects of lure and the vegetation covariate included in the corresponding occupancy parameterization. As such, there were 35 models for site use and detection probabilities.

We performed AIC model selection to rank the set of candidate models in terms of fit and parsimony (BURNHAM & ANDERSON 2002). We used differences in AIC values between the best model (lowest AIC) and the other models to measure their relative support based on the data. We considered models with ΔAIC values ≤ 2 to be good candidates for explaining variation in data. The relative likelihoods of models (Akaike weights, w) were summed for all models with a particular variable to assess the relative importance of the habitat amount, quality and structure. To assess the magnitude of habitat effects we examined Bayesian 95% credible intervals obtained by the hierarchical parameterization of the lowest AIC occupancy models (KÉRY & SCHAUB 2012). Moreover, to account for model uncertainty, we computed the AIC-weighted estimate of mean occupancy across sites and unconditional SE (BURNHAM & ANDERSON 2002). Model averaged predictions and 95% confidence intervals for both occupancy and detection were generated across the range of the most relevant covariates.

We fitted and ranked models in PRESENCE 2.12.37 (HINES 2006) and R (R Development Core Team, 2019). We used WinBUGS (LUNN *et al.*, 2000) and the R - R2WinBUGS package (STURTZ *et al.* 2005) for Bayesian analysis. We performed average model predictions with the aid of the R “unmarked” package (FISKE & CHANDLER 2011) and an R code written by M. Marcelli.

Tab. 1 - Model selection results for the occupancy (ψ) and detection (p) probabilities of the European wildcat (*Felis silvestris*) in the NPCVD. Given are the relative difference in AIC values compared to the top ranked model (Δ AIC), the AIC weights, the -2 log-likelihood values and the number of parameters (K). All models with Δ AIC $<$ 2 and the null model for ψ , are shown. A full list of candidate models is provided in appendix S1.

Model	K	AIC	Δ AIC	AIC weight	-2Log Likelihood
ψ (Forests), p (Lure)	4	189.39	0	0.1593	181.39
ψ (Forests.), p (Forests + Lure)	5	190.16	0.77	0.1084	180.16
ψ (High-forests), p (Lure)	4	190.99	1.6	0.0716	182.99
ψ (Shrublands + Livestock), p (Shrublands + Lure)	6	191.1	1.71	0.0677	179.1
ψ (Forests + Habitat edge), p (Lure)	5	191.35	1.96	0.0598	181.35
ψ (Forests + Livestock), p (Lure)	5	191.38	1.99	0.0589	181.38
ψ (.), p (Lure)	3	195.71	6.32	0.0068	189.71

RESULTS

Camera-trapping

The camera-trap effort resulted in 5983 operational days over 71 camera locations (sites). We identified wildcats on 61 recorded photographs at 19 sites, resulting in 25 weekly detections (mean = 1.35 ± 0.58 [SE] per site) and a naïve proportion of sites used of 0.27. Wildcats were detected mostly at camera stations located in mixed forest stands (33%), in aged turkey oak stands (*Quercus cerris*; 33%) and holm oak stands (*Q. ilex*; 17%).

Occupancy modeling

We discarded 6 models that failed to converge in PRESENCE. Model selection results suggested some model uncertainty (Tab. 1).

However, most of the highly supported models (Δ AIC \leq 2) included the proportion of forest as predictor of wildcat site use. Indeed, the amount of forest was the most important covariate in determining site use, comprising 45% of the model weights; proportion of high forest ($w = 0.15$) and proportion of shrub ($w = 0.20$) provided poorer descriptions of habitat selection. Livestock and habitat edge density had lowest importance ($w < 0.13$) The weight of evidence for effects of habitat types on detection was overall weak, although models with proportion of forest and proportion of shrub ranked 2 and 4, respectively.

Model-averaged estimate of mean (SE) occupancy across sites was 0.716 (0.231). Mean detection probability was 0.084 (0.052).

The top AIC-ranked model suggested that wildcat use probability increased with the relative amount of forest and detection was higher at sites with multiple applications of scent lure. Bayesian 95% credible interval was above 0 both for the

effect of forest amount on use ($\beta_{Forest} = 2.750$ [0.076, 6.89]) and the effect of lure applications on detection of wildcats ($\beta_{Lure} = 1.213$ [0.379, 2.020]). Credible intervals for the alternative occupancy covariates included in the top ranked models included 0. Model-averaged predictions indicated high occupancy probabilities (> 0.80) when proportion of forest was > 0.52 (Fig. 2).

Model-averaged detection probability was 0.052 (95% CI [0.024, 0.109]) at sites where scent lure was applied only one time and 0.180 (95% CI [0.083, 0.348]) at sites with repeated applications.

DISCUSSION

Wildcat occupancy and habitat

Our camera trapping fieldwork was conducted during 2008-2010 and preliminary results on detection and occupancy probabilities of wildcat were published in an informative book (FUSILLO & MARCELLI 2014) edited by the Cilento VDA National Park. Although the use of occupancy models were growing exponentially during those years (after MACKENZIE *et al.* 2002), even in studies of carnivore ecology, our work represented the first application of this family of extremely flexible models to wildcat camera-trapping data.

Camera-trapping and occupancy models are probably the best approach for testing hypotheses about 1st and 2nd order habitat selection (JOHNSON 1980) in carnivores. Systematic presence-non detection data representative of a large area, that allow accounting for false absences, can be easily collected with camera-traps. Our study area was large compared to most of wildcat studies in Europe (but see LOZANO *et al.* 2003, 2010) and encompassed a heterogeneous landscape with single-species broadleaved high-forests, mixed

Fig. 2 - Model averaged prediction (with 95% confidence intervals) of the effect of the proportion of forests on the probability of site use by the European wildcat (*Felis silvestris*).

deciduous forests, Mediterranean scrublands and cultivated areas. Such conditions were particularly suitable for investigating habitat selection (*sensu* JOHNSON 1980) of the European wildcat *Felis silvestris*. In particular, our aim was to evaluate the role of forest habitats in the site occupancy (“use”) pattern of the species.

The wildcat distribution was not random in the study area, as shown by the analysis of competing occupancy models. We found a significant positive association between wildcat use and the proportion of forests. Specifically, the probability that a camera location was included in one or more wildcat home ranges increased with the availability of forest habitat in an area that approximates the size of a home range (3 km buffer).

Such results seem to support the general view of the European wildcat as a forest carnivore (see Introduction) and contrast with those of previous studies in Mediterranean countries. Some studies in Spain (LOZANO *et al.* 2003, LOZANO 2010) and Portugal (MONTERROSO *et al.* 2009) suggested the importance of shrublands and scrub-meadow mosaics for wildcats in Mediterranean areas. However, these investigations had limitations that may weak the generality of their findings (e.g., small sample size or study area, scat-based detections, unaccounted false absences).

In very recent years, other studies supported the importance of forests for wildcats even in Mediterranean landscapes. A radiotracking study in Spain and Portugal revealed differences in 2nd order habitat selection between sexes, although both females and males settled in areas close to broadleaved forests (OLIVEIRA *et al.* 2018). A selection for forests against shrublands and meadows has been recently found also in Sicily, Italy (ANILE *et al.* 2019). Differences in wildcat habitat preference in Mediterranean areas can arise from different compositions of local landscapes. Shrublands are probably important, in terms of cover and prey, for wildcats and other carnivores (e.g. MANGAS *et al.* 2008) in landscapes dominated by agriculture and open habitats (e.g., Spain); however, where forests are largely available, these probably offer a better habitat to the species, in particular broad leaved woods.

Some authors (e.g. SARMENTO *et al.* 2006, LOZANO & MALO 2012) suggested that broadleaved forests are more suitable for wildcats than pine forests, in terms of availability of prey. ANILE *et al.* 2019 in Italy reported a similar evidence. In our study area coniferous forests were represented by small and few patches and thus we did not included this habitat in our candidate covariates for occupancy. We provided evidence that single-species

deciduous high-forests were not better descriptors of wildcat habitat than deciduous forests with different management practices and structure. We thus revealed relative generalist habitat requirements. Nevertheless, our data supported the importance of deciduous woods for the felid, as reported in the above cited authors.

The estimated relationship between site use probability and the proportion of forests informed about a good tolerance of wildcats to relatively low forest habitat cover. A 0.5 probability of site use is reached for a forest cover of about 33% in the area of an assumed home range. In other words, in the study area the wildcat was likely to be present also in areas where the extent of forest habitat was reduced and the Mediterranean shrubland prevailed. However, according to model predictions, a small reduction in forest cover would dramatically reduce the wildcat use probability in shrub-dominated areas, with the potential for local extinctions. In such areas, fires and inappropriate harvesting operation or forest cutting can pose therefore significant threats to *Felis silvestris* and its habitat. The National CVDA Park should address management and conservation efforts to maintain residual forest habitats in shrub-dominated landscapes, by applying appropriate fire prevention measures and regulation for forest management.

We did not find any effect of the habitat edge density on wildcat occupancy. The habitat edge variable included both forests and shrublands and was a measure of the amount of ecotones between vegetated and open lands. Differently that in other studies (EASTERBEE *et al.* 1991, LOZANO *et al.*, 2003), we argued that ecotones are not a key habitat feature for the wildcat in our landscape. Moreover, our data supported the predictions that the overall loss of forest habitat beyond some threshold may be a treating factor for wildcats rather than a process of habitat fragmentation (ANILE *et al.* 2019)

High-forest proportion and livestock density effects on wildcat habitat use did not receive support from data. We hypothesized that high forests, “near old-growth”, could provide a number of structures (e.g. tree cavities, large tree branches, deadwood piles) for shelter and resting of wildcats. However, the European wildcat uses deadwood structures but also understory vegetation as resting sites, both in old forests and coppices (JAROSCH *et al.* 2010). In the study area, mixed forests have high understory cover that can provide as good shelter sites as structures of mature high forests. We used the livestock density as a proxy for the degree of grazing in forests and understory degradation. The lack of effect of this variable on site use suggested that grazing intensity might not be a substantial factor in wildcat habitat selection. However, our results may have been also

influenced by the use of an indirect descriptor of grazing intensity.

Deectability

The probability of capturing at least one image of wildcat during one week in a site used by at least one individual was low, and equal to 0.084 on average. As a consequence, during the deployment time of camera traps (on average 7 weeks), a small number of detections per site was collected. This situation influenced the precision of the relationship between forest cover proportion and wildcat use probability. Wildcats were not detected in 33 of 52 used sites, according to Bayesian analysis of the best occupancy model. Therefore, a high number of false absences contaminated the sampling. A naïve approach to the interpretation of the data would have concluded that the wildcat was present in 26.8% of the camera trapping sites, while the occupancy models we developed provided an occupancy estimate of 71.6%, correcting false absences in the data.

A low detection probability was found in several camera-trapping studies of felid species, included the European wildcat (see ANILE *et al.* 2019). Photographic capture probabilities can be improved by using lures and bait. Cumulative detection probability can be increased by increasing the survey length or in some cases, the number of camera traps established in large survey sites. In our context, the optimal survey length of the camera traps would be 22 weeks for an optimal cumulative probability of detection of 85% (MACKENZIE *et al.* 2006). However, in addition to the problem of site closure assumption (MACKENZIE *et al.* 2006)), our results suggested that extending the operational time of cameras may not be the best option for optimizing wildcat sampling. The application of lures every 15 days in 16 of the camera-trapping sites, increased the probability of wildcat photographic detection by 3.5 times. As this treatment was applied to only 22% of the camera trapping sites, the average photographic capture probability was found to be low. By re-applying lures bi-weekly to all camera trapping sites would have much improved our estimates of occupancy parameters. FERRERAS *et al.* (2018) showed that the probability of detecting a species after k sampling occasions (7 days each) where it was present, was highly improved with both lures and baits. In particular authors found that a combination of valerian extract and lynx urine was most efficient for detecting the whole mesocarnivore community, including rare species such as wildcats.

In a recent wildcat camera trapping survey in Scotland, valerian lures did not appear to attract any cats (KILSHAW *et al.* 2014), and similar lack of

effect was found by ANILE *et al.* (2009) in Sicily, despite that valerian was used with success in Central Europe (e.g. WEBER 2008, STEYER *et al.* 2013). We put both valerian and catnip extracts at the camera trap stations, therefore our results were not conclusive about which attractant is more effective for wildcats; nevertheless, we showed the importance of maintaining fresh lures at each camera trap location in order to increase the detection probability of wildcats.

In general, the reinforcement of attractants at camera-trapping stations has costs deriving from the need to revisit the sites after the deployment of the camera trap. However, a prolonged stay of the camera traps in the field represents itself a cost, because it reduces the number of sampling sites that can be activated when a limited number of camera traps is available. In the planning phase of a wildcat camera trapping study, the relative costs of the survey length and of the periodic reinforcement of the attractants should be quantified, choosing the most advantageous option. We believe that whether using or not using scent lures should be a pivotal question in wildcat studies, but this aspect has been neglected so far.

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Conclusions

The results of this study suggested that the preservation of forests, especially in areas with a predominance of shrublands, may be the most effective conservation measure for wildcat populations. From a methodical point of view, our results provided useful information for designing optimal camera trap studies aimed to investigate habitat requirements and monitor occupancy/habitat use of wildcat. The number of camera trap stations and the operational time of each camera in the field are key factors in optimal photographic sampling. According to our results, the use of effective scent lures can largely increase the wildcat detectability and reduce the cameras operational time, ensuring meaningful “snapshot” occupancy estimates with good level of accuracy and precision.

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Model	AIC	deltaAIC	AIC wgt	Model Likelihood	no.Par.
psi(F3),p(LURE)	189.39	0	0.1593	1	4
psi(F3.),p(F3, LURE)boot	190.16	0.77	0.1084	0.6805	5
psi(HF3),p(LURE)	190.99	1.6	0.0716	0.4493	4
psi(S3, LD3),p(S3, LURE)bootstr	191.1	1.71	0.0677	0.4253	6
psi(F3, HE3),p(LURE)	191.35	1.96	0.0598	0.3753	5
psi(F3, LD3),p(LURE)	191.38	1.99	0.0589	0.3697	5
psi(S3),p(LURE)	191.87	2.48	0.0461	0.2894	4
psi(H3),p(LURE)	191.88	2.49	0.0459	0.2879	4
psi(F3, LD3),p(F3, LURE)	192.14	2.75	0.0403	0.2528	6
psi(S3, HE3),p(LURE)	192.57	3.18	0.0325	0.2039	5
psi(HF3),p(HF3, LURE)	192.74	3.35	0.0298	0.1873	5
psi(HF3, HE3.),p(LURE)	192.74	3.35	0.0298	0.1873	5
psi(HF3, LD3),p(LURE)	192.76	3.37	0.0295	0.1854	5
psi(S3),p(S3, LURE)	193.09	3.7	0.025	0.1572	5
psi(H3, HE3),p(LURE)	193.13	3.74	0.0245	0.1541	5
psi(H3, LD3),p(LURE)	193.18	3.79	0.0239	0.1503	5
psi(F3, HE3, LD3),p(LURE)	193.34	3.95	0.0221	0.1388	6
psi(H3),p(H3, LURE)	193.73	4.34	0.0182	0.1142	5
psi(S3, LD3),p(LURE)	193.87	4.48	0.017	0.1065	5
psi(HF3, HE3, LD3),p(LURE)	194.53	5.14	0.0122	0.0765	6
psi(S3, HE3, LD3),p(LURE)	194.54	5.15	0.0121	0.0762	6
psi(HF3, HE3.),p(HF3, LURE)	194.58	5.19	0.0119	0.0746	6
psi(HF3, LD3),p(HF3, LURE)	194.61	5.22	0.0117	0.0735	6
psi(H3, HE3, LD3),p(LURE)	194.9	5.51	0.0101	0.0636	6
psi(H3, LD3),p(H3, LURE)	195	5.61	0.0096	0.0605	6
psi(HE3),p(LURE)	195.43	6.04	0.0078	0.0488	4
psi(.),p(LURE)	195.71	6.32	0.0068	0.0424	3
psi(HF3, HE3, LD3),p(HF3, LURE)	196.43	7.04	0.0047	0.0296	7
psi(LD3),p(LURE)	197.5	8.11	0.0028	0.0173	4

Appendix S1

Full list of competing models for site use and detection probabilities of wildcats.

THE EUROPEAN WILDCAT IN THE POLLINO NATIONAL PARK: WORK IN PROGRESS

IL GATTO SELVATICO NEL PARCO NAZIONALE DEL POLLINO: LAVORI IN CORSO

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Abstract. In Pollino National Park (PNP) is being held a study whose aim is to define, on a genetic base, the conservation status of the European Wildcat *Felis silvestris silvestris* Schreber 1777, and to check if there could be found, in short or long-term, risk evidences for its survival: proximity/superimposition of its home range with anthropic activities such as contacts with domestic cats (cross-breeding) or passages across driveways (road casualties) are highly probable. The study was carried out through a gradual and integrated approach of camera-traps and the collection of non-invasive biological samples (hair collecting) at first, and later capturing in-vivo specimen to be submitted to health control and genetic analysis. To all the captured individuals, belonging to the subspecies *silvestris*, was applied a radio collar GPS-GSM to define their home range composition.

Riassunto. Nel Parco Nazionale del Pollino è in corso uno studio volto a definire su base genetica lo stato di conservazione del gatto selvatico europeo *Felis silvestris silvestris* Schreber 1777, e a verificare la presenza di fattori di rischio a breve e lungo termine per la sua sopravvivenza, come la vicinanza/sovrapposizione del suo home range con attività antropiche dove sono più probabili il contatto con i domestici (ibridazione) ed il passaggio su strade carrabili (investimenti). Il lavoro è stato svolto adottando un approccio graduale ed integrato: associando la tecnica del fototrappolaggio prima alla raccolta di campioni biologici non invasivi (cattura del pelo), poi alla cattura di esemplari in vivo da sottoporre a controllo sanitario e analisi genetica. Gli individui catturati, risultati poi tutti appartenenti alla sottospecie *silvestris*, sono stati muniti di radiocollare GPS-GSM per definire la composizione dei loro home range.

INTRODUCTION

Between 2012 and 2017, as part of a monitoring project of the park's carnivore communities carried out through the camera-trapping technique, in 42 capture sites was taken an amount of 8600 pictures of wild species, 2800 of which were Carnivores. More than a half of these capture sites (N = 22) proved the presence of the European Wildcat *Felis silvestris silvestris* Schreber 1777 or of cats whose coat did not have evidence of pattern clearly leading back to domestic phenotype (RAGNI & POSSENTI 1996). Based on these results referred to the area of camera-trapping surveys, a first and partial map of the felid presence in the Park was developed (fig. 1). The following step was to check these data on a genetic base.

STUDY AREA

Pollino National Park is an area of about 192.000 ha between Basilicata and Calabria on a mainly mountainous landscape, with two most important massifs of Pollino and Orsomarso, and a third one, isolated in the North-West, the Mount Alpi. The Northern reliefs softly decline along the river

valleys of Sinni and Mercure-Lao, while the Southern landscape is rough and uneven with the deep valleys of Argentino, Lao and Raganello. Its surface at almost 60% is covered with wooded habitat (110.000 ha), 70.000 ha of them, approximately, are broadleaves.

Fig. 1 - GSE presence sites of in the PNP (camera-trapping 2012-2017)

METHODS

Hair Traps

In the years 2017 and 2018, starting from the sites with more recent cat observations ($N = 9$), with the use of smelling spurs (70% hydroalcoholic extract of valerian) and food (pasta with sardines, fish and, above all, chicken), were tested three different devices for catching animal hair (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2 - Devices for catching hair tested in the PNP in 2017-2018 – A: valerian hair trap, B: tunnel hair trap, C: wood air trap.

- A. *Valeriana hair trap*: wooden stake with velcro and 70% hydroalcoholic extract of valerian.
- B. *Tunnel hair trap*: tunnel cage with wooden stakes, velcro and food bait.
- C. *Wood hair trap*: open fence with velcro and central cage to protect food bait.

Camera-trapping and hair trap control, with substitution of SD card and restoration of food bait, was done on a weekly basis.

Live Trapping

In July 2018 the Minister of Environment granted to PNP the authorization to capture $n = 10$ samples of European Wildcat, as an exception to DPR 357/97, in order to monitor them through GPS/GSM for conservative purpose.

Fig. 3 - Double entry trap for small carnivores, 150 X 42 X 42, with tilting central platform and upper opening to release the animals.

Between January 2019 and February 2020, 15 capture stations in 10 different sites with tunnel traps 150 x 42 x 42 equipped with double entry tunnel traps 150 x 42 x 42 with tilting platform (fig. 3) associated to camera-traps were used (alternatively *Multipir 12, Cuddeback C1, IR plus BF 110, Scout Guard SG860C*). Counting on the strong territoriality of the species, it was decided to use, as an incentive, urine of domestic cat (either male or female), probably selective towards other carnivores.

The capture program, to be realized in autumn, winter and spring, avoiding the delivery and weaning period (May to September) was carried out by dividing the study area in two districts: Pollino and Orsomarso, managed by two different teams and sustained by a shared veterinarian. Once activated, the traps were controlled every day early in the morning, while the camera-traps were checked once a week or, exceptionally, to verify specific events (e.g., a closed but empty trap). The olfactory lures were changed at each control. In the event of capture, the general conditions of the individual (for example verifying the absence of wounds) were considered, then the cage was covered with a dark perforated cloth and the veterinarian was informed. At his arrival, the team had already executed a standard manipulation protocol, previously arranged:

1. The cats were moved from the capture cage to an enclosure cage with movable walls; here, by intramuscular injection, they were given anesthetic drugs. *The established anesthetic protocol of the first capture involved Tiletamina-Zolazepam 1mg/Kg + Medetomidina 0,05 mg/Kg + Atipamezolo (MAZZI 2008), while the others animals were given Ketamina 5 mg/Kg + Medetomidina 0,08 mg/Kg + Atipamezolo (WEST et al. 2014).*

2. When sedated, they were weighted and laid down in right lateral decubitus, covered their eyes to reduce visual stimulus and blocked their jaw with a lace to work safely. If their body temperature decreased, thermal towels, blankets and pocket hand warmers were used.

3. Their clinical conditions were evaluated, through teeth wearing sex and age were estimated, then biometric measurements were taken, the drawing-colour pattern observed and photographed and biological samples collected (a hematic sample with EDTA test-tube for genetic analysis, a hematic sample for serological analysis and a rectal swab and faeces for coprological analysis).

4. a satellite telemetry collar was applied (fig. 4).

5. If present, ectoparasites were collected and (for the two last captures) samples of hair from withers and abdomen for the cortisol dosage were taken.

6. At the end the cats were put back in the

enclosure cage and given them the Atipamezolo as antidote and the cage was covered with a shading cloth to reduce visual stimulus. The cats were observed at a distance enough to reduce stress, and then released when completely awake.

Fig. 4 - Ecotone satellite collar Felis GPS-GSM

RESULTS

Hair Trap

In the years 2017-2018, 730 pictures were taken in 9 different hair capture stations, 29 of them were cats (tab. 1) and only three hairs were picked up with *wood hair trap and food bait* (tab. 1).

Tab. 1 - picture catching with smelling spurs and feed in 2017-2018

Taxon	Capture with valerian	Capture with food bait
DOG	21	58
DOMESTIC CAT	0	2
WOLF	4	10
BADGER	17	26
FOX	100	270
SKUNK	0	3
MARTENS	0	15
BEECH MARTENS	19	156
WILDCAT	1	28
CARNIVORES	162	568

Live Trapping

During the first capture series, January to February 2019, due to heavy snowfalls, the trap nights were only 104. In the second series, carried out in two different periods, the first one from the 2nd to the 20th December 2019 and the second one from the 21st January to the 19th February 2020,

Tab. 2 - Trap Night January 2019 – February 2020

CAPTURE SITES	TRAP NIGHTS			TOT
	JANUARY-FEBRUARY 2019	DECEMBER 2019	JANUARY-FEBRUARY 2020	
POLLINO	97	60	61	218
GOREGHE	17	12	17	46
PRASTIO	18	0	0	18
SANTA ELENA	21	12	11	44
SANTA ELENA 2	11	0	0	11
VITO 3	15	0	0	15
MONTAGNA DI BASSO	15	12	11	38
CROCE PANTANA	0	12	11	23
VITO 1	0	12	11	23
ORSOMARSO	7	30	87	124
PIETRA CAMPANARA	0	6	18	24
TIMPONE FORNELLI	0	6	18	24
MARE PICCOLO	0	6	18	24
ROSSALE	0	6	18	24
FRASCINETO	7	0	0	7
NOVACCO	0	6	10	16
POVELLA	0	0	5	5
PNP	104	90	148	342

Tab. 3 - European wildcat specimens captured in the PNP between January 2019 and February 2020

Date	Capture site	Collar	Cat	Age	Weight
January 23, 2019	Santa Elena	FELT01	♂ VITO	2	4600
December 05, 2019	Vito 1	FELT02	♀ ROSARIA	4	2700
December 12, 2019	Montagna di Basso	FELT05	♀ MARIA	2	3150
January 31, 2020	Santa Elena	FELT03	♀ ERIKA	2	2700
February 19, 2020	Pietra Campanara	FELT04	♂ CIRO	6	2593

respectively 90 (60 Pollino and 30 Orsomarso) and 148 (61 Pollino and 87 Orsomarso) trap nights were realized.

In a total of 342 trap nights, three carnivore specimen were captured: beech marten N = 6, fox N = 8 and wildcat N = 5 (tab. 2 and 3)

Foxes and beech martens, after a quick control of their general health conditions, were released. Cats instead were subjected to the previously described manipulation protocol. Here below a summary of the examinations made and the proved circumstances in the different phases:

- ✓ **SEDATION:** in three out of five cases (*Rosaria*, *Erika*, *Ciro*) sedation was evident in 5-8 minutes from injection, with *onset* (stillness) in 10-15 minutes and *offset* (head lifting) in 40-45 minutes. Vito and Maria respectively were given one and two further doses of anesthetic to obtain a deeper sedation.
- ✓ **GENERAL CONDITION:** the captured samples were in good nourishing conditions, apart from *Ciro*, elder (5/6 year-old), thin and with dull coat. Maria, although she presented all young dental characters (reduced wear, crests on the canines and the shape of lower molar), had tartar on molars and pre-molars.
- ✓ **MANIPULATION:** each one took about 20-25 minutes for biometric measurement and coat pattern reliefs, blood sample and radio collar application.
- ✓ **BLOOD BIOLOGICAL SAMPLES:** each cat was taken of a blood sample for genetic analysis and was made a rectal swab, while only four of them were taken of a blood sample for serology. Faeces of three of them were found and picked up in their cages and the two last captured (*Erika* and *Ciro*) were taken some hairs from withers and abdomen.
- ✓ **RELEASE:** after being given the antidote, the cats gradually regained movement and coordination ability (8-12 minutes). They were observed

for about 15 minutes before being released in a suitable location close to the capture site.

The biometric measurements of the captured individuals (Fig. 5) were those reported in bibliography. All them were perfectly within the *range* described for the European wildcat (BOITANI *et al.* 2003). Noteworthy is the dimension of the first captured individual, a male of about 2 years old and 4,639 kg of weight. The coat drawing-colour pattern (Fig. 6) corresponded to the wild phenotype in all the samples that were captured (RAGNI & POSSENTI 1996).

Fig. 5 - Biometrical reliefs

The genetic analysis carried out by ISPRA confirmed that all samples belong to the subspecies *silvestris*. The search for *Toxoplasma gondii* antibodies (ELISA method), gave positive results for all samples; the antigen of Feline Leukemia Virus (*FelV*) was only found in a sample, while none of them was positive to feline immunodeficiency and feline coronavirus (tab. 4).

The cat positive to *FelV* was Vito, a 2-year-old male, of 4,639 weight, with mucous membranes and lymph nodes in the norm, no breathing or heart problems observed, and no signs of other diseases.

On all captured specimen was deployed

Fig. 6 - Coat drawing-colour patterns: dorsal view

a GPS-GSM satellite collar (fig. 7) to allow the monitoring by the Park Conservative Area working team, through the *Ecotone* web server facilities. Below the first processing of the *home range* of three individuals is reported:

- ✓ Vito (FELT01) captured on January 23, 2019
- ✓ Rosaria (FELT02) captured on December 5, 2019
- ✓ Maria (FELT05) captured on December 12, 2019

Fig. 7 - Ecotone Felis GPS-GSM satellite collar

Tab. 4 - Serological and parasitological exams made by the IZS of Cosenza on samples of the captured wildcats.

	VITO Felt01	ROSARIA Felt02	MARIA Felt05	ERIKA Felt03	CIRO Felt04
Parasitological examination	Eimeria Oocysts sp. Ancylostoma eggs caninum e Toxocaracati.	Unsuitable sample	Negative to helminth eggs and oocyst coccidia	no faeces	no faeces
DNA research for Mycobacteriumavium subsp. Paratuberculosis through Real time PCR in faeces	Not observed	Not observed	Not observed	Not observed	Not observed
RNA Corona Virus Feline RNA research through Real Time RTPCR	Not observed	Not observed	Not observed	Not observed	Not observed
Salmonella research spp.(cultivation method)	absent	absent	absent		
DNA research for Giardia intestinalis and Cryptosporidium spp through Multiplex Real Time PCR				Not observed	
ELISA virological Leucemia Felina	positive	negative	no serum sample	negative	negative
ELISA direct Feline Immunodeficiency	negative	negative		negative	negative
Antibodies anti-toxoplasma gondii research through ELISA	positive	positive		positive	positive

Home range calculation

The *Kernel Density Estimation KDE* is used to calculate the animal species *home range* and gives a density estimation of land use. The result of KDE analysis is a *raster* map representing the most used part of land. In calculating KDE it is very important to choose the right *bandwidth or search radius*. There are different methods to estimate *home range*, starting from the available presence data: in this study the *Silverman* function (SILVERMAN 1986) in QGIS 3.14 environment was used.

Two density using levels were chosen: 95% (95° percentile) to define the *home range* and 50% (medium for density) to calculate the core area. The results of the analysis are referred, only for Vito, to the period between January 2019 and May 2020, and between January and May 2020 for Vito, Rosaria and Maria (Figg. 8, 9, 10 and 11).

The calculated HR (*KDE 95%*) are as follows: Vito 3770 *ha* (3.611 *ha* in total), Rosaria 871 *ha*, Maria 376 *ha*. About the Core Areas (*KDE 50%*): Vito 1.380 *ha* (1.187 *ha* in total), Rosaria 483 *ha*, Maria 305 *ha*.

The overlapping area of the total HR (Kernel 95% JAN-MAY 2020) for Vito and Rosaria is 4,8%

for Vito's HR and 20,7% for Rosaria's HR (Fig. 12). The overlapping area of the total HR (Kernel 95% JAN-MAY 2020) for Vito and Maria is 8,7% for Vito's HR and 87,2 for Maria's HR.

So, between January and May 2020 Vito's HR includes the 20,7% of Rosaria's HR, the minimum distance between them was 800 mt and it was registered on March, 23. In the same period Vito's HR includes the 87,2% of Maria's HR and the minimum distance between them was 196 mt and it was registered on February, 24 (Fig. 13).

From the environmental point of view, the prevailing types of land cover, taken from *Corine Land Cover 2012 level IV*, are the forests of deciduous mesophilic oaks and beeches, which are either for Vito and Rosaria the 59-60% of the total (Figg. 14 and 15).

Both animals also stand in rural areas formerly occupied by riparian forest, where can still be found remains of natural vegetation along ditches and rows; these were often used by the male to move and rest.

For the other female (Maria) the forests represent 100% of her HR (Fig. 16).

Fig. 8 - Home range (KDE 95%) and Core area (KDE 50%) for Vito from January 23 to, 2019 to May 31, 2020

Fig. 9 - Home range (KDE 95%) and Core area (KDE 50%) for Vito January to May 2020

Fig. 10 - Home range (KDE 95%) and Core area (KDE 50%) for Rosaria January to May 2020

Fig. 11 - Home range (KDE 95%) and Core area (KDE 50%) for Maria January to May 2020

Fig. 12 - Spatial overlapping FELT01 (Vito) - FELT02 (Rosaria) and FELT 05 (Maria) January to May 2020

Fig. 13 - Minimum distance between FELT01 (Vito) and FELT05 (Maria) February, 24 2020

Fig. 14 - KDE environmental characteristics 95% FELT01 (Vito) - Land use categories *Corine Land Cover 2012 IV level*

Fig. 15 - KDE environmental characteristics 95% FELT02 (Rosaria) - Land use categories *Corine Land Cover 2012 IV level*

Fig. 1 - KDE environmental characteristics 95% FELT05 (Maria) - Land use categories *Corine Land Cover 2012 IV level*

DISCUSSION

The trials on the techniques for collecting hair suggested that the most efficient capture device was the *wood hair trap* used with food bait. On the contrary, valerian as an attractant resulted inefficient. On a total of 29 wildcat observations, only one was made with the use of this incentive, and the picture shows an absolutely casual passage. More generally, from a costs/benefits point of view, the hair capture showed not to be very convenient.

Instead, the traditional capture *in-vivo* with cassette traps and smelling incentive (urine of male or female domestic cat) was very efficient, with a Capture Index of 0,015 in 342 trap nights, which seems to be very encouraging if compared with the 0,029 obtained in 1995 in the Maremma Regional Park for 700 trap nights, with food incentive (live breeding quails).

The use of the enclosure cage with movable wall allowed to immobilize the cats very quickly, to give them drugs safely, and to reduce the stress exposition time. The capture protocol proved to be always very efficient, in fact no wildcat had problems resulting from narcosis or manipulation (BIZZARRI *et al.*, 2010).

During the first weeks following the release of Vito (FELT01) there was a lower number of localizations (fixes) than expected. It was probably due to the extensive vegetation cover of the areas frequented by the wildcat, that prevented a suitable

power supply to the battery photovoltaic charging process.

In particular situations the battery charge level reaches a critical point: the GPS receiver needs a quite high power and the poor satellite signal coverage in ravine and hiding places quickly strains the small devices batteries.

Following these observations, the Ecotone Company made some changes to other satellite collars that were not in use; by modifying the software implementation in the managing of the “motion” mode the waste of energy in its search for the GPS signal was reduced, stopping the search for satellites from the receiver when animals activity is scarce or completely absent.

However, in spite of such changes, the satellite collars gave a lower number of fixes than expected.

A first elaboration of the home ranges, only related to three samples and to a given period, suggests that the broadleaved forest is the predominant habitat (Vito and Rosaria) or the unique one (Maria), but also a regular use of rural areas for the first two animals (about 40% of total HR), which sometimes move towards isolated houses, using parts of riparian forest as a shelter or passageway. Between January and May 2020 the two females HR have wide spatial overlapping as the male, but they are not mutual. In particular it is very interesting the space/time overlapping between Vito and Maria in the reproductive period (February 24, 2020) with a minimum distance of 196 mt.

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INTEGRATING INSTITUTIONAL DATA COLLECTION AND COLLABORATIVE MONITORING: THE ITALIAN WILDCAT PROJECT

COME INTEGRARE LA RACCOLTA DATI ISTITUZIONALE E IL MONITORAGGIO COLLABORATIVO: IL PROGETTO GATTO SELVATICO ITALIA

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Abstract. Over the past decades, advances in technology have radically changed the way environmental data collection can be performed. Web-based facilities and smartphone apps have become increasingly common, considerably widening the opportunities offered to contribute to monitoring activities. Biodiversity data gathering solutions inspired by citizen science principles have been successfully applied to several species, whose monitoring greatly benefitted from a network of potential observers. The time is ripe to widen the range of application of these potentialities to less easy-to-monitor species. The Italian Wildcat Project (www.gattoselvatico.it) is the first experience in Italy of a country-wide survey that builds upon the double remit of institutional wildlife monitoring and citizen science data collection, aiming at taking the most from the combination of both fields. A similar effort is only made possible by a network of private and public entities at the regional and national level and by the participation of passionate citizen scientists. An example to be possibly extended to other species of conservation concern.

Riassunto. Negli ultimi decenni i progressi tecnologici hanno cambiato radicalmente il modo in cui può essere effettuata la raccolta di dati ambientali. Soluzioni basate su piattaforme internet e app per smartphone sono diventate sempre più comuni, ampliando notevolmente le opportunità offerte per contribuire ad attività di monitoraggio. Le soluzioni per la raccolta di dati sulla biodiversità ispirate ai principi della citizen science sono state applicate con successo su diverse specie, per le quali il monitoraggio ha beneficiato notevolmente di una rete di potenziali osservatori. I tempi sono maturi per ampliare il campo di applicazione di queste potenzialità a specie meno facili da monitorare. Il progetto Gatto Selvatico Italia (www.gattoselvatico.it) è la prima esperienza nazionale di un'indagine ad ampio livello che si basa sul duplice apporto del monitoraggio istituzionale della fauna selvatica e della raccolta di dati da citizen science, con l'obiettivo di trarre il massimo dalla combinazione di entrambi i settori. Un simile sforzo è reso possibile solo dalla collaborazione di una rete di enti pubblici e privati a livello regionale e nazionale, oltre che dalla partecipazione di appassionati cittadini-scienziati. Un esempio da estendere eventualmente ad altre specie di interesse conservazionistico.

INTRODUCTION

Most Felids are known to be elusive species, whose detectability in the field is often limited by several factors (e.g. mainly crepuscular or nocturnal activity, low population densities, preference for dense cover; SUNQUIST & SUNQUIST, 2002). Gathering reliable data on their presence and distribution can hence be a demanding activity, hard to be carried out at a wide scale and in the long term. The European wildcat provides a leading example in this respect (KILSHAW *et al.* 2015). Historical national maps of the species suffered from paucity of data and were produced as a compendium of several information of different nature, unevenly distributed in time and space.

Mapping its presence at regional or national scale and gathering insights on its population trend is furtherly made complex by the indisputable difficulty to correctly identify the species. Limited number of field researches trained on the species,

low population densities and consequent poor availability of first hand observations left no other solutions than relying on expert-based mapping and trends estimation.

Nevertheless, over the past decade, advances in technology have radically changed the way environmental monitoring can be performed. Web-based facilities and smartphone apps have become increasingly common, considerably widening the opportunities offered to data collection. Biodiversity data gathering solutions inspired by citizen science principles have been successfully applied to several species, whose monitoring greatly benefitted from a network of potential observers (POCOCK *et al.* 2013).

CITIZEN SCIENCE AND WILDLIFE MONITORING

Citizen science can be defined as the non-professional involvement of volunteers in the scientific process (commonly in data collection, but it could also include other phases of the research

process). As highlighted by a recent report (EUROPEAN COMMISSION 2020), the active involvement of people in the collection of environmental data is an emerging field of growing potentiality. EU and Member State authorities are already making use of citizen science data in the context of official environmental monitoring and reporting in several policy areas, such as to monitor the progress on the United Nations sustainable development goals, SDGs).

In some environmental areas, such as biodiversity, citizen science already provides large datasets on indicator species like butterflies (the European butterfly monitoring scheme: <https://butterfly-monitoring.net>) and birds (the pan-European common bird monitoring scheme: <https://pecbms.info>), hence demonstrating a great potential of application on other taxonomic groups. The need for complementary data was identified in the Commission's 2017 fitness check of reporting and monitoring of EU environment policy (COM 2017). That review concluded that tapping into new sources of data, including data collected by members of the public, could help to improve and streamline reporting, and make it more reliable, thereby strengthening the evidence base for environmental policy.

Member States have indeed used observations from volunteers and conservation groups at national or international level (e.g. Birdlife) for official reporting under Article 12 of the Birds Directive 2009/147/EC and Article 17 of the Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC. Several biodiversity indicators used to measure progress towards the targets in the EU's biodiversity strategy and the Aichi targets in the 2011-2020 strategic plan for biodiversity (i.e. the streamlined European biodiversity indicators, SEBIs) heavily rely on observations by volunteers.

Citizen science has hence the potentiality to play a role of growingly importance (EUROPEAN COMMISSION 2020), even in traditionally less explored contexts.

In many cases the contribution can be really valuable, especially in those circumstances where the official monitoring alone could not produce the number of observations and the geographical and temporal coverage needed, actually reachable by thousands of volunteers.

Several leading examples on different species provide evidence that "traditional" wildlife monitoring can be effectively enhanced by data collection carried out with the help of people. Among others, a couple of recent papers on the subject (VAN DER WAL *et al.* 2015; ZAPPONI *et al.* 2017), for example, provide evidence from the UK and Italy (respectively on two species of bumblebees and

some species of xylophagous beetles) that citizen science data can effectively fill gaps of knowledge, spatially and temporarily complementing expert data. Remarkably, in the latter case this achievement also allowed reaching reliable results in a much shorter time span. Several other examples come from CS projects on Mammals, where volunteers can play a major role in supporting researchers, both directly in the field (by collecting first-hand data) or from their home, by offering their free time to interpret photos, identify patterns in pictures, and so on (SWANSON *et al.* 2015). The internet and modern smartphones offer technological solutions able to empower anyone e.g. to take a high quality picture and a quite precise GPS position (often associated with relevant metadata) and to send them in real time to on-line databases. Mobile devices are also capable of running specific software and web services (including maps, AI applications and dedicated sensors). Most of these features were hard to be even only imagined no more than ten years ago. Nowadays e.g. orangutan nests can be spotted through small scale aerial surveys whose pictures can be identified by volunteers, enhancing the researcher's capability to identify and protect them with specific forest conservation measures (KNOTT *et al.* 2021), endangered Koalas can be monitored and their populations estimated through a specific citizen science project (Hollow *et al.*, 2015), just to provide some samples.

The development and diffusion of modern camera traps, for example, had the effect of a real revolution, empowering researchers as well as passionate citizens with flexible and rather powerful tools to be used widely in the field. Early solutions to take pictures of wildlife in their natural habitat have been in use for over a century, since the beginnings of wildlife photography. Nevertheless, as a wildlife research tool they remained limited to a small number of users until the 1990s, when the first commercial devices were produced and began to spread. Modern digital camera traps came to prominence from the mid-2000s, soon becoming a standard tool (WEARN & GLOVER-KAPPER 2017).

Today, beside professional researchers, a growing number of people are using camera traps in the field, for many different purposes. This wide potential constitutes a virtually very useful and interesting source of information that deserves to be enhanced and correctly managed.

Many research institutions, Environmental Agencies and national biodiversity networks have developed solutions to feed citizen science data into their official databases to inform and complement policy decisions. One of the leading examples in this respect is the UK National

Biodiversity Network, a membership organisation built on principles of collaboration and sharing. Its vision is that: “Biological data collected and shared openly by the Network are central to learning and understanding biodiversity and are critical to all decision-making about nature and the environment.” To achieve that vision the Network must deliver improvements to the recording, collection, verification, curation, aggregation, analysis and use of biological observations, including citizen science data.

In Italy the Ministry of the Environment and the Protection of the Territory and the Sea (currently Ministry of Ecological Transition) has promoted the NNB: “National Biodiversity Network” (Network Nazionale per la Biodiversità: www.nnb.isprambiente.it/en), which carries out a strong joint action in support of the National Strategy for Biodiversity. NNB, managed by the National Institution for the Protection of Environment (ISPRA), is a network of internationally and nationally accredited entities for the management of biodiversity records, which share data and information on biodiversity. It is a shared data management system consisting of a central node, which allows to perform search and management operations on the data, and peripheral nodes (databases that possess primary biodiversity data) aimed at guaranteeing consultation and efficient integration of information on biodiversity. The databases owned by the individual nodes communicate through the BioCASE Protocol. The latter also guarantees communication with the international community, part of the BioCASE network. The Network also ensures interoperability with similar international infrastructures (LifeWatch, GBIF, etc.) and with the National GeoPortal, in accordance with the provisions of the INSPIRE Directive (D.L. 32/2010). Specific data entry solutions have been recently developed to implement institutional datasets with observation coming from the widespread and well known INaturalist app (<https://www.inaturalist.org>), through the APIs made available by developers.

STATE OF THE ART ON WILDCAT DISTRIBUTION IN ITALY

The European wildcat is a species of conservation interest, included in Appendix II of CITES, in Appendix II of the Berne Convention and in Annex IV of Directive 92/43 / EEC HABITAT.

The species shows a wide distribution, ranging from Scotland in the North to South-Eastern Europe, including some Mediterranean islands. It was once widespread throughout Europe, before several populations underwent a drastic decline during the

19th century, mainly caused by direct persecution and habitat loss (SCHAUBENBERG, 1970). In Italy the species has been protected by national law since 1977. In recent times it has slowly recolonised portions of its former distribution range and, more recently, it successfully colonised portions of the central-Northern Apennines that were not part of its Known historical range (RAGNI *et al.* 1994). The European wildcat is listed as a “particularly protected” species in Italy.

A recent revision separated *F. silvestris* and *F. lybica*, and ascribed the Sardinian population to the latter, further feeding the scientific debate on the taxonomic classification of the species. However the interpretation considered most correct by main authors and reported in several papers (e.g. RANDI *et al.* 2001, MATTUCCI *et al.* 2016), is that of a polytypic species, *Felis silvestris*, constituted by various inter-fertile forms. The three subspecies occurring in Italy are *F. s. silvestris* (European wildcat), *F. s. lybica* (Sardinian wildcat) and *F. s. catus* (domestic cat). Occasional crossing with the domestic cat is a proven fact, which is likely to occur more frequently at higher incidence in isolated populations and in expansion areas of the wild subspecies (MATTUCCI *et al.* 2019).

In Italy the wild European form *F. silvestris silvestris* is considered nearly threatened (NT), like the Sardinian form *F. silvestris lybica*. Their main conservation threats are road mortality, habitat fragmentation, poaching and the interactions with the domestic cat (*Felis silvestris catus*), that can bring both to hybridation and pathogenic issues (RAGNI 1993).

The species occurs in Italy in three main disjoint sub-areas: Apennine ridge (and ecologically connected areas) from Calabria to Romagna (with a recent expansion front along the Tuscan-Emilian Apennines up to Liguria, with currently only scattered data), Sicily (mainly the northern portion of the island), the North-East (Carnic Alps and Pre-alps, Tolmezzine Alps, Julian Alps and Pre-alps and Friulian Morainic Hills). In the last decade, these populations have expanded towards the west, permanently occupying the Belluno area, up to the Dolomiti Bellunesi National Park and the Grappa Massif. The Gargano promontory (Apulia) hosts a local population isolated from the main range of the species.

The historical sub-area of the species in western Liguria is still under study and needs confirmation with further recent objective data (see Gavagnin, this volume). In Sardinia lives the Sardinian (or African) wild cat *Felis s. lybica*. Little recent information is available on its current range.

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

Monitoring a species showing a secretive behaviour (along with low densities in natural conditions) on a large scale is undoubtedly a critical issue. The currently available European wildcat distribution maps show a highly fragmented range, with (often not interconnected) patches distributed over different countries. Remarkably, many regional maps have been built using records from diverse sources and/or following expert-based knowledge, with poor or limited confirmation rate over large portions of territories. This kind of data has also traditionally been the sole source of information to define the wildcat's conservation status (GIL-SÁNCHEZ *et al.* 2020).

Moreover, classically the output is mainly a static, large scale distribution map, printed in a book or a paper and difficult to update on a regular basis.

Italy is not an exception in this respect. A solution is needed to overcome what is a real limit to secure the basic knowledge to set up proper conservation measures. The Italian Wildcat Project aims at providing a solution to partially overcome this problem, building upon the huge potential resulting from the integration of data coming from official monitoring surveys (carried out by professionals, public authorities, protected areas, etc.) and occasional records collected by citizen scientists (roadkill casualties, occasional pictures and, remarkably, pictures and videos from camera traps).

The recent spread of camera-trapping has been already described above. However, the potential of the “grey data” regularly produced is still mainly untapped, cause records collected by a growing number of users, in the vast majority of cases, fail to be shared with the scientific community. Collecting citizen science opportunistic camera traps data is in fact quite a recent, although promising issue (HSING *et al.* 2018). A further increasingly common application of citizen science in this field take advantage from volunteer efforts to classify images. Citizen science has the power to engage the public in conservation

science and accelerate processing of the large volume of images generated by camera traps.

Nevertheless, at least in Italy, the two currently most common scenarios are photos or video privately stored or posted in thematic forums and (most commonly) on social media, with the multiple aims of receiving a confirmation on the identification, starting a discussion on the topic or giving wide visibility to the results of a personal hobby. This growing amount of data might be lost if not retrieved, verified and pooled into a wider comprehensive dataset aimed at the conservation of the species.

Available interoperability solutions allow a reliable combination of records from different sources. Although pictures or videos not systematically taken may have several limitations in terms of their scientific use, if correctly verified and integrated with official records, they can represent a relevant source of information, able to fulfil basic data implementation needs, complement the knowledge-base of a species' distribution and address future studies.

The time is ripe to widen the range of application of these potentialities to less easy-to-monitor species, as the European wildcat.

The Italian Wildcat Project aims at creating a national network of potential contributors, recovering and classifying their “grey data” to integrate them with official records that underwent the same classification process, for the sake of creating a country-wide dataset openly viewable in a live map, constantly updated (Fig. 1).

The core of the historical data available on the European wildcat in Italy is that scrupulously collected and verified by the leading national expert on the species, the late Prof. Bernardino Ragni during his almost 40 years of scientific activity. His personal database will be integrated as the historical background of the project map.

Having an up-to-date picture of the distribution of the species to compare with historical data is indeed essential to evaluate variations of the range

Fig. 1 - process followed in the setting up of the Italian Wildcat Project

and to set up proper conservation measures. In the case of the wildcat (as well as other secretive species), it is crucial to integrate historical data with recent reliable observations collected by researchers, in addition to verified records from formal reports and occasional but verified observations.

The silver lining of the above is that virtually anyone owning photos or videos of the target species can contribute by sending the observations (together with ancillary data) to the system, using the "data entry" form provided at the dedicated page of the portal (Fig. 2).

Data entered are sent to a verification map and, once validated and verified (Fig. 3), become visible on a public map hosted by the platform www.gattoselvatico.it, in the framework of the National Biodiversity Network.

In the public map, to safeguard the sensitive geographic information concerning the detailed location of data (especially for those coming from camera traps) an automatic feature has been set up to limit the zooming function. Scrolling over that limit the selected points disappear from the visualization layer.

Users can filter data by classification feature (see below) and/or date, with a set of different temporal combinations.

Up to three pictures for any observation can be uploaded in the system, while videos can be shared providing a link to a cloud service hosting the files. Sightings with no photos or videos are not accepted, as they won't be verifiable. Operational fact sheets on various topics of interest are under development and will be available shortly.

<p>Data dell'osservazione</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 10px;"> </div> <p>Privacy video</p> <p style="font-size: x-small;">Indicare se rendere pubblico il video oppure no</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> <input type="radio"/> sì </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> <input type="radio"/> no </div> <p>Note</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; height: 20px; margin-bottom: 10px;"></div>	
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Fig. 2 - on-line data recording form, provided by ISPRA

Fig. 3 - data verification procedure provided by ISPRA: a) verification map; b) detail of their verification tools; c) public map showing verified data. Each colour corresponds to a different data classification category.

CLASSIFICATION OF THE OBSERVATIONS

Identifying an European wildcat only from phenotypic characters poses some limits, and for this reason the sole picture or video, whatever its quality, is not sufficient to determine with certainty the species.

Extension and disposition of black and grey stripes on the coat have a specific diagnostic value, showing a clear ontogeny and age-evolution. In the early stages of life the fur of the kittens shows a marked spotted pattern that evolves, over time, into the final one. Some parts of the drawings (evanescent) tend to disappear almost completely, while others (permanent) characterize the coat-color pattern typical of adult individuals.

To make the picture even more complex, the European wild cat (*Felis silvestris silvestris*) and the common domestic cat (*Felis silvestris catus*) belong to the same species. They are, therefore, inter-fertile, giving rise to fertile offspring. In nature, there are usually ecological and behavioral barriers that limit the onset of crossings, but in many contexts, especially in anthropized areas close to populations of *silvestris* or in newly colonized areas, mating can occur between members of the two subspecies, with consequent introgression of domestic genes in the wild gene pool. It follows that the reliability of identifications made only on pelage characteristics should be considered with great caution. The similarity of the coat colour and pattern of the wild phenotype to those of some domestic (tabby) cats

or their hybrids is a matter of concern, affecting the process of data verification. Where a tissue sample is available, genetic analyses can provide a valid tool to discriminate among the different forms (subspecies). Since the collection of tissue samples (from the dead animals, e.g. roadkill casualties, or blood from captured individuals, hair from hair traps or samples from stuffed specimens) represents the minority of data collected, evidences from camera traps (and, to a lesser extent, photos of road killed animals or occasional pictures) represent the vast majority of data sources usually available. Despite phenotypic indexes and genetic analyses respectively constitute a well experimented and increasingly reliable tool, pictures taken from camera traps, depending on several factors such as their positioning in the field, local visibility conditions, distance, position and movements of the individuals, etc. may introduce further variables, limiting the effectiveness of the classification procedure.

The objectively complex identification of the species and the potential phenotypical and geographical overlap with domestic cats and hybrids impose the adoption of selective criteria to build up distribution maps based on reliable data. To avoid loss of information and to limit the probability of false positives, a reliability categories system can provide a solution to classify the observations collected. Most large carnivore monitoring programs in Europe (e.g. KACZENSKY *et al.*, 2009; MOLINARI-JOBIN *et al.* 2012; MARUCCO *et al.* 2020) use the criteria defined “SCALP” to classify the quality of data collected on large carnivores. The SCALP (Status and Conservation of the Alpine Lynx Population) is a lynx conservation initiative in the Alps (www.kora.ch), that first developed standardized criteria for the interpretation of lynx monitoring data. Inspired by this approach, a similar set of criteria have been developed to classify pictures and videos of the European wildcat in the context of the www.gattoselvatico.it project. Namely, in the case of the Italian Wildcat Project, C1 are so-called hard-fact data, confirmed by genetic analyses and/or by gut index, C2 are wild phenotype individuals documented by photos, but not confirmed by other evidences, C3 pools individuals whose phenotype documented by photos is not totally visible or difficult to interpret, but might include some “wild type” characters, C4 enlist individuals whose phenotype shows some “wild” characters, but clearly not *silvestris* (potential hybrids), 0 are cats with a clear domestic pelage (Sforzi & Lapini, 2022).

PARTNERSHIPS

The Italian Wildcat Project relies on a wide network of collaborations, which lay the basis for

a shared approach, at the national and regional level. Moreover, it builds upon the double remit of institutional wildlife monitoring and citizen science data collection, aiming at taking the most from the combination of both fields. Project design, data structure and technical facilities are provided by a network made up by the Maremma Natural History Museum (Grosseto), the Ragni collection (namely the data, notes and materials gathered by the late Prof. Bernardino Ragni during his professional activity and recently donated by his family to the Spoleto Municipality to build up a dedicated collection), ISPRA (the Italian Institution for Environmental Protection, managing the National Biodiversity Network and running the Conservation Genetic Lab Unit at Ozzano Emilia, BO) and the Ministry of Environment (recently renamed as Ministry of Ecological Transition). An increasing portion of recent and current data are provided by citizen scientists uploading pictures or link to short videos (mostly from camera traps) through the form hosted in the portal www.gattoselvatico.it

Contributions are not limited to records from camera traps, but include also pictures of road-killed wildcats or occasional photos taken in the field.

Besides the partnership with leading national authorities, the project relies upon a regional network made up by associations, private and public institutions, protected areas and other entities that signed a formal agreement with the Maremma Natural History Museum, committing themselves to provide relevant support to the activities. That is intended as a constantly growing number of partners, depositaries of a remarkable local knowledge, essential not only to collect data, share archives and carry out surveys at the local scale, but also to activate a broader network of people (photographers, hunters, hikers, nature enthusiasts, etc.), enhancing the local participation of the public in the project and their sensitiveness for the conservation of this important species.

FINAL REMARKS

Setting up a country-wide survey requires time and energies. A similar effort is only made possible by a network of private and public entities at the regional and national level and by the participation of passionate citizen scientists.

In this respect the Italian Wildcat Project is the first experience of this kind in Italy. The success to the portal might pave the way to further projects on other species of vertebrates where a similar approach might result useful. That could help tapping into new sources of data, that can improve EU and local reporting, thereby strengthening the

evidence base for environmental policy. Scientific societies, Parks and any kind of realities interested in the conservation of the species in Italy are warmly invited to take part. That might act as an example to be applied in other European countries, in the framework of future collaborations that might share the structure, tools and data for the sake of engaging people, associations and institutions to a shared monitoring of the wildcat in Europe.

Moreover, while the output of the classical approach to distribution data (e.g. national or regional atlases) was static, large scale, distribution maps, with limited temporal value, the solution provided by the Italian Wildcat Project goes beyond it, enhancing the applicability of almost real time data. A step forward to monitor wildlife in the 21st century.

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INDICE / CONTENTS

BIZZARRI L. & SFORZI A. - Bernardino Ragni and the wildcat of the old world <i>Bernardino Ragni e il gatto selvatico del vecchio mondo</i>	3
MASSETTI M.- “Qui gatta ci cova” - A short natural history of <i>Felis silvestris</i> Schreber, 1777, in Italy <i>“Qui gatta ci cova” - Breve storia naturale di Felis silvestris Schreber, 1777, in Italia</i>	7
MATTECCI F. - Conservation genetics of the European wildcat (<i>Felis silvestris silvestris</i>) <i>Genetica della conservazione del gatto selvatico (Felis silvestris silvestris)</i>	27
FRANGINI L., FRANCHINI M., PESARO S., STRAVISI A. & FILACORDA S. - Cortisol and camera-trapping as useful tools to explore ecological aspects of the European wildcat (<i>Felis silvestris silvestris</i>) <i>Il cortisolo e il fototrappolaggio quali strumenti utili ad approfondire aspetti dell'ecologia del gatto selvatico europeo (Felis silvestris silvestris)</i>	35
CATELLO M., TORMEN G., DEON R., VENDRAMI S., LOSSO C. & RAGNI B. - The European wildcat (<i>Felis silvestris silvestris</i> , Schreber, 1777) in the Veneto region (Italy) <i>Il gatto selvatico europeo (Felis silvestris silvestris, Schreber, 1777) in Veneto</i>	45
CATELLO M., TORMEN G., DEON R. & LOSSO C. - The use of hair trapping and camera traps for monitoring the European wildcat (<i>Felis silvestris silvestris</i> Schreber, 1777) in the Eastern Venetian Prealps (Italy) <i>Uso di trappole per la cattura di peli e trappolaggio fotografico per monitorare il gatto selvatico europeo (Felis silvestris silvestris Schreber, 1777) nelle Prealpi orientali venete</i>	55
GAVAGNIN P. - The European wildcat in the Italian Western range: something new? <i>Il gatto selvatico europeo nel sub areale occidentale italiano: qualcosa di nuovo?</i>	63
VELLI E., SANTONI R., MATTECCI F., FAZZI P. & LUCCHESI M. - Population survey of the European wildcat in the natural biogenetic reserve of the Foreste Casentinesi National Park (northern Apennines) <i>Indagine genetica sulla popolazione di gatto selvatico europeo nelle Riserve Naturali Biogenetiche Casentinesi (Appennino settentrionale)</i>	73
FUSILLO R. & MARCELLI M. - Evaluating habitat use and detection probability of the European wildcat (<i>Felis silvestris</i>): a camera trapping study in Southern Italy <i>Valutazione dell'uso dell'habitat e probabilità di detezione del gatto selvatico europeo (Felis silvestris): uno studio di fototrappolaggio nel sud Italia</i>	83
CASCINI V., MARCHIANÒ V., OTTONE E., POERIO G., ROTONDARO F., SANGIULIANO A., SERRONI P., TEDESCO C. & VOLPONI S. - The European wildcat in the Pollino National Park: work in progress <i>Il gatto selvatico nel Parco Nazionale del Pollino: lavori in corso</i>	93
SFORZI A.- Integrating institutional data collection and collaborative monitoring: the Italian wildcat project <i>Come integrare la raccolta dati istituzionale e il monitoraggio collaborativo: il progetto gatto selvatico Italia</i>	103

